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EU-CEM Handbook for CCAM

European Common Evaluation Methodology
Handbook for Connected, Cooperative
and Automated Mobility

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Abbreviations & Terms

Abbreviation or Term	Definition
AD	Automated driving
ADAS	Advanced Driver Assistance System
ADF	Automated Driving Function
ADS	Automated Driving System
CBA	Cost-Benefit Analysis
CCAM	Connected, Cooperative, and Automated Mobility
CCAM project	A project that tests, evaluates or implements CCAM
CCAM system	Technology or service that enables Connected, Cooperative, and Automated Mobility
C-ITS	Cooperative Intelligent Transport Systems
COD	Current Operational Domain
Data owner	Partner in possession of data needed for evaluation
EC	European Commission
EU	European Union
EU-CEM	European Common Evaluation Methodology for CCAM
Evaluation	Systematic process to research the amount, value, quality, or consequences of an aspect related to a CCAM system and its use
Evaluation area	High-level category for topics addressed under evaluation activities
Evaluation level	The viewpoint of evaluation: (single) vehicle, (single) human, transport system, or society
Evaluation team	Partners responsible for the evaluation in the project
FOT	Field Operational Test
GDP	Gross Domestic Product
GDPR	General Data Protection Regulation
GHG	Greenhouse Gas

HMI	Human-Machine Interface
ICT	Information and Communications Technology
Impact area	Field of study addressed under impact assessment activities
Impact assessment	Evaluation addressing the broader implications of the CCAM systems and their use on people and society
ITS	Intelligent Transport Systems
MCA	Multi-Criteria Analysis
OD	Operational Domain
ODD	Operational Design Domain
PKT	Passenger Kilometres Travelled
Project team	All partners in the project
RQ	Research Question
Technical team	Partners responsible for implementing the CCAM system
Test site team	Partners responsible for setting up and performing the field experiment
TKT	Tonne Kilometres Travelled
TRL	Technology Readiness Level
VKT	Vehicle Kilometres Travelled

Executive Summary

This European Common Evaluation Methodology (EU-CEM) for Connected, Cooperative, and Automated Mobility (CCAM) is written for professionals planning and conducting evaluations for CCAM projects, as well as for project coordinators and proposal evaluators. EU-CEM provides guidance for establishing a solid foundation for successful evaluation already in the project preparation phase with an evaluation plan that is feasible to execute. The objective is to ensure high-quality evaluations that provide reliable input for decision- and policymaking in both the public and private sectors.

The EU-CEM Handbook aims to provide guidelines and best practices for planning and conducting CCAM evaluations, particularly impact assessments. EU-CEM can be applied in three types of activities: (1) ex-ante impact assessments, where it can help to prepare for CCAM deployment and uptake, or to identify unintended outcomes that may require mitigation; (2) ex-post evaluations, to assess the impacts of already implemented CCAM systems; and (3) the design and deployment initiatives of CCAM systems, with an aim to maximise societal benefits. The EU-CEM Handbook provides guidelines for three different phases of a project: Proposal writing, the starting phase, and the ending phase. It is important to recognise that this handbook is not a substitute for expertise.

CCAM can have impacts on the level of (1) single vehicles and (2) humans, on (3) the transport system, and on (4) the society overall. This handbook covers all four levels of evaluation, totalling 18 evaluation and impact areas. To be applicable for different CCAM evaluations, EU-CEM leaves room for projects to adapt it according to their specific scope and needs.

Chapter 1 'Introduction' of the EU-CEM Handbook provides the background and scope for EU-CEM. In scope of the methodology is higher automation in road transport of people and goods. To claim compliance with EU-CEM, the project must meet certain minimum requirements, such as including impact assessment activities, preparing an evaluation plan, and providing an explanation if any guideline in the EU-CEM Handbook could not be followed.

Chapter 2 'Guidelines for the project preparation phase' of the EU-CEM Handbook focuses on the essential steps for preparing the evaluation in a CCAM project, particularly during the proposal preparation phase and the beginning of the project. The guidelines emphasise the importance of scoping the evaluation to ensure that the commitments made in the proposal can be executed effectively. This involves understanding the overall project goal and the state of the art of CCAM, and being realistic about what can be tested within the project.

The chapter also highlights the need for a well-organised project structure and governance to manage the complexities of large, multi-partner projects. This includes defining clear roles and responsibilities, ensuring effective communication, and setting up processes for conflict resolution. The guidelines stress the importance of collaboration between the evaluation, technical, and test site teams to ensure alignment and successful project outcomes.

Chapter 3 'Guidelines for developing an evaluation plan' provides detailed guidelines for developing an evaluation plan in CCAM projects. The process begins with a clear description of the CCAM system under evaluation, including its operational design domain and service concept. This is followed by formulating specific, answerable, and relevant research questions that align with the evaluation scope and project objectives.

The chapter emphasises the need for setting up an iterative process of refining research questions, evaluating their feasibility, and prioritising them based on relevance, importance, and resource availability. It also covers the selection of appropriate evaluation methods, data specification, and experimental design. The goal is to ensure that the evaluation plan is feasible, realistic, and capable of providing reliable input for decision-making.

Chapter 4 ‘Evaluation-area-specific guidelines’ of the EU-CEM Handbook supplements Chapter 3. Chapter 4 is divided into four main evaluation levels, each containing several impact areas:

- **Vehicle Level:** This section focuses on the technical functioning and driving behaviour of CCAM systems. It includes guidelines for assessing software and hardware functionalities, performance, cyber-security, and reliability. Driving behaviour evaluation covers the vehicle's dynamics, the vehicle's interactions with the environment and other road users.
- **Human Level:** This section addresses interaction of people with CCAM systems, including user opinions, expectations, and awareness. It also covers people mobility, examining the effects on availability, access, quality, suitability, and affordability of mobility options. Additionally, it includes quality of life, considering individuals' physical, mental, social, and financial well-being.
- **Transport System Level:** This section addresses impacts of CCAM on the broader transport system, including services and operation, logistics, transport activity and fleet composition, traffic safety, traffic flow efficiency, energy and environment, and accessibility. It provides guidelines for assessing the impacts of CCAM on business models, logistics processes, total amount of travel and transport, number of accidents, collective traffic patterns, emissions, the potential to reach destinations, and so on.
- **Society Level:** This section covers the societal impacts of CCAM on land use, liveability, economic activity and employment, socio-economics, equity, and sustainability. It provides guidelines for assessing the spatial and functional implications of CCAM, the quality of living in studied areas, economic development, societal outcomes, and the fairness and inclusivity of CCAM impacts, and the sustainability perspective of different impacts.

Chapter 5 ‘Guidelines for reporting evaluation outcomes and EU-CEM feedback’ covers the reporting of the evaluation and impact assessment in CCAM projects. Reporting should be seen as an opportunity to reflect on the entire evaluation cycle, document lessons learned, and share insights with the different stakeholders. Requirements for reporting the evaluation methodology and its outcomes can vary depending on the study commissioner.

In conclusion, the EU-CEM Handbook provides a comprehensive framework for planning and conducting high-quality evaluations in CCAM projects. By offering detailed guidelines for various phases of a project and covering multiple evaluation levels, EU-CEM ensures that evaluations are well-coordinated, feasible, and impactful. The use of EU-CEM not only supports the preparation and execution of evaluation for CCAM projects, but it can also maximise societal benefits of CCAM and improve the usefulness of the evaluation results for decision-making in both public and private sectors.

The first complete version of the EU-CEM Handbook was published in 2025. The methodology is planned to evolve over time, incorporating new learnings and experiences. The next update is expected in 2028.

1. Introduction

This European Common Evaluation Methodology (EU-CEM) for Connected, Cooperative, and Automated Mobility (CCAM) is intended for professionals planning and conducting evaluations for CCAM projects¹, as well as project coordinators and proposal evaluators. EU-CEM provides guidance for establishing a solid foundation for successful evaluation already in the project preparation phase with an evaluation plan feasible to execute. The objective is to ensure high-quality evaluations that provide reliable input for decision- and policymaking in both public and private sectors.

1.1. Background

In 2020, the European Commission defined the Sustainable and Smart Mobility Strategy [1], with the policy ambition of large-scale CCAM deployment by 2030. To support the testing of CCAM systems, the Horizon Europe programme funded the FAME² project to establish a *European framework for the testing of CCAM on public roads* (Figure 1). EU-CEM is a part of this framework, providing guidance in the form of a handbook on setting up and conducting evaluations of CCAM.

Figure 1. Components of the European framework for testing on public roads.

¹ The term ‘CCAM project’ refers to any project that tests, evaluates or implements CCAM in road transport.

² FAME (2022–2025). *Framework for coordination of automated mobility in Europe* (EU HEU CL5-2021-D6-01-06, RIA, Project No. 101069898). Horizon Europe. <https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/101069898>

The FAME project supported stakeholder collaboration regarding knowledge sharing, consensus building, and facilitating data sharing in European CCAM projects. It built on previous projects: the EU-funded Coordination and Support Actions ARCADE³, CARTRE⁴, VRA⁵, FOT-Net⁶, and FESTA⁷.

Common evaluation methodologies have previously been developed for driver support systems and driving automation. The most well-known is the FESTA methodology, developed for field operational tests (FOT) of advanced driver assistance systems (ADAS) and other vehicle information and communication technologies (ICT). The FESTA methodology was written for systems that can be used by ordinary drivers in their daily lives over long periods of time. It has been successfully used in large-scale FOTs in European and national projects. The handbook describing the methodology has been updated several times (most recently to version 8 in 2021 [2]) and remains a valuable resource when setting up and evaluating FOTs.

With CCAM, a new approach for evaluation was needed, particularly where low technology readiness could not support such testing. Gaps have been identified in FESTA concerning its applicability for evaluation of CCAM. There are high expectations about the benefits of CCAM, including wide societal impacts, yet some concerns remain related to its use. Therefore, it is important to estimate the potential impacts of CCAM, even if FOTs are not yet feasible. EU-CEM was designed to evaluate CCAM systems at any stage of technological readiness.

A few methodological frameworks specifically for CCAM evaluation existed before EU-CEM. The Trilateral Impact Assessment Sub-Group for Automation in Road Transportation [3] made the first effort to harmonise approaches and vocabulary in impact assessment globally. However, as a high-level framework, it does not cover all evaluation steps. Projects under the EU's Horizon 2020 Framework Programme have built extensive evaluation methodologies, adapting the FESTA methodology for large-scale automated driving pilots (e.g. L3Pilot [5]). However, these methodologies were tailored for the specific project needs and are not generally applicable to all projects.

These frameworks include several good practices. At the start of EU-CEM development, CCAM projects were interviewed to identify successful practices, shortcomings, and lessons learned, beyond what was documented in their reports. Based on the underlying reasons for the challenges faced, topics for guidelines and the project phases requiring methodological support were identified, forming the structure for EU-CEM. In addition, project-specific best practices were generalised to be applicable to all projects. Thus, the insights and practices from the previous methodological frameworks and CCAM evaluations were adapted to establish the foundation for the common, generalised evaluation methodology of EU-CEM.

³ ARCADE (2018–2022). *Aligning research & innovation for connected and automated driving in Europe* (EU H2020 DT-ART-2018, CSA, Project No. 824251). Horizon 2020. <https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/824251>

⁴ CARTRE (2016–2018). *Coordination of automated road transport deployment for Europe* (EU H2020 ART06, CSA, Project No. 724086). Horizon 2020. <https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/724086>

⁵ VRA (2013–2016). *Support action for vehicle and road automation network* (EU FP7-ICT-2013-10, CSA, Project No. 610737). Seventh Framework Programme. <https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/610737>

⁶ FOT-Net (2008–2010). *Field Operational Tests Networking and Interaction* (EU FP7-ICT-2007-2, CSA, Project No. 224088). Seventh Framework Programme. <https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/224088> and follow-up Actions: FOT-Net 2 (2011–2014). *Field Operational Tests Networking and Methodology Promotion* (EU FP7-ICT-2009-6, CSA, Project No. 269983). Seventh Framework Programme. <https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/269983> and FOT-Net Data (2014–2016). *Field Operational Test Networking and Data Sharing Support* (EU FP7-ICT-2013-10, CSA, Project No. 610453). Seventh Framework Programme. <https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/610453>

⁷ FESTA (2007–2008). *Field Operational Tests support Action* (EU FP7-ICT-2007-1, CSA, Project No. 214853), Seventh Framework Programme. <https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/214853>

The first draft of EU-CEM was published for public consultation one year before its final version. Over 30 external experts provided feedback on the draft. To test the handbook with its target audience, a summer school was organised for junior members of CCAM evaluation teams. This feedback played a crucial role in finalising the handbook.

1.2. Scope of EU-CEM

1.2.1. Overall objective and scope

The primary objective of the EU-CEM Handbook is to provide guidelines and share best practices for planning and conducting CCAM evaluation, especially impact assessment. Within the handbook, **evaluation** is defined as “*the systematic process to research the amount, value, quality or consequences of an aspect related to a CCAM system and its use*” and **impact assessment** as “*the evaluation addressing the broader implications of the CCAM systems and their use on people and society*”.

The overall scope of EU-CEM is the evaluation and impact assessment of CCAM systems⁸. However, it is also beneficial for the development or deployment of CCAM when decisions between available alternatives are made based on their potential impacts. It is important to note that in such cases, clear objectives should be defined to allow ranking of the alternatives. This ranking is a political decision and falls outside the scope of EU-CEM.

The following objectives were set for EU-CEM:

- Ensure **high quality evaluation** of CCAM.
- Provide **common vocabulary and a common basis** for CCAM evaluation in different projects.
- Allow all CCAM projects to benefit from methodological **lessons learned and best practices**.
- Support **comparability** and **complementarity** of evaluation activities.
- Ensure **exploitation of results** of CCAM projects for future research and development.
- Ensure high quality input for **decision- and policymaking** supporting both industry and authorities.

EU-CEM puts particular emphasis on helping projects make robust and feasible evaluation plans in collaboration with those responsible for implementing the CCAM system in the project (referred to as the '*technical team*' in this handbook). Thorough planning and effective collaboration set the foundation for successful evaluation and project outcomes overall.

It is important to recognise that this handbook is not a substitute for expertise. Evaluation partners must possess the necessary (multidisciplinary) expertise in evaluation. This is also recommended for evaluation work package leaders. A common vocabulary is needed to ensure a shared understanding of the evaluation focus and objectives, the applied methodology and the results and conclusions drawn. To meet this objective, the EU-CEM Handbook is supplemented by the **Taxonomy for CCAM** [4], which contains the key terminology used in EU-CEM and CCAM in general. At the time of publication, the terminology of EU-CEM was aligned with the online taxonomy, which is regularly updated. For the latest definitions, it is recommended to refer to the key terminology from the **Taxonomy tool** provided in [the Connected and Automated Driving Knowledge Base](#).

Five high-level principles were developed for EU-CEM. They are related to setting the minimum requirements for evaluation (Guiding star principle), sharing best practices and lessons learned (Collaboration principle), using harmonised approaches (Comply-or-explain principle), encouraging agile ways of working (Agility principle), and being adaptable to project-specific needs (Flexibility principle). These principles are presented in Figure 2.

⁸ CCAM system may include a service concept or remote management.

Figure 2. Core principles of EU-CEM.

1.2.2. Type of projects and CCAM use cases within the scope of EU-CEM

EU-CEM can be applied in three types of activities:

- (1) Ex-ante impact assessments conducted before the full deployment, where it can help to prepare for CCAM deployment and uptake or to identify unintended outcomes that may require mitigation
- (2) Ex-post evaluations to assess the impacts of already implemented CCAM systems
- (3) Design and deployment initiatives of CCAM systems with an aim to maximise societal benefits.

EU-CEM is designed for large multi-partner projects but can also be applied to smaller ones. These projects may be funded by a customer, or they could be internal activities within companies or institutes. EU-CEM is most useful for projects where a technical team, separate from the evaluation team, is responsible for collecting (at least part of the) data in a field experiment, and especially if this is done at multiple sites.

EU-CEM includes guidelines for project-internal communication, which is fundamental to creating a feasible evaluation plan that aligns with available resources. In smaller projects, differing objectives among partners are less problematic, simply because there are fewer partners and communication is easier.

EU-CEM is mainly intended for projects addressing CCAM systems with the following focus:

- Automation in road transport of people and goods, covering all motor vehicle categories (specifically cars, trucks, shuttles, buses) and private, shared, and public transport
- Higher-level driving automation (SAE [6] level 3 and higher), with and without connectivity
- Use cases on public roads, automated driving systems with a specified operational design domain operating in mixed traffic.

Additionally, EU-CEM is suitable for projects that include, for instance, testing of safety-critical scenarios on test tracks to supplement on-road testing, or driving in confined areas where the automated vehicle interacts with humans or non-automated vehicles.

Projects focusing on technical testing or usability can utilise the basic guidelines for building a robust evaluation plan. Yet, it is good to acknowledge that EU-CEM addresses technical functioning and user aspects only from the perspective of providing necessary input for successful impact assessment.

EU-CEM does not focus on the following use cases: assisted driving i.e. low-level driving automation (SAE levels 1–2), automation of rail, aircraft and watercraft transport, and Cooperative Intelligent Transport Systems (C-ITS) without driving automation. However, it is worth noting that most components of EU-CEM are not directly linked to a specific use case but can provide valuable input for CCAM evaluation cases beyond its core focus.

1.2.3. Evaluation areas covered

CCAM can lead to different effects on the level of (1) single vehicles and (2) humans, on (3) the transport system and on (4) the society overall. This handbook covers all four levels. The EU-CEM Handbook provides evaluation area-specific guidelines for areas grouped under these four evaluation levels as described in Table 1. In this handbook, an **evaluation area** is defined as “a high-level category for topics addressed under evaluation activities”. These are technical evaluation, user evaluation and impact assessment. An **impact area** is defined as: “a field of study addressed under impact assessment activities”.

Table 1. Evaluation and impact areas covered by the EU-CEM Handbook and their scope.

Level of evaluation	Area	Scope
Vehicle	Technical functioning	Software and hardware functionalities of CCAM systems, especially in terms of performance, cyber-security, and reliability.
	Driving behaviour	Driving dynamics of a single vehicle, its longitudinal and lateral movements, and interactions with the environment and other road users.
Human	User	Interaction of people (CCAM users and non-users) with CCAM system; their opinions, expectations and awareness of the technology, and how they use it.
	People mobility	Individuals' potential and actual mobility choices; availability, access, quality, suitability, and affordability of mobility options.
	Quality of life	Individuals' physical, mental, social, and financial well-being.

Transport system	Services and operation	Business models and operation of vehicle fleets and transport services, effects on the operation of traffic management of the network.
	Logistics	Efficiency, effectiveness, and adaptability of the logistics process, changes in freight transport, and material flows in supply chain processes.
	Transport activity and fleet composition	Total amount of realised travel and transport; number and types of vehicles used.
	Traffic safety	Number of accidents ⁹ and injuries of different severities.
	Traffic flow efficiency	Collective traffic patterns, travel times and throughput on a road network.
	Energy and environment	Energy use and emissions of vehicles, air quality and noise pollution.
	Accessibility	Potential of population groups to reach destinations and services at different times of day; the potential of businesses, facilities, and other activity centres to receive people and goods.
Society	Land use	Spatial and functional implications, land utilisation patterns, including infrastructure development.
	Liveability	Suitability or quality of living in the studied area(s).
	Economic activity and employment	Economic development and labour dynamics, overall economic vitality, evolution of businesses and the job market, and skill requirements of the workforce.
	Socio-economics	Economic and societal outcomes of CCAM, benefits and costs, societal and economic value.
	Equity	Fairness, impartiality, and inclusivity, how impacts are distributed across different population groups, regions or generations.
	Sustainability	Environmental integrity, social well-being, and economic vitality, capacity to meet current needs while not compromising resource and opportunity availability for future generations.

⁹ During the writing of this handbook, it was noted that the terms ‘a crash’ or ‘a collision’ were often used interchangeably with ‘an accident’. It is perfectly acceptable to use any of these terms.

1.3. Structure of the EU-CEM Handbook

The EU-CEM Handbook provides guidelines for three different phases of a project:

1. **When writing the project proposal:** Chapter 2 provides guidelines for laying the ground for successful evaluation in the proposal preparation phase. It includes guidelines written for the partners responsible for the evaluation in the project (referred to as *'the evaluation team'* in this handbook), coordinators, and proposal evaluators.
2. **When the project starts:** Chapter 3 provides guidelines for setting an evaluation plan that is feasible to execute, regardless of the evaluation areas in focus (technical evaluation, user evaluation, impact assessment). Chapter 4 describes evaluation-area-specific guidelines to support this planning. Chapters 3 and 4 are intended for the evaluation team.
3. **When the project ends:** Chapter 5 provides guidelines for reporting evaluation outcomes, and for providing lessons learned, new best practices and feedback for future EU-CEM updates. Chapter 5 is intended for the evaluation team.

The role of each chapter and their outputs are described in Figure 3 below. The outputs include the project plan (Description of Action), an agreement on what data to collect and how, the evaluation plan, and feedback for future EU-CEM updates.

Figure 3. Role of different chapters of the EU-CEM Handbook (light green) and their outputs (dark green).

1.4. Compliance with EU-CEM

EU-CEM is intended for the evaluation of CCAM use cases in road transport with higher-level driving automation. One of the principles that guided the development work was flexibility. To be applicable for different CCAM evaluations, EU-CEM must leave room for projects to adapt it to their specific scope and needs. This raises the question of how to determine whether a project is compliant with EU-CEM. To claim compliance, the project must meet these minimum requirements:

- The project includes evaluation activities, specifically **impact assessment**, as defined in the EU-CEM Handbook (see the first paragraph of Chapter 1.2.1).
- The evaluation plan is prepared **by the evaluation team** following the guidance in Chapter 3, alongside the planning of all other project activities, at the beginning of the project. High-level planning is already conducted during the project proposal preparation phase, in accordance with Chapter 2. Specifically, the evaluation planning is not left until after the planning of potential field experiments, nor is it carried out by anyone outside the evaluation team.
- The guidelines of the EU-CEM Handbook are followed. If a specific guideline cannot be followed, an explanation for the deviation is given (comply-or-explain principle).
- A line of communication between the evaluation team and other project partners is established (and utilised during the project's lifetime).
- The results are analysed from a sustainability **perspective** in accordance with Chapter [4.4.6](#).
- The project utilises the Taxonomy for CCAM.
- The project contributes input and feedback for future updates of the EU-CEM Handbook and provides recommendations for future research needs in the evaluation report.

1.5. Outlook

The first complete version of the EU-CEM Handbook was published in 2025. The methodology is intended to evolve over time, incorporating new learnings and experiences. The next update is expected in 2028.

2. Guidelines for the project preparation phase

This chapter provides guidelines for preparing the evaluation in a CCAM project, focusing primarily on the proposal's preparation phase, but also on the project's initial stages. These guidelines help establish a strong foundation for successful evaluation. They specifically address topics that have proven challenging in previous CCAM projects. General project management issues that are not specific to CCAM evaluation are not covered, as information on these topics is available in many other publications. In addition to the evaluation team, the guidelines below are also useful for coordinators and project proposal evaluators.

2.1. Scoping of evaluation

The expected impacts of CCAM are wide-ranging. As it is not possible to assess all potential impacts, scoping and prioritisation are necessary. Finding agreement already in the proposal phase ensures that project partners share a common understanding on how to address project goals.

Scoping ensures that the commitments made during the proposal phase can be executed. That is, that the consortium's expertise and tools align with the project's scope and the scope aligns with the consortium's expertise and tools. Scoping is first required for the project as a whole and then specifically for the evaluation, ensuring consistency with the overall scope. The project proposal must clearly demonstrate how evaluation activities align with the overall project scope. The guidelines below cover the following topics:

- How to set the overall scope of the evaluation
- How to choose impact areas for evaluation
- How to build a consortium fit for the evaluation scope

Guideline 2.1. How to set the overall scope of the evaluation

The **overall evaluation scope** should align with the overall project goal and the overall project scope. Scoping of evaluation requires understanding the overall project goal and scope, the state of the art of CCAM, its potential benefits and adverse effects, and being realistic about what can be tested within the project.

Both the overall project goal and scope are derived from the call text by extracting the essence of the call, from the objectives that the client has for it. These objectives may include obtaining information for policy and investment decisions, facilitating and stimulating the learning process and knowledge exchange, and paving the way towards deployment of CCAM.

Note that in this handbook the term "*call text*" refers to any document outlining the expectations for the actions to be carried out in the project. This may include an EU research and innovation programme call text, any request for a proposal, or any other expressed wish of the client.

Define the **key terminology** in the proposal. Misunderstandings related to the interpretation of the call text or the scope of the project and evaluation are hard to resolve afterwards. For clarity, define what is excluded from the scope to leave less room for ambiguity, even if these exclusions are not included in the proposal.

The scoping of evaluation starts by specifying the **targeted level of evaluation** in the proposal: will it focus on the level of single vehicles and humans, the transport system, or society? The scope may extend beyond real-world testing capabilities. For example, if the project conducts field tests of CCAM vehicles in limited use cases, the scope of evaluation can still include broader impacts, such as regional effects.

The evaluation scope can be structured around **numeric targets**, expected **key impacts**, or **societal challenges**, depending on the call text. When the call text allows flexibility in scoping, stakeholder analysis or

consultation can help refine it. Ensuring alignment with a clear demand for new knowledge will maximise the project's impact and relevance.

The evaluation scope can also build upon earlier evaluations by addressing identified knowledge gaps, unresolved challenges of earlier projects, or expanding previous evaluations to new impact areas, scenarios or stakeholder groups. Additionally, the scope may include repeating certain evaluations to improve the validity and reliability of important impact estimates. This can be achieved with systems of higher technological readiness, larger or better-quality datasets (e.g. improved evidence from the field), enhanced tools or increased resources for evaluation.

In some cases, call texts may set unrealistic expectations regarding the impacts of CCAM. When this occurs, a balance must be found between responding to the call and making realistic commitments.

Example

Call text: "The overall objective of this call is to promote a wide market introduction of highly automated driving systems towards SAE level 4." [7]

The consortium sets the following overall goal for the project: "Make driving automation robust and reliable by taking intelligent vehicles technology to conditions and scenarios neither extensively tested nor demonstrated earlier in European and overseas traffic." [8]

In practice, the high frequency of take-over requests was identified as one of the main challenges in achieving this overall objective of the call. Consequently, the consortium decided to aim for "*defragmentation and extension of the operational design domains (ODDs)*" [9] by introducing technology enablers to support automated driving.

The overall scope of impact assessment was set to assess "the impacts of highly automated driving [...] and what is the contribution of the technology enablers on the impacts" [10].

Guideline 2.2. How to choose impact areas for evaluation

The details of the evaluation will be defined in the evaluation plan (Chapter 3). However, it is important to determine already during the project preparation phase which impact areas (overview in Table 1, full details in Chapter 4) will be covered and the main approaches for their assessment.

This early decision-making ensures sufficient resources are allocated for evaluation—especially for expensive or time-consuming approaches like field experiments, driving simulators, or extensive traffic simulations—and enables the formation of a consortium suitable to the task (see Guideline 2.3). Once the consortium and budget are fixed, flexibility in choosing the impact areas becomes more limited. Balancing what impact areas to cover and what resources to allocate to evaluation with other project activities is an iterative process. Prioritising impact areas based on their importance in addressing the overall scope of evaluation and the potential for impact allows researchers to allocate their resources and efforts more effectively. This helps to ensure the evaluation is efficient and the findings are relevant and impactful.

To choose which impact areas to cover, check the call text to see if it specifies impact areas directly or lists impacts or indicators that must be assessed. Then, assess whether the high-level scope set for evaluation determines the impact areas (see Guideline 2.1).

Both top-down and bottom-up approaches should be used when determining relevant impact areas:

Top-down: If the call text explicitly sets requirements for impacts that should be addressed, the corresponding impact areas should be included in the evaluation. This often means incorporating other impact areas from which input is required for the evaluation of those areas set by the call. For example, traffic safety impact assessment requires input from driving behaviour evaluation. If addressed, start with the

society-level impact areas, working towards the impact areas included in the transport system, human and vehicle levels.

Bottom-up: If the call text does not specify impact areas, the selection process can start from the CCAM system itself by considering how it directly affects road users and driving behaviour, and how these changes might affect traffic and transport and, ultimately, how they impact the whole society.

Drafting impact pathways, from aspects directly affected by CCAM to the impact areas in the evaluation scope, can help in this process by identifying linkages and dependencies between impact areas and levels of evaluation. Use theories and literature to establish these connections. The illustrations in Chapter 4 may be used as supporting material. Prioritise the areas where substantial impacts, benefits and burdens are expected. These pathways are a good tool to check against unrealistic expectations and ensure that the chosen evaluation scope produces outputs that can be delivered.

It is good to acknowledge that the impacts of CCAM can be so far-reaching that no single project can address them all. Therefore, it is advisable to **focus on fewer topics and evaluate them thoroughly**. The availability of resources for evaluation should align with the choices made and the estimated resources needed.

The impact areas described in this handbook (see Chapter 4) relate to one or more pillars of sustainability: economy, society, and ecology—or people, planet, profit. Understanding how CCAM systems affect sustainability is important. Regardless of the chosen impact areas, all projects are strongly encouraged to reflect on their results from a **sustainability** perspective. Guidelines for this are provided in Chapter 4.4.6.

Example

Top-down approach:

The call text mentions the following topics that the project should address: *Road safety, energy use, pollutant emissions, traffic congestion, equity*. The corresponding impact areas are included in the evaluation.

Next, the pathways to the listed impact areas are drawn. For example, to see how the impacts are distributed among different population groups (impact area: *equity*), it is important to know the most potential users and non-users, in other words, acceptance and possibilities for CCAM use (*user*) for different groups. Therefore, all these aspects should be studied separately.

Bottom-up approach:

CCAM influences comfort of travel and value of travel time (*user*). This leads to changes in travel patterns (*people mobility*), and consequently in vehicle kilometres travelled (VKT, *transport activity and fleet composition*). The impact on total VKT influences the total impact of CCAM on the *energy and environment* at transport system level.

Scaling up effects at single vehicle level (emissions per distance driven) to traffic flow impacts usually requires simulations, which need information on changes in *driving behaviour* for proper model calibration.

Finally, the impacts of CCAM on *sustainability* will be assessed. The sustainability perspective provides a way to draw overall conclusions of the impact across all results.

In summary, the impact areas chosen in this example, using EU-CEM terminology, are: *Driving behaviour, user, people mobility, traffic safety, energy and environment, traffic flow efficiency, equity, sustainability*.

Guideline 2.3. How to build a consortium fit for the evaluation scope

It is important to ensure that the partners on the evaluation team have the necessary expertise for the planned evaluation and impact areas.

Ideally, the evaluation scope and impact areas are defined first, followed by forming a suitable consortium to carry out the evaluation. However, in practice, this process is typically iterative, with adjustments to the project plan while building the consortium, to create a plan fit for the consortium and a consortium fit for the plan.

Including multiple partners with expertise in specific topics of the evaluation plan enhances its resilience and promotes in-depth collaboration. Relying on a single partner to deliver an outcome means there is a risk of not being able to execute the plan. It is recommended to consider alternative approaches already during the project preparation phase if the plan depends on a method or tool being developed by a partner during the project.

The evaluation team should collectively possess the expertise necessary for all impact areas and complement each other in skills and available tools.

Ensure key stakeholders are included in the consortium or consulted, for example, through an advisory board, if their input is essential to the success of the evaluation.

Example

The following list of requirements was identified for the evaluation team to address the planned scope of evaluation:

- Driving behaviour evaluation
 - Understanding of scenario-based evaluation
 - Tool scripting skills
 - Expertise in driving data analysis
- Traffic safety impact assessment
 - Access to accident¹⁰ databases
 - Availability of simulation tools specialised in safety-critical situations
 - Knowledge of injury risk functions
 - Expertise in mapping accident types to simulated scenarios
 - Understanding of indirect impact mechanisms on safety

Partners are matched to these requirements. It is verified that at least one, preferably two, partners meet each requirement and are willing to contribute, and whether expertise is concentrated in single experts within these partners. If the selected partners seem insufficient for a specific requirement, additional partners are sought to fill the gap. If this is not feasible, the plan must be adjusted accordingly.

¹⁰ During the writing of this handbook, it was noted that the terms ‘a crash’ or ‘a collision’ were often used interchangeably with ‘an accident’. It is perfectly acceptable to use any of these terms.

2.2. Project structure and governance

An effective and well-organised project structure and governance are important in CCAM projects, as these projects are often large and complex, involving numerous partners and long durations and increasing the likelihood of personnel changes during the project. The involvement of multiple partners in preparing and conducting experiments, as well as in data collection and analysis, adds to the complexity of the evaluation process. Even if different evaluation activities do not share the same precise focal point, their results should align to support a cohesive narrative. A well-structured project and effective governance help ensure this alignment.

CCAM is often studied in innovation projects with immature technologies tested in the real world. Data collection can be complex and costly, with data flows between partners raising security and confidentiality concerns. These issues require attention already during the project preparation phase. Additionally, permits for testing on public roads are necessary and impose specific requirements on the execution of the experiments.

The **project structure** defines the framework for project execution. It outlines work packages, their timelines, activities, milestones, and interconnections. A logical and easy-to-understand project structure facilitates good governance and project management.¹¹

However, even with a suitable project structure, ineffective governance can lead to difficulties. Failures and delays in activities that provide input for evaluation and misunderstandings between partners can disrupt the evaluation. These issues may arise due to:

- Unrealistic targets within the project timeframe
- An overcomplicated evaluation plan
- Poor execution of key activities
- Weaknesses in project structure or partner capabilities
- Lack of commitment from partners
- Insufficient or infrequent communication.

During the project preparation phase, the project structure and governance should be designed to allow for necessary adjustments while ensuring that the evaluation remains feasible within the time and budget constraints, without overburdening the evaluation team members. Project governance also involves managing expectations and balancing the perspectives and interests of partners, clients and other stakeholders. The aim is to deliver high-quality evaluations with impactful outcomes.

The following guidelines cover key aspects of project structure and governance:

- How to plan evaluation activities for the proposal
- How to create a project structure that supports evaluation
- How to assign responsibilities across work packages and activities
- How to ensure information exchange to support the evaluation of CCAM
- How to enable adaptivity of the evaluations
- How to ensure the quality of the evaluation
- How to set up a process for mediating conflicts

¹¹ **Project management** aims to deliver project results on time and within budget, and therefore focuses on planning, organising, and managing resources. This handbook does not provide guidance on what constitutes good project management.

Guideline 2.4. How to plan evaluation activities for the proposal

The description of the evaluation work packages (WP)¹² must be written by evaluation experts. It would be good to involve them from the beginning of the proposal preparation phase. Experience from previous CCAM projects is recommended.

There are multiple options for structuring evaluation activities within the project. All evaluation activities can be consolidated into one dedicated evaluation WP, or they can be distributed across other WPs, for example by test site (see Guideline 2.5). However, it is strongly recommended to at least dedicate a specific WP to a common evaluation methodology.

Partners preparing the evaluation WP must be in regular dialogue with partners responsible for other parts of the proposal. This dialogue ensures that:

- Evaluation partners can provide expertise and experience to maintain realistic commitments, particularly when describing the project's expected impacts.
- Evaluation partners understand the technology readiness level (TRL) of the tested systems and the feasibility of different testing opportunities. This is particularly important in CCAM projects, where the system's TRL and testing potential are sometimes overestimated.

Clear communication during proposal writing is necessary to ensure alignment in the scope and content of WPs contributing to the evaluation. This includes identifying potential risks to the evaluation and agreeing on mitigation strategies, especially for delays in data collection or other evaluation inputs. Such delays are common, especially in projects with extensive field experiments.

WP descriptions should specify the impact areas to be covered (see Guideline 2.2) and provide examples of possible approaches, methods, indicators, and data sources, aligned with available resources. Establish project-level basic principles for collecting and sharing data for evaluation.

The planning must ensure that the project's evaluation activities align with the available resources, including budget, timeline, duration, and partner expertise.

Example

Estimating a realistic effect size to avoid **overcommitment** of the expected impact:

- A project provides easy-to-use CCAM-based first-and-last-mile transport to a public transport hub.
- Identified theoretical basis for impacts: The service reduces the generalised travel cost of public transport by increasing its accessibility, thereby leading to a higher mode share of public transport.
- Effect size and exposure estimation: If 10% of the city's population resides within the service area and 20% already use public transport, the maximum increase in users cannot exceed 8% of the city population ($10\% * (100\% - 20\%)$).
- Comparable data: In a similar city, the new user adoption rate for a comparable service was 10%, indicating a similar increase could be expected here.

Accounting for **limited possibilities for real-world testing** in the evaluation activities:

- If only professional test drivers are permitted to operate the test vehicles, the evaluation should not rely on observing the drivers, as their behaviour will not reflect the behaviour of future users. Test drivers follow strict safety protocols, limiting their ability to mimic real user behaviour in automated driving.

¹² Using work packages in the project structure is not mandatory. Depending on the project's size, tasks or sub-projects can also be used. Here, 'work package' is used for simplicity.

- Instead, the evaluation could be based on vehicle data collected during automated driving, excluding take-over events.

Ensuring **alignment** of plans:

- Evaluation-related milestones (see Guideline 2.5) are incorporated into the project's Gantt chart, ensuring alignment with the timing of other project activities.

Risk mitigation measures:

- To mitigate the risk of evaluation delays, the technical team agrees to provide realistic assumptions for the parametrisation of CCAM in simulations. This ensures that if real-world testing is delayed beyond the must-start date of simulations, lack of real-world data will not become a bottleneck, allowing simulations to proceed using the provided assumptions.

Guideline 2.5. How to create a project structure that supports evaluation

The project structure must be designed to support the evaluation work. To achieve this, decisions must be made to ensure the following:

- **Key persons** responsible for conducting evaluations must also be involved in setting the evaluation plan from the beginning.
- **The work package (WP) structure** must facilitate the necessary interaction between the following teams:
 - **Technical team** – partners responsible for implementing the CCAM system.
 - **Test site team** – partners responsible for setting up and performing the field experiments.
 - **Evaluation team** – partners responsible for data analysis and impact assessment.

It must also facilitate internal coordination within the evaluation team to ensure alignment across different evaluation areas, impact areas, and evaluation approaches. (See Guideline 2.7)

- **The evaluation WP can be organised in different ways**, for example, by:
 - Main research questions
 - Levels of evaluation (vehicle, human, traffic and transport, society)
 - Impact areas
 - Test sites

Regardless of the structure, sufficient and frequent interaction between these organisational elements must be ensured. It is highly recommended to dedicate a WP to developing the evaluation plan and methodology across all sites, as well as among evaluation and impact area partners. Within any structure, it is important to ensure coherence of the overall evaluation plan.

- **Project milestones** are important for planning and monitoring progress within the project beyond the start and end dates of WPs. Thus, milestones related to evaluation and any activities the evaluation depends on (such as data delivery) must be incorporated into the project timeline. Below is a list of proposed milestones.
- **Timelines** must show that evaluation activities begin at the start of the project to allow for timely discussions and coordination between the technical, test site, and evaluation teams. Sufficient time must be allocated for preparing and implementing the evaluation plan, drawing conclusions, and reporting.

Recommended milestones related to evaluation:

1. *A first draft of research questions*, early in the evaluation planning to allow sufficient time for developing the evaluation plan with all necessary iterations.
2. *Agreement on the experimental design* between the evaluation, technical, and test site teams to ensure alignment with evaluation needs.

3. *Agreement on the data provision* between the evaluation team and data owners on the test site team. Includes timing and details on the provided data, its format, how it is shared, and the data provision milestone (5th item below).
4. *Evaluation plan completed and communicated to the consortium*, with detailed information provided especially to the technical and test site teams. This should be completed before the mid-term review of the project.
5. *Data provision for evaluation completed*. This milestone should be set early enough in the project's timeline to allow some flexibility for delays. After this milestone, no new data will be accepted for the evaluation.
6. *Presentation or delivery of interim evaluation results*. These should be presented before publishing them or progressing to the next evaluation phase. These presentations serve as an internal validation of the approaches and results, ensuring consistency and allowing for necessary reviews.

A common challenge in CCAM projects is the focus on technology at a low readiness level. This often leads to prolonged preparation phases for real-world tests due to the time required to obtain permits and resolve technical issues. Severe delays are not uncommon during test preparation, which can reduce the time available for the evaluation phase or necessitate extension of the project.

Monitoring project progress is therefore essential. To ensure that the evaluation team has sufficient time for analysis and reflection, it is recommended to set *cut-off dates* after which no new data from experiments will be accepted for the evaluation, as noted in the 5th milestone above.

Example

The task structure in an evaluation work package:

- Task 1: **Methodology** – jointly for all evaluation areas to ensure alignment.
- Task 2: **Vehicle level impacts** – for analyses using field experiment data.
- Task 3: **Human level impacts** – for evaluation using user experiment data.
- Task 4: **Transport system level impacts** – for evaluation mainly using simulations.
- Task 5: **Societal impacts** – for evaluation using findings from other evaluation levels and addressing them at society level.
- Task 6: **Conclusions** – jointly for all levels of evaluation and all test sites to address the high-level research questions.

Guideline 2.6. How to assign responsibilities across work packages and activities

Once the overall project goal and general approach are established, the consortium must assign clear roles to partners and define their responsibilities within different work packages. Evaluation activities require active commitment also from partners beyond the evaluation team. For example, the process of collecting and processing data from field experiments typically involves multiple work packages, partners, and test sites, including at a minimum the technical team, test site team, and data owners (partners in possession of data needed for the evaluation).

From the evaluation team perspective, it is important to identify key dependencies and establish clear agreements on the related responsibilities to ensure the availability of the necessary inputs for evaluation. Work package leaders must be aware of the dependencies between work packages. Clearly defined processes and roles help ensure that all relevant partners understand their responsibilities.

For cohesive evaluation and integrated results—outcomes no single partner could achieve individually—overall coordination of both the planning and execution of evaluation is crucial. If evaluation activities are

distributed across multiple work packages, consider appointing an evaluation manager to oversee the entire evaluation process.

In very large or long-term projects, leadership of different stages of the evaluation process can be assigned to different persons. Responsibilities should be clearly defined, with a structured handover process in place. For example, the person responsible for evaluation planning could transfer leadership to another person responsible for executing the evaluation.

Example

Consider a proposal for a large-scale, collaborative CCAM project involving multiple partners. The following steps give an example of the process for identifying and distributing key responsibilities within the consortium:

1. Identifying key dependencies between evaluation, data collection, and transfer
 - The consortium maps dependencies between evaluation activities and related work packages and tasks to clarify linkages
 - The mapping establishes that the evaluation team will require data from multiple field experiments conducted at different test sites.
2. Establishing requirements for data generation and transfer
 - To ensure the effective use of all data in the evaluation, the consortium agrees that field experiments will be conducted in a harmonised manner. The evaluation team commits to including support for specifying the experimental design in their work plan.
 - The test site and evaluation teams agree that data will be provided in a common data format, which must be confirmed by the data providers and users, along with related procedures for handling data.
3. Distributing specific responsibilities to all relevant partners
 - The consortium identifies the relevant partners for each test site and evaluation work package.
 - The respective work package leaders assign specific roles to each partner on these teams, ensuring that:
 - Each partner has a clear, well-defined role, whether related to data collection, processing, transfer or evaluation.
 - All relevant processes are assigned to clearly responsible partners, including harmonising test procedures, converting data, and managing secure data transfer.

Guideline 2.7. How to ensure information exchange to support the evaluation of CCAM

Throughout the project, partners must make joint decisions related to evaluation processes. To facilitate this, the main structures for active dialogue and collaboration within the evaluation team and with other partners should be agreed upon during the project preparation phase.

The aim is to ensure direct communication between relevant partners. An effective project structure supports this by keeping communication lines short. While online collaboration tools facilitate efficient information exchange and storage, they cannot replace direct interaction. Regular virtual or in-person meetings are important for resolving complex issues and fostering alignment across teams.

An important component of information exchange is expectation management regarding evaluation.

The evaluation lead must have expertise to:

- Understand technical and evaluation aspects of the project.
- Support collaborative work.

- Communicate effectively with partners to align expectations in light of feasibility, timeline, and resource constraints.
- Address potential misunderstandings about the evaluation process early on.

Example

To ensure continuous alignment, a structured information exchange between work packages is established. Biweekly meetings are scheduled from the start of the evaluation planning phase until all data has been analysed. These meetings facilitate:

- Dialogue between the evaluation team and related activities, such as technical and test site teams, as well as within the teams.
- A shared understanding of the overall project, enabling stakeholders to respond to plans and updates effectively.
- Regular updates on the progress of data collection or analysis.
- Discussions on any technical issues affecting evaluation.
- Alignment of expectations, monitoring the progress of milestones, identification of risks.

Guideline 2.8. How to enable adaptivity of the evaluations

CCAM and related regulations evolve rapidly, sometimes necessitating adjustments to CCAM test planning and execution during the project. As such changes may affect the evaluation, the evaluation scope and structure must be designed with adaptivity in mind (see the example for Guideline 2.1). In practice, the high-level project plan outlined in the proposal will be elaborated into an evaluation plan early in the project. Revisions may be required during the project due to changing needs, possibilities, and challenges. Fundamental adaptations require approval from the consortium leader and the client.

Start evaluation planning early in the project and adapt to what is feasible at test sites (see Guideline 2.5 for milestones and timeline). Feasibility may change, so work in close collaboration with test sites until the field experiments are completed. In practice, this will be an iterative process (see Chapter 3 introduction).

When preparing the project proposal, it is important to recognise that iterations will be required during the project's lifetime before the evaluation plan is finalised. To ensure that the evaluation team has sufficient time to complete their tasks, a cut-off date should be established, after which major adaptations can no longer be accommodated. The cut-off date should be set based on experience regarding the time required for the planned key approaches and methods, as outlined in Milestone 5 in Guideline 2.5.

Example

An example of ensuring adaptivity to changes in test site plans is to extend the evaluation methodology task until the planning phase of the field experiments is completed, or until successful data collection can be reasonably verified.

Guideline 2.9. How to ensure the quality of the evaluation

Each project strives to deliver high-quality results. Several project governance mechanisms help ensure the quality of evaluation activities, and these should be discussed during the project proposal phase and included in the work plan:

- **Monitoring the quality and validity of the evaluation plan** by members of the evaluation team with the most experience of CCAM evaluations. The evaluation manager or evaluation work package lead

should assign these responsibilities. The plan should be communicated to all relevant stakeholders in the consortium. Identify and communicate key decisions in the evaluation plan (e.g. assumptions made in the evaluation). Early communication with project partners ensures that everyone is aware of critical decisions and has the opportunity to seek clarifications or suggest changes. Failure in this regard can lead to inconsistencies that may only become evident after the results have been finalised.

- **Testing all steps of the evaluation process beforehand** should be facilitated by the project plan, ensuring that initial data collection and analysis can begin as early as possible. Clearly describe the plans for this in the project proposal.
- **'Evaluation partnerships'** (see the example of Guideline 3.18) can be used for discussing interim results and identifying missing, unlikely or unexplainable results, especially when analysing real-world data. Allow sufficient time for these collaborative reviews to check for potential inconsistencies and to interpret the results accurately. These partnerships can also assist in planning the reporting of results, defining both the desired content and the presentation format.

Example

In the proposal for a CCAM project, the evaluation team ensures the quality of the evaluation as follows:

- Experienced experts are involved in the evaluation work packages both for development and execution of the evaluation plan. The proposal explicitly requires that an experienced expert review the evaluation plan early in the project, with necessary revisions made based on their feedback.
- The proposal includes a phase for testing the evaluation process using preliminary data from the test sites. Insights from this will be used to refine the evaluation plan and tools before the full-scale evaluation begins.
- The proposal explicitly requires interim result reviews to discuss the preliminary findings. These reviews are both internal and external to the work package.
- The proposal allocates sufficient time at the end of the project for comprehensive work-package-internal and -external reviews of the reports. An internal milestone is set, requiring the reports to be finalised at least one month before the submission deadline to allow for these reviews.

Guideline 2.10. How to set up a process for mediating conflicts

CCAM evaluations typically involve multiple project partners working together towards shared goals. In such large, multi-partner or complex projects, conflicts may arise despite robust information exchange processes. These conflicts often stem from differences in expectations, goals, values, perceptions, and knowledge levels among team members and organisations. To effectively manage such challenges, a conflict resolution mechanism should be incorporated into the project preparation phase.

A well-defined dispute resolution mechanism improves the ability to manage potential conflicts without compromising project objectives or causing significant delays. Common dispute resolution mechanisms include, for instance:

- **Negotiation:** Direct discussion between conflicting parties to find a mutually agreeable solution.
- **Mediation or conciliation:** A neutral third party facilitates discussions between conflicting parties to reach a voluntary resolution.
- **Arbitration (non-binding or binding):** A third party reviews the dispute and provides a decision. Non-binding arbitration offers a recommendation, while binding arbitration is a final decision the parties must accept.

Conflict resolution mechanisms are needed for situations where conflicts cannot be resolved within or by the evaluation team. This involves designating a 'conflict resolver', who may be the evaluation work package

leader, the project coordinator or a specifically appointed person, to liaise with the project coordinator and work package leaders.

Unclear communication lines often contribute to conflicts. Defining and actively using structured communication channels minimises this risk. This is why EU-CEM specifies necessary lines of communication for the planning of evaluations (see Chapter 3). In addition, ensure that all project partners are aware of their designated points of contact for conflict resolution and the steps involved in escalating unresolved issues.

Example

1. Conflict **within** the evaluation team:

An evaluation partner does not adhere to the agreed societal scenarios, making it impossible for other evaluation partners to use their results as input. In these work package internal issues, the conflict resolver is the evaluation work package leader.

A practical way to address this issue is by organising workshops to define the societal scenarios, allowing partners to indicate essential (*must-have*) and desirable (*nice-to-have*) features from the perspective of their activities. This collaborative process helps build consensus on setting the societal scenario or establishing several alternative ones. Once consensus is reached, all evaluation areas can proceed with detailed evaluation planning, ensuring alignment across the project.

2. Conflict **between** different work packages:

The evaluation team requests specific data from the test site team. Initially, the data providers agree to deliver the requested data. However, later in the project, they report that providing the data is not possible due to technical challenges.

For the evaluation team, the lack of necessary data undermines the validity and completeness of the evaluation outcomes. For the test site or technical teams, challenges related to data collection may exceed the available resources or may have arisen from unexpected technical limitations.

As multiple work packages are affected, a project level conflict resolver, such as the project coordinator, should facilitate finding a solution.

For effective mediation, private discussions between the conflict parties and the resolver are preferred to more public disputes or confrontational messaging. Close and continuous dialogue between the evaluation team and data providers can help prevent such conflicts.

3. Guidelines for developing an evaluation plan

This chapter provides guidelines for developing an evaluation plan in CCAM projects. When mutual understanding and agreement among the project team has been reached on the characteristics of the CCAM system to be evaluated, the iterative process for developing the plan begins. If new information on the CCAM system is acquired, the evaluation plan must be adjusted accordingly, leading to iterations.

The main elements of the evaluation plan are:

- Description of the CCAM system under evaluation (Chapter 3.1)
- Research questions (Chapter 3.2)
- Evaluation methods (Chapter 3.3)
- Data specification and tools (Chapter 3.4)
- Experimental design (Chapter 3.5).

These elements are interconnected, making the evaluation inherently iterative. Adaptations are often needed for each of these elements based on feedback or requirements identified during the development of the others. This process continues until the evaluation plan is finalised. Figure 4 below describes these iterations. Guideline 3.28 in Chapter 3.6 describes how to compile the evaluation plan once a feasible solution has been found for each step.

Figure 4. Workflow and iterations in setting the evaluation plan until a feasible plan is established.

3.1. CCAM system description

The first step in developing an evaluation plan is to clearly describe the CCAM system that will be addressed in the evaluation, along with any related service concept where relevant. In projects addressing multiple CCAM systems or service concepts, each must be described individually. This chapter provides a common system description for all evaluation areas.

It is important to recognise that assessing the wider socio-economic impacts of CCAM tested in field experiments may not be meaningful if these experiments involve low technology readiness level (TRL) systems. Instead, evaluation, especially impact assessment, may focus on a higher-TRL version of the system when implemented at scale.

Therefore, two descriptions may be needed: one for the CCAM system tested in field experiments and another for a higher-TRL version of the system when CCAM is fully deployed. It is important to understand and clearly document the differences between these two descriptions. Due to the diversity of CCAM systems, each project must determine the relevant aspects to describe, using the guidelines below as a starting point.

These system descriptions guide the development of research questions, the establishment of experimental design, and the planning of data collection. They also provide context when forming conclusions from evaluations and help external stakeholders understand and interpret the study and its results.

The guidelines below cover the following topics:

- How to describe the CCAM system
- How to describe the ODD of an automated driving system
- How to describe the CCAM service concept
- How to describe the gap between the CCAM system tested in field experiments and the system used for the impact assessment

These steps may be linked and require iterations; they are not hierarchical steps done in sequence. Note that the best chronological order of tasks may differ from the sequence of guidelines below, depending on the project.

Guideline 3.1. How to describe the CCAM system

Describe the CCAM system in terms of the following elements, with additional elements added when relevant to the specific project. The descriptions should be short but precise.

- Vehicle category: passenger car, shuttle or minibus, bus, truck, etc.
- Level of automation (SAE level [6]): If the system does not align perfectly with any SAE level, describe the closest match and explain any discrepancies.
- Automated driving system type: e.g. highway chauffeur
- Connectivity: e.g. communication technology, communicated information
- Capabilities of the automated driving system, covering for example:
 - Dynamic driving tasks that the vehicle is able to perform and is not able to perform in automated mode (e.g. lateral and longitudinal vehicle control, monitoring the driving environment, object and event response execution)
 - Type of sensors installed, sensor ranges and operating angles
 - Target speed range
 - Target time headway, possible time headway settings
 - Human-machine interface (HMI), for example related to take-over requests—when and how they are directed to the driver; and activation and deactivation of the automated driving system—how the mode status is indicated, and what is required from the driver)
 - Minimal risk manoeuvres, such as coming to a standstill on the side of the road
- Technology Readiness Level (TRL 1-9): In case of low TRL, whether safety drivers or other necessary safety procedures (e.g. remote monitoring) is required specifically due to low TRL
- Traffic management and operation required for the CCAM use case, including physical, digital, and operational infrastructure

Example

An automated driving system for passenger cars (adapted from [11]):

Motorway Automated Driving System:

Vehicle category	Passenger car	
Level of automation	SAE level 3	
Automated driving system (ADS) type	Highway chauffeur. ADS is capable of driving on a motorway in the current lane.	
Connectivity	Vehicle-to-vehicle communication (ETSI MCS)	
Capabilities of the automated driving system	Dynamic driving tasks	In automated mode, the system is able to keep the vehicle within its lane and maintain a safe distance to vehicles ahead while in automated mode. It is not able to perform overtaking manoeuvres in automated mode.
	Sensors, ranges and operating angles	<p>Mid- and long-range radar, short- and long-range camera, LiDAR</p>
	Target speed range	Speed limit up to 120 km/h
	Target time headway	1.6 s
	HMI: Activation by user	The driver activates the ADS by pressing a button on the steering wheel. Signature auditory sound that automated driving mode is activated.
	HMI: Deactivation by user	The driver deactivates the ADS by pressing a cancel button on the steering wheel or through steering input or pedal operation. Signature auditory sound that automated driving mode is deactivated.
	HMI: Automated driving mode status	Automated driving mode status is shown in the instrument cluster, on the steering wheel and on the centre display.

	Takeover request	<p>If the system needs to deactivate automated driving mode, the ADS issues a take-over request to the driver.</p> <p>The request shows in the instrument cluster, on the steering wheel and on the centre display together with signature auditory sound indicating that the driver should take over.</p> <p>The belt tensioner tugs on the driver's seatbelt if the driver does not respond to a take-over request.</p>
	Minimal risk manoeuvres	Safe stop, safety driver to take over control.
Technology Readiness Level	Low TRL. The driver must be a trained safety driver.	
Traffic management and operation	No dedicated traffic management required.	

Guideline 3.2. How to describe the ODD of an automated driving system

The **operational design domain (ODD)** describes the “operating conditions under which a given driving automation system is specifically designed to function. This includes, but is not limited to, environmental, geographical, and time-of-day restrictions, and/or the requisite presence or absence of certain traffic or roadway characteristics.” [12]

Specify the conditions under which the ADS can and cannot operate, considering for example:

- **Road type:** type of public road, closed areas or dedicated corridors
- **Traffic rules and control:** speed limit, traffic signs, traffic lights, overtaking allowed
- **Infrastructure elements:** intersection types, railroad crossings, separation of driving directions/lanes, slope of road, tunnels, bridges, presence of roadside parking or roadworks, connectivity, availability of space for minimum risk manoeuvres
- **Quality of infrastructure:** lane markings (e.g. faded), traffic sign readability, road surface (potholes, longitudinal ruts), quality of digital infrastructure
- **Weather and road conditions:** precipitation, temperature, road surface condition (e.g. standing water, snow, ice), fog
- **Traffic conditions:** traffic volume, presence of pedestrians and cyclists in lane
- **Lighting conditions:** daylight, darkness, road lighting

Describe other relevant aspects as needed, such as abilities for border crossing.

Example

Example of the ODD specified for an urban automated driving system (ADS) for passenger cars (adapted from [13]):

The ADS operates on main public streets with separated driving directions and speed limits up to 50 km/h. It is capable of navigating signalised intersections, but non-signalised intersections and all rail-road crossings are outside its ODD. Roadworks, temporary lane changes, and construction zones are also outside its ODD. The ADS requires visible lane markings or a curb on at least one side.

The ADS operates in good weather conditions and in light or normal rain (up to 7.5 mm/h). Heavy rain (>7.5 mm/h), snow, fog, and extreme weather conditions, as well as icy or snowy road surfaces, are outside the ODD.

The ADS operates in all traffic conditions. It works in daylight and at night, with and without road lighting.

Further reading

ISO (2023). ISO 34503:2023 Road Vehicles—Test scenarios for automated driving systems— Specification for operational design domain. <https://www.iso.org/standard/78952.html>

SAE International (n.d.). J3259 (WIP) Taxonomy & Definitions for Operational Design Domain (ODD) for Driving Automation Systems. (Integrated in the ISO standard above)

Koopman, P., & Fratrick, F. (2019). How Many Operational Design Domains, Objects, and Events? *Safe AI 2019: AAAI Workshop on Artificial Intelligence Safety, Jan 27, 2019*. https://ceur-ws.org/Vol-2301/paper_6.pdf

Guideline 3.3. How to describe the CCAM service concept

The description of the CCAM system under evaluation should include a description of the service concept in terms of the following, where relevant:

- **Type of service:** private transport, public transport, taxi, on-demand transport with fixed (flexible) schedule and fixed (flexible) route, freight transport services
- **Vehicle ownership model:** vehicles owned privately, by a company or by a public entity
- **Vehicle use model:** private use, shared uses or shared rides
- **Area of operation, size:** city centre, built-up area, rural-area, inter-regional operation, size in terms of area (km²) or length of routes (km)
- **Fleet operation and management:** remote operation, remote supervision, vehicle routing
- **Service description from a user's perspective:** what are the requirements for use and the steps in using or travelling
- **Business model,** including costs for the user: as part of local public transport, subscription based, payment per ride/km
- **Target population:** All, older adults, disabled people, schoolchildren, etc.

Describe other relevant aspects as needed.

Example

A service description for an automated shuttle service providing last-mile connection to and from a metro station:

Type of service	Public transport, fixed route, fixed schedule
Ownership model	Owned by the regional public transport operator
Use model	Shared rides
Area of operation	Lauttasaari area in Helsinki, 4 km ²
Fleet operation and management	Remote supervision of the fleet, centralised routing

Description of service from the user's perspective	The user can board the shuttle at one of the predefined stops along a predefined route through a residential area, leading to a metro station. A shuttle departs from the tram stop every 10 minutes. No driver or operator is present on the shuttle, but it is connected to a remote operation centre that users can contact via a screen in the shuttle.
Business model	The public transport operator receives a normal public transport fee from the users; the service receives the same subsidies as the local public transport

Guideline 3.4. How to describe the gap between the CCAM system tested in field experiments and the system used for the impact assessment

Field experiments in CCAM projects typically involve low technology readiness level (TRL) systems that require additional safety measures, such as safety drivers. However, impact assessment focuses on high-TRL systems that are widely adopted and used by the general public as drivers or passengers.

Therefore, the fully developed CCAM system envisioned in impact assessment needs to be defined separately from the one tested in field experiments, using the instructions of the previous guidelines. Here, their main differences and the resulting implications of these differences must be specified. This should consider:

- **Capabilities of the CCAM system**, for example in terms of target speed and speed limit, headway, human-machine interface (HMI), and dynamic driving tasks.
- **Operational design domain and operating domain**, compare the conditions under which the CCAM system is designed to operate, is tested, and is assumed to function for impact assessment.
- **Safety procedures**, for example how fallback procedures differ.
- **Infrastructure support or requirements**, covering physical, digital, and operational road infrastructure, traffic management.
- **Service concept**, such as being part of public transport, on-demand transport, robotaxi, shared vehicles for private use.

Clarify the implications for impact assessment by explaining how these differences affect the evaluation. This should allow determining:

- Which field experiment data can be used in impact assessment and for which research topics.
- Where adjustments are necessary to account for the differences.
- Which parts require additional modelling or assumptions due to the gap.

Example

This example illustrates how to identify and describe the gap between a tested system (low-TRL automated passenger car) and the assumed system (high-TRL automation for impact assessment).

Aspect	Tested system	Assumed system in impact assessment	Differences and implications
Dynamic driving tasks	Safety driver performs lane changes manually, other dynamic	All dynamic driving tasks are automated.	Gap: The characteristics and frequency of lane changes in the tests does not represent true automated behaviour. Implications: Data related to lane-change driving behaviour cannot be used directly in

	driving tasks are automated.		impact assessment. Thus, additional data sources or assumptions are required regarding lane changes.
Speed and headway	Speed up to 20 km/h and minimum headway of 2 s.	Speed up to 50 km/h and minimum headway of 1.6 s in urban environments.	Gap: Substantial difference in the maximum speed and minimum headway. Implications: If used in impact assessment, the test data may underestimate effects on, for example, congestion or safety.
ODD	Streets up to 50 km/h speed limit, no signalised intersections, high-quality road markings, only in good weather conditions.	All speed limits up to 60 km/h with any kind of intersections, all weather conditions except heavy snowfall, not on icy or snowy roads.	Gap: Difference in the maximum speed limit (likely reflected also in street characteristics), exclusion of signalised intersections, and good weather is the only subset of weather conditions of the high-TRL system. Implications: Limited generalisability. Safety and performance in intersections or adverse weather cannot be inferred from the field data and require simulations or data from other sources.
Driver type	Only professional safety drivers allowed.	Vehicles operated by ordinary drivers.	Gap: Safety drivers are part of the safety protocol and trained to anticipate and mitigate risks, unlike typical users. Implications: Data on frequency of conflicts or driver interventions likely underestimates real-world risks. Non-driving related activities cannot be addressed. User behaviour studies are necessary for a more accurate assessment.
HMI	Activation and deactivation by a button on the steering wheel.	Activation by a button on the steering wheel. Deactivation via cancel button on steering wheel, steering input, or pedal operation.	Gap: The HMI itself might be different in prototype vehicles versus widely used products. Safety driver interactions do not reflect ordinary driver behaviour. Implications: HMI results are not applicable. Separate user testing is needed.
Safety protocol	Safety driver serves as fallback mechanism.	Automated safe-stop manoeuvre on the roadside.	Gap: In field tests, safety drivers handle fallback scenarios, whereas in high-TRL systems, automated responses are expected. Implications: Data from field tests on fallback mechanisms do not generalise and cannot be used in impact assessment.

			Separate experiments or simulations are required.
Infrastructure support	High-definition map only.	High-definition map combined with connectivity, providing information on roadworks, for example.	Gap: The tested system lacks the connectivity assumed in the high-TRL system. Implications: Navigation through roadwork sites cannot be evaluated based on field experiments. Connectivity-related impacts need to be addressed separately.
Service concept	No service concept.	Vehicle used as part of shared car fleet.	Gap: Field tests provide no data for evaluating the service concept. Implications: Impacts related to the service concept cannot be assessed directly from test data. These impacts require additional methods or assumptions.

Further reading

Innamaa et al. (2020). L3Pilot Deliverable 3.4: Evaluation plan. Chapter 2.2.

https://l3pilot.eu/fileadmin/user_upload/Downloads/Deliverables/Update_07102021/L3Pilot-SP3-D3.4-Evaluation_plan-v1.0_for_website.pdf

3.2. Research questions

Formulating and selecting specific, answerable, and relevant **research questions** refines the evaluation scope established during the project preparation phase (see Chapter 2.1) and specifies how the project's key objectives will be addressed. Research questions are the primary inquiries the study aims to answer, directing every step from planning to conclusion. They provide a foundation for planning subsequent evaluation steps, such as method selection, data specification, and experimental design (see Chapters 3.3 to 3.5).

When the evaluation scope is broad, a hierarchical structure of research questions is recommended. This involves organising research questions in a structured manner that reflects their level of detail and scope, breaking down large, complex topics into smaller, more precise sub-questions.

For research questions in CCAM projects to be effective, they should be:

- **Specific:** Clearly defined and focused on a particular aspect of CCAM, its use or impacts.
- **Measurable:** Designed to yield qualitative or quantitative results.
- **Relevant:** Aligned with the evaluation scope and project objectives.

Research questions should address knowledge gaps, challenges, or key issues in CCAM. Their development must be based on a thorough understanding of the technology and its operational scale, the deployment context (see Chapter 3.1), and the potential and expected users and impacts.

Developing a practical evaluation plan is inherently iterative. It involves repeated cycles of refining research questions and incorporating feedback based on **feasibility checks** for methods, experimental design, and data collection. This process continues until the evaluation plan is ready for execution (see Milestone 4 in Guideline 2.5).

Evaluating the feasibility of research questions and prioritising them are essential to ensure the evaluation is realistic and achievable. Feasibility checking is not a quick or superficial process. It requires substantial groundwork across multiple evaluation plan components before it can be conducted, essentially drafting a full evaluation plan. To determine whether a research question can be addressed within the project's constraints, the following elements of the evaluation plan must be checked for their feasibility (see Guideline 3.8 for the complete set of instructions):

1. **Availability of necessary data** (see Chapter 3.4)
2. **Possibility to implement required experimental design** (see Chapter 3.5)
3. **Availability of appropriate tools and methods** (see Chapter 3.3)

Only after significant progress in the evaluation methodology planning can a proper feasibility check be conducted. This structured process ensures project-level commitment to realistic and achievable research questions by engaging the entire project team in discussions. However, these steps are interconnected and iterative rather than strictly sequential, and the order may differ from the sequence of guidelines given below, depending on the project's complexity, scope, and goals.

Research questions may originate from a variety of sources—such as brainstorming sessions, collaborative workshops or individual expert contributions—resulting in a diverse and sometimes extensive list. Two complementary approaches can guide the refinement process:

- **Prioritisation first:** If the initial list is extensive, it may be effective to first prioritise the questions based on criteria such as relevance, impact, and alignment with the project's objectives, before proceeding with planning of the methodology and feasibility check. This step helps to focus attention to the most promising questions.
- **Preliminary feasibility screening first:** If a significant number of questions are suspected to be impractical, an initial screening can filter out unworkable ones, before proceeding with prioritisation and more detailed planning of the methodology. This is less intensive than full feasibility checking but ensures that only questions with a reasonable chance of being answered proceed to prioritisation.

In practice, whether to prioritise or screen first depends on the nature of the input. Often, a hybrid approach—iteratively alternating between prioritisation and feasibility screening—works best. The list of research questions will undergo multiple iterations before the evaluation plan—and the final, feasible, focused, achievable, and aligned set of research questions—is finalised. Thus, it is important to be prepared for this in the planning process.

The guidelines below cover the following topics:

- How to elaborate the scope of evaluation
- How to formulate and organise research questions
- How to prioritise research questions
- How to check the feasibility of research questions
- How to set hypotheses

Guideline 3.5. How to elaborate the scope of evaluation

Elaborating the evaluation scope begins with the initial, overall evaluation scope defined during the project preparation phase (Guideline 2.1). This process involves further refining the understanding of knowledge gaps, opportunities or concerns related to the CCAM system under evaluation. The aim is to reassess the relevance of the initial evaluation scope and propose adjustments, if necessary, to the consortium and client.

This process is iterative and requires continuous alignment with the overall project goals to ensure the evaluation stays focused, feasible, and impactful.

Key steps in elaborating the scope:

1. **Review the project proposal or work plan:** Ensure that the project goals and evaluation scope, as agreed with the client, serve as the foundation for drafting research questions. Also, check if any (high-level) research questions have been specified in the proposal.
2. **Analyse the state of the art:** Analyse the current state of the CCAM technology under evaluation, guided by the system description of Chapter 3.1. Leverage insights from CCAM industry partners involved in its development.
3. **Identify knowledge gaps and key research topics:** The aim is to find areas needing further exploration and questions that remain unanswered. Utilise existing evaluation expertise, experience from previous projects, and literature related to the impact areas (see Guideline 2.2).

Example

This example continues from the one presented in Guideline 2.1 where the project proposal set the scope of impact assessment to assess *“the impacts of highly automated driving [...] and what is the contribution of the technology enablers on the impacts”* [10]. The impact areas are selected for evaluation as outlined in the example of Guideline 2.2, included driving behaviour, user, people mobility, traffic safety, energy and environment, traffic flow efficiency, equity, and sustainability.

To further refine this scope, the evaluation team specifies that the assessment will focus on *“specific scenarios and on European level after their market introduction”* [10]. In addition, it is determined that *“In addition to the direct impacts, the aim is also to assess the indirect impacts which cover the broader effects of individual direct impacts and result from a chain of impacts, often with complex interactions and external factors”* [10].

A literature review is then conducted to understand the existing research on the impacts of selected technology enablers. This review reveals a lack of systematic assessment that combines these enablers with high automation. Key topics that should be addressed in relation to the selected impact areas are identified from the literature, including:

- **CO₂ emissions** (relevant for the *energy and environment* impact area).
- **Value of travel time** (important for *people mobility*).

This refined focus on specific research topics and impact areas forms the **elaborated scope for evaluation**.

Guideline 3.6. How to formulate and organise research questions

Research questions (RQ) must be **specific** and **answerable** using qualitative or quantitative methods and **relevant** to the evaluation scope. They should be articulated in **clear and precise language**.

The phrasing of RQs affects the type of information the evaluation will provide. Here are examples to show how wording shapes the scope of responses:

- What is the impact of CCAM on [X]? Answer: Result indicator and effect size.
- How does CCAM affect [X]? Answer: Result indicator and effect size, or a list of impact mechanisms.
- What are the main factors influencing [X]? Answer: A list of factors.
- Will CCAM halve the number of [X] compared to [Y]? Answer: Yes or no.

When the evaluation scope is broad, a **hierarchical structure** of RQs is recommended. This structure organises them to reflect their level of detail and scope. This helps break down large, complex topics into more specific and precise sub-questions.

- **High-level RQs:** These have a wide scope and should be written in a broad manner, e.g. *“What is the effect of CCAM on traffic safety?”*, *“How does CCAM affect equity?”*
- **Medium-level RQs:** These explore specific dimensions of the broader topic. For example, under the traffic safety RQ, a medium-level question could be, *“How does CCAM affect accident rates in urban environments?”*
- **Low-level RQs:** These target even more detailed aspects of the topic. For instance, *“What is the change in rear-end collision frequency at intersections with CCAM compared to the baseline without?”*

This way, a clear hierarchy is created: high-level RQs set the main themes, medium-level RQs break the themes into more focused topics, and low-level RQs dive into the specifics. The answers to the low-level RQs should collectively provide a comprehensive answer to their respective higher-level ones.

Identifying relevant RQs involves combining a top-down approach, starting from the chosen impact areas, with a bottom-up approach that begins from the tested CCAM systems and their expected direct impacts, working towards the impact area level RQs. The purpose is to ensure that the RQ list is complete and covers all relevant aspects.

Aim for few high-level RQs, even in large, comprehensive projects. Ensure that each impact area considered has at least one high-level RQ and avoid grouping multiple impact areas under one question.

RQs are inherently scenario-bound (see Guideline 3.10 and Guideline 3.11). The societal scenarios define the population, timeframe, and geographical context for the impact assessment. This contextual information does not need to be explicitly specified in the RQs but should be reflected in their interpretation.

The development of feasible RQs starts with drafting an initial list of RQs as a basis for discussions. The RQs are finalised through multiple cycles of:

- Formulation and organisation of RQs (Guideline 3.6).
- Prioritisation of RQs (Guideline 3.7).
- Feasibility checking of RQs (Guideline 3.8).

Well-structured and well-formulated RQs form a solid foundation for building the rest of the evaluation plan. They also help draw comprehensive conclusions from the evaluation results by showing the relationships between different evaluation topics within an impact area.

Example

A CCAM system is expected to improve equity within and between rural and urban areas by enhancing accessibility for underserved people and regions. There is also a knowledge gap on how travel modes that do not require driving affect travel mode choices. Based on these considerations, the following three high-level RQs are drafted, along with their corresponding lower-level questions and scenario types in which they will be addressed:

- **RQ1: How does CCAM affect accessibility in urban and rural areas?**
Scenario: Societal scenarios and service scenarios set for urban and rural areas.
 - *RQ1.1: What is the impact of the robotaxi service on the number of reachable activities in different areas?*
 - *RQ1.2: How does the robotaxi service affect the affordability of mobility for different population groups?*
- **RQ2: How does the CCAM system affect people mobility?**
Scenario: User scenarios in both urban and rural contexts, including public transport users, car owners, different age groups. These match the context set by the societal scenario above.
 - *RQ2.1: What is the impact of the robotaxi service on mode choice?*

- **RQ3: How does the CCAM system affect equity?**

Scenario: Same societal scenarios as above.

- *RQ3.1: How does acceptance of the CCAM system differ between different population groups?*
 - Addressing differences between user scenarios.
- *RQ3.2: How does CCAM affect accessibility for different underserved population groups in rural and urban areas?*

An example of how the phrasing of RQs influences the scope of results:

- **Does CCAM affect accessibility?**
 - *Answer:* Yes.
- **What is the impact of CCAM on accessibility?**
 - *Answer:* The CCAM system increases the number of reachable destinations by X% for non-car-owners in [specific area].
- **How does CCAM affect accessibility?**
 - *Answer:* The CCAM system improves accessibility by offering an alternative means of transport in areas with poor public transport coverage, particularly benefiting persons without a driver's licence.

Further reading

- **High- and medium-level RQs:**
Metz et al. (2023). Hi-Drive Deliverable D4.1: Research Questions. https://www.hi-drive.eu/app/uploads/2023/05/Hi-Drive-SP4-D4.1-Research-questions-v1.0_for_website-1.pdf
- **High-, medium-, and low-level RQs:**
Innamaa et al. (2020). L3Pilot Deliverable D3.4: Evaluation Plan. https://l3pilot.eu/fileadmin/user_upload/Downloads/Deliverables/Update_07102021/L3Pilot-SP3-D3.4-Evaluation_plan-v1.0_for_website.pdf

Guideline 3.7. How to prioritise research questions

The process of defining research questions may raise more questions than the project has resources to address properly. To develop a feasible and focused evaluation plan, prioritisation is essential. This ensures that the selected research questions align with the project goals and available resources. Base prioritisation on:

1. **Relevance:**
Ensure that each research question aligns with the project goals and the agreed evaluation scope. Prioritise questions that fill important knowledge gaps, align with the call text, and fulfil the client's requirements.
2. **Importance:**
Focus on questions that relate to the expected main impacts of the CCAM system or that have the potential to produce high-impact findings. These could be related to societal priorities, regulatory requirements or technological breakthroughs. Stakeholders outside the consortium may be consulted if it is otherwise difficult to determine the importance.
3. **Dependency within the hierarchy:**
Prioritise questions whose outcomes contribute to answering other higher-priority questions. For example, foundational questions on *driving behaviour* may be necessary to answer broader questions on *traffic flow efficiency*.

4. Feasibility:

Prioritise questions that are realistically answerable within the project's available resources, tools, timeline, experimental design, and data (see Guideline 3.8). Consider the complexity and development needs of the required research methods.

Example

Consider a CCAM project focused on the impacts of automated driving on urban mobility. Initially, the consortium proposed 15 research questions. However, due to limited resources, it uncertain whether all of them could be properly evaluated. Thus, the evaluation team followed the four steps outlined in the guideline to prioritise the list and exclude research questions of low priority:

Step 1: Relevance.

- The team brainstormed the research question for all impact areas within the evaluation scope (see the example in Guideline 2.2).
- Research questions that did not directly align with the project's goal of assessing impact on urban mobility were deprioritised.
 - *Example:* Questions focused on rural areas were deprioritised, as the project specifically targeted urban environments.

Step 2: Importance.

- Through a literature review and experience with past projects, the evaluation team identified the most likely impact mechanisms related to CCAM on urban mobility.
 - *Example:* Research indicated that automation in privately-owned cars could increase car travel, affecting congestion. Thus, questions such as “*How does CCAM affect urban congestion patterns?*” were prioritised.

Step 3: Dependency within the hierarchy.

- The team mapped interdependencies between research questions based on the impact pathways (see Chapter 4).
 - *Example:* Questions on *driving behaviour* and interactions between different vehicle categories in traffic were seen as necessary for evaluating *traffic flow efficiency*.
- Thus, foundational questions like “*How does CCAM influence car-following behaviour in urban settings?*” were prioritised, as they supported answering the most relevant and important research questions.

Step 4: Feasibility.

- The evaluation team assessed available resources, tools, and data collection and analysis methods. Each question's resource requirements were cross-checked against them.
 - *Example:* Some questions required resource-intensive tool development or extensive new data collection, which exceeded the project's budget and timeline.
- Questions that could not be answered within the project's constraints were excluded from the final list.

After applying these prioritisation steps, the evaluation team had identified eight research questions that were relevant, important, and feasible given the resources. The rest were documented but not pursued within the project's evaluation plan.

Guideline 3.8. How to check the feasibility of research questions

Once a draft evaluation plan is ready, it is essential to check the **feasibility** of each research question. Feasibility checking ensures that the evaluation can be executed effectively within the project's resources, timeline, and technological constraints. If changes to the project plans occur at later stage, such as during the testing phase, the feasibility of the planned research questions should be re-evaluated. This process involves assessing several critical components:

- 1) **Data provision** (see Chapter 3.4):
Verify that all required data for evaluation are covered by the data-sharing agreements. Ensure that the planned external data sources are available, accessible, and appropriate, and that the provided quantity of data is sufficient for the methods foreseen. Confirm the required inputs for relevant methods and tools, their calibration and validation, and proper contextual data.
- 2) **Experimental design** (see Chapter 3.5):
Ensure that the experimental design meets the minimum requirements of the envisioned methods, including the type and number of participants, as agreed with the test site teams. Check if the technological readiness level of the tested system is sufficient for the envisioned testing.
- 3) **Evaluation tools and methods** (see Chapter 3.3):
Confirm that the necessary tools are available to the responsible evaluation team members. If tool development is required, verify that the planned development timeline and resource allocation (time, funding, personnel) are reasonable.
- 4) **Timeline alignment** (see Chapter 3.6):
Verify that the time allocated for each element of the evaluation process is realistic. Consider the dependencies between different stages of the evaluation and how they align with the overall proposed project timeline.
- 5) **Resource availability** (see Chapter 3.6):
Check that evaluation team partners are available for evaluating each research question with sufficient **resources** (time, researchers, budget).

If important research questions are deemed unfeasible, check the following adaptations:

- Is it possible to adapt the data collection (see Chapter 3.4)? For example, by acquiring additional data sources or modifying the existing data collection process to meet the requirements.
- Is it possible to adapt the experimental design (see Chapter 3.5)?
- Can the team develop new methods or tools or adapt the existing ones (see Chapter 3.3)?
- Can the research question be reformulated (see Guideline 3.6)?

If no feasible solution can be found, the research question should be removed from the evaluation plan.

To build a resilient evaluation plan, prioritise high-level research questions that:

- Have a feasible plan for execution.
- Do not depend on a single researcher, data provider, or unique tool.
- Require minimal development of new evaluation tools.

Higher risks and more uncertainties can be tolerated for low-level RQs unless they are vital to answering a higher-level RQ.

Example

These examples illustrate how a CCAM project conducted feasibility checks from the five perspectives outlined in the guideline, along with examples of solutions to overcome different barriers to evaluation.

Data provision:

- *Challenge:* A research question focused on the CCAM system's operational design domain (ODD) in varying weather conditions. However, no weather or road condition data were available from the test sites, preventing the evaluation of this research question.
- *Solution:* An external source for road and weather condition data was identified, allowing the research question to remain in the evaluation.

Experimental design:

- *Challenge:* A research question addressed user acceptance of the CCAM system with the intention to study users' opinions after experiencing the system in a field experiment. However, only professional safety drivers employed by the developer of the system were allowed to operate the test vehicles. Their experience does not reflect that of ordinary users.
- *Solution:* The experimental approach was adjusted to place the participant in the passenger seat instead of the driver seat. This change retained the research question, and limitations from experiencing the system as a passenger rather than as a driver were planned to be addressed in the evaluation report.

Evaluation tools:

- *Challenge:* A research question focused on traffic safety required simulation-based evaluation. However, one partner lacked validated safety simulation software.
- *Solution:* The partner committed to investing resources (time, funds) into validating their in-house simulation tool. Two backup plans were developed in case the validation failed: it was ensured that another partner also had the means to conduct these simulations and that an alternative tool could be used for the evaluation.

Timeline:

- *Challenge:* A research question required the results of other research questions for its evaluation to even begin, and also several months of execution time. This would exceed the total time allocated for evaluation in the project, meaning this research question was deemed unfeasible.
- *Solution:* The timeline was adjusted by scheduling the assessment of the other research questions a few months earlier.

Resources:

- *Challenge:* A research question required access to a driving simulator, which was costly and not included or budgeted in the original project plan.
- *Solution:* The project coordinator reallocated the budget through an amendment to the project agreement, allowing the research question to remain in the evaluation plan.

Guideline 3.9. How to set hypotheses

Hypotheses are statements about the state of the world and about the causal relationships between variables.

Scientific hypotheses should be both falsifiable and testable. Falsifiability means that the hypothesis can be proven false, while testability means that the hypothesis can be evaluated based on collected data. A hypothesis supported by evidence is typically accepted as true until new evidence potentially refutes it.

Hypotheses should describe what will be measured and estimate the magnitude of the impact. The measure can be either quantitative (e.g. percentage change in travel time) or qualitative (e.g. increase, decrease or no effect). The expected magnitude might involve precise values, like "a 20% reduction in travel time", or general trends, such as "an increase in user satisfaction." When applicable, hypotheses should describe the conditions

under which the impact is expected and the causal mechanisms that explain why the anticipated impact is expected.

Hypotheses can be derived from previous research or propose entirely novel ideas. In both cases, the link between existing knowledge and the current hypothesis should be explained to position the evaluation within the broader scientific context.

Deriving hypotheses can contribute to the development and phrasing of research questions. A single research question may give rise to several hypotheses. Well-articulated hypotheses help design experiments (Chapter 3.5), structure data collection (Chapter 3.4) and analysis methods (Chapter 3.3) to answer research questions, though they are not mandatory for CCAM evaluation. They are valuable when the goal is to test specific causal relationships or quantify how independent variables (e.g. CCAM implementation) affect dependent variables (e.g. travel time, number of accidents). However, hypotheses may not be suitable for purely exploratory questions or for research focused on describing properties, phenomena, or simply measuring values without establishing causal links. Ultimately, whether to use hypotheses depends on the goals of the evaluation.

Hypotheses can be evaluated using null hypothesis significance testing, where the null hypothesis assumes no effect or no difference (e.g. “CCAM has no impact on trip frequency”) and the alternative hypothesis posits an effect (“e.g. “CCAM increases trip frequency”). Researchers often use p-values to assess statistical significance. A p-value below a chosen threshold suggests that, assuming the null hypothesis is true, the observed effect (or one more extreme) would be unlikely to occur due to random variability in the data. This result typically leads to rejecting the null hypothesis. While very prevalent in scientific research, null hypothesis testing is not the only method for evaluating data in CCAM projects. Depending on the context, alternative approaches—such as constructing confidence intervals, focusing on effect sizes, or using Bayesian analyses—may be more appropriate.

Example

High-level research question:

What is the impact of the CCAM service on people mobility?

This can be refined into specific hypotheses:

1. CCAM service users’ monetary value to travel time is, on average, 20% lower than of the users of conventional human-driven vehicles.
2. The average number of trips per week is 10% higher for CCAM service users than for a comparable group of non-users.
3. The average trip distance for CCAM service users is 20% greater than that for a comparable group of non-users.
4. Within the operating area of the CCAM service, 50% of the trips that would otherwise have been undertaken using private cars are instead completed using the CCAM service.

In practice, the drafters of the hypotheses should provide a justification for the specific percentages used based, for example, on theoretical reasoning or pilot data.

Further reading

FESTA. (2021). *FESTA Handbook* (Version 8). Chapter 6.1.1.

<https://www.connectedautomateddriving.eu/methodology/festa/>

3.3. Evaluation methods

This chapter provides guidelines for selecting methods and tools to assess the impacts of CCAM. The primary goal of impact assessment is to estimate the magnitude of effects on specific indicators when a CCAM system is introduced or in use (*treatment*), compared to the situation before its introduction or when it is not in use (*baseline*). An **effect** refers to the relative difference in an indicator value that results from the use of CCAM. Effects can be expressed in quantitative terms (e.g. $\pm 10\%$), qualitative terms (e.g. 'more', 'less', 'higher', 'lower'), or absolute terms (e.g. 100 injury accidents¹³, 1000 vehicle kilometres travelled, 20 tons of CO₂).

Careful planning is required to define what is being compared and under which conditions. Since the evaluation focuses in this handbook's case on CCAM systems, their use and related impacts, it is important to isolate the changes caused by CCAM from other simultaneous changes and parallel trends, such as fleet electrification or transport service digitalisation. Therefore, the baseline and treatment conditions must be comparable and specified such that the assessment reflects only the effects of CCAM.

It is also important to understand the differences between the CCAM system tested in field experiments and the CCAM system addressed in the impact assessment (see Chapter 3.1). Many CCAM field experiments involve systems with low technology readiness level (TRL), making it less meaningful to study the broader socio-economic impacts of these early-stage implementations. Instead, impact assessments should focus on higher-TRL versions of the systems, often assuming widespread adoption with a significant share of transport or mobility. These differences impose certain requirements on method selection, particularly in considering what can be directly measured from field experiments and how to bridge the gap between tested low-TRL systems and high-TRL systems targeted in the impact assessment.

Once the research questions are established (see Chapter 3.2), **indicators** are defined to answer them. Indicators translate research questions into concrete, measurable metrics that can be evaluated using different methods. They bridge the gap between theoretical research questions and the practical, measurable dimensions of what those questions aim to capture. If hypotheses have been formulated, they may also influence the selection of indicators.

The next step involves selecting suitable **methods and tools** for estimating the indicator values. The evaluation method specifies how each research question will be addressed after data collection from CCAM experiments. While some research questions might be answered using indicators that can be directly measured or calculated, others may require several stages with intermediary indicators before the primary indicator of interest can be assessed. Each step in this process may involve different methods, tools, and datasets to derive or assess interim and final outcomes.

Scenarios are useful for structuring evaluations, as they enable detailed scoping and provide reference points for ensuring systematic coverage. In EU-CEM, a scenario is defined as *a structured depiction, specified by a set of pre-determined conditions and variables, representing actual or theoretical states, situations, or interactions*. All evaluation and impact areas require scenario setting, though the scope and detail of scenarios may differ across areas.

¹³ It is acknowledged that the terms 'crash' and 'collision' are often used interchangeably with 'accident'. Projects may use any of these terms.

EU-CEM defines seven distinct scenario categories for evaluation (see Guideline 3.10 and Guideline 3.11 for more details):

- **Societal scenarios** describe the broader societal context, including the envisioned CCAM system and its usage.
- **Service scenarios** describe a single CCAM service or a chain of transport services that CCAM is part of, such as logistics services, public transport services, and shared mobility services.
- **Traffic scenarios** represent traffic characteristics and road infrastructure on specific road segments or networks. Vehicles in a traffic scenario are involved in different, non-predefined driving scenarios.
- **Driving scenarios** depict short, specific periods of driving defined by primary driving tasks (e.g. car following, lane change) or triggered by specific events (e.g. an obstacle in the lane) [13]. These describe smaller, more focused traffic contexts compared to traffic scenarios. They cover shorter periods of time and fewer road users. For example, interaction between two vehicles over a few seconds. In contrast, there may be hundreds or thousands of vehicles in an hour-long traffic scenario.
- **Test scenarios** describe sequences of triggers, events, and actions among road users (e.g. ego vehicle, adjacent vehicles, pedestrians) to achieve a specific testing goal. This scenario type relates only to the evaluation of technical functioning (see Chapter 4.1).
- **User scenarios** describe population segments and their state related to CCAM, such as mobility behaviour, attitudes, and socio-demographic characteristics.
- **User behaviour scenarios** describe the direct or indirect interaction between different users and the CCAM system.

While other scenario classifications exist (e.g. ISO 34501 [14] and ASAM OpenSCENARIO [15]), the one presented here is tailored to describe the diverse perspectives necessary for impact assessment of CCAM. In this handbook, traffic, driving, user, and user behaviour scenarios are considered as lower-level scenarios and societal scenarios as high-level scenarios.

It is important to recognise that the scope of scenarios directly determines the scope of conclusions drawn from the results. Narrow scenarios, or a narrow set of scenarios, will only yield specific, context-bound conclusions. Broader societal conclusions require correspondingly broad societal scenarios.

Field experiments typically address lower-level scenarios, such as driving or user scenarios, on a particular road section or within a limited area or based on a limited group of participants. However, broader societal impacts of CCAM require assessing them within societal scenarios that cover entire networks and all trips made in them, including non-automated vehicles and non-motorised travel.

Depending on the impact areas and research questions, it may be necessary to scale up the impacts from lower-level scenarios to broader societal contexts reflected by the societal scenario. This requires a method for **scaling up** results to a societal level, reflecting a broader spatial and temporal frame than the lower-level scenarios.

In addition to direct impacts, it is important to consider cascading **indirect and possibly unintended impacts** of CCAM. These include increased car usage due to improved comfort and behavioural adaptations among non-users. These indirect impacts can be difficult to detect and quantify, as they may result from gradual processes. For example, behavioural adaptations among CCAM users and non-users can take months or years to fully manifest. Nevertheless, qualitative considerations of these impacts are recommended.

In summary, this chapter guides the development of methods for answering defined research questions within the project's timeline and available resources. It ensures that data collected by the project (see Chapter 3.4) is fully exploited during evaluation. Developing robust evaluation methods involves careful selection of suitable indicators, methods, and tools. This process is iterative, requiring coordination between the different elements of the evaluation plan described in Chapter 3 (see Figure 4). Once these iterations are complete, the final method is documented in the evaluation plan (see Guideline 3.28).

Further guidance, specific to each evaluation and impact area, is provided in Chapter 4. This includes terminology definitions, background overviews, recommendations for result indicators, different methods and approaches, and best practices to avoid common pitfalls. These guidelines should be used alongside the general ones given here.

The guidelines below cover the following topics:

- How to describe the societal scenarios for impact assessment
- How to define mid- and low-level scenarios: traffic and driving scenarios, user and user behaviour scenarios
- How to define relevant indicators for impact assessment
- How to set a method for answering a research question
- How to consider the scaling up of results in the methodology
- How to consider intended direct impacts, indirect and unintended impacts, and the impacts on non-users

These steps are interconnected and may require iterations; they are not strictly hierarchical or sequential. Note that the best chronological order of tasks may also differ from the sequence of guidelines below, depending on the project.

Guideline 3.10. How to describe the societal scenarios for impact assessment

The societal scenarios define the broader context and setting for impact assessment. They specify the region and timeframe of interest and describe how CCAM systems relate to existing transport infrastructure and supply. A societal scenario must be established for all baseline and treatment conditions planned for assessment (see Guideline 3.27). When defining societal scenarios, it is important to consider what requirements the research questions place on them. Evaluation can focus on one societal scenario or several alternative ones.

Even if socio-economic or other broader societal impacts are not within the evaluation scope, defining a societal scenario is beneficial. Using shared societal scenarios across all evaluation and impact areas as a foundation for developing more relevant, targeted scenarios (see Guideline 3.11) ensures consistency. It ensures that results from different areas complement rather than contradict each by aligning assumptions across different evaluation steps or areas.

If societal-level impact areas (see Chapter 4.4) are planned, the societal scenarios used in those assessments form the basis for the scenarios across all impact areas. The assessment of society-level impacts relies on results from other impact areas, which must align. To ensure feasibility across all impact areas, scenario development should be a joint activity. While maintaining consistency with the overarching societal scenario is essential, other impact areas include additional scenarios of specific interest.

To define a societal scenario, set the characteristics of the high technology readiness level (TRL) CCAM system for which the impact assessment is made (see Chapter 3.1), the transport system it operates within, the CCAM users, and the targeted scope of evaluation in terms of time, place, and population.

The process starts with the research questions, as their phrasing can specify the necessary scope of the societal scenario. If they do not specify all aspects, these must be agreed upon at this phase. The broadest defined scope sets the general context, such as “in the EU”, “on urban and rural roads”, “in city X”.

The following table provides key elements to consider when defining societal scenarios. These elements provide a starting point, but are not exhaustive, and additional aspects—such as economic activity, political factors or socio-cultural trends—may be relevant. In the impact assessment, the impact of CCAM should be isolated from other changes in these elements.

Element of societal scenario	Examples of considerations
Temporal scope	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • CCAM introduced into current transport system • Specific future year targeted (e.g. 10 years from now) • Specific period (e.g. from now until 2050) • Specific deployment milestone (e.g. 50% CCAM penetration rate in vehicle fleet)
Spatial scope	Specific city, region or country; all motorways in the EU
Transport system and role of CCAM	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Travel and transport service offerings and usage patterns <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • CCAM as a complementary service or disruptive replacement • Impacts on other transport modes • Fleet composition and vehicle characteristics <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Systematic differences between CCAM and other vehicles, e.g. all CCAM vehicles being electric • Penetration rate of CCAM vehicles in traffic flow or vehicle stock
CCAM target users	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Car drivers, persons without a driving licence, certain demographic or social groups • Service and fleet operators, traffic management operators, professional drivers
Other road users	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Car drivers, public transport users, pedestrians, cyclists, micromobility users, certain demographic or social groups • Service and fleet operators, traffic management operators, professional drivers
Dedicated infrastructure for CCAM	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Dedicated lanes • Pick-up and drop-off zones • V2X and telecommunications equipment
Regulations and policies	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Need for a driving licence • Policies promoting shared mobility, electric vehicles or other • Taxation and insurance policies

Example

The project addresses one societal scenario with the following characteristics:

Element	Description
CCAM system	High technology readiness level as defined in Guideline 3.4 for the system addressed in impact assessment
Temporal scope	The current transport system (year 20xx with latest statistics available)

Regulation and policies	As in the temporal scope year
Dedicated infrastructure to CCAM	Infrastructure-to-vehicle connectivity available on motorways of the Trans-European Transportation Network (TEN-T) to support temporary routing (e.g. roadworks)
Transport supply	Privately owned SAE Level 3 automated passenger cars replacing current privately owned conventional cars. Vehicles replacement occurs randomly, and the automated vehicles maintain the same size and powertrain as the replaced vehicles. No changes to public transport supply or freight transport compared to situation without automated vehicles.
Targeted area	All motorways in EU-27.
Penetration rate of ADS among passenger cars in traffic	10% (short-term realistic) 50% (long-term realistic) 100% (theoretical maximum potential)

Guideline 3.11. How to define mid- and low-level scenarios: traffic and driving scenarios, user and user behaviour scenarios

The previously defined societal scenario serves as a basis for defining the mid-level service, traffic, and user scenarios, as well as low-level driving and user behaviour scenarios (see scenario definitions in the introduction to Chapter 3.3).

The mid-level scenarios must align with the conditions set in the societal scenario, and the low-level scenarios with the mid-level scenarios. These scenarios add necessary detail for the impact areas that use them for evaluation, and several parallel scenarios can be used to study various conditions of interest.

The selected mid- and low-level scenarios together should represent exposure (e.g. travel activity, vehicle kilometres travelled), road network, traffic patterns, fleet composition, as well as CCAM users, non-users, and their interaction with CCAM within the societal scenario.

Although different evaluation areas focus on various impacts, their results should be complementary. Consequently, the chosen scenarios should not contradict one another across impact areas.

The required number of scenarios depends on the evaluation scope, research questions, context addressed, and available resources. When balancing the depth of analyses with resources, the estimated effect size and exposure should guide scenario setting. It is advised to include scenarios where both positive and negative effects might occur.

Relevant aspects to describe per scenario type include:

- Traffic scenarios:
 - CCAM penetration rates, at least those required by the societal scenarios
 - Road environment and layout (intersection types, length of sections, number of lanes, speed limits)
 - Features of digital infrastructure (coverage and features of connectivity, etc.)
 - Traffic volumes

- Fleet composition in traffic (size, category, age of vehicles, engine and fuel types, pedestrians, cyclists)
- Service scenarios:
 - Service concept
 - Business or funding concept
 - Vehicle category
 - Operating environment
- Driving scenarios:
 - Vehicle whose behaviour is being addressed (ego vehicle)
 - Another vehicle or object to interact with
 - Road environment
- User scenarios:
 - Mobility behaviour (motorised and non-motorised travel modes)
 - Attitudes
 - Socio-demographic characteristics
- User behaviour scenarios:
 - User interacting with the system
 - Non-user affected by the system
 - Interaction with CCAM
 - Context for interaction (e.g. where it happens, in which conditions)

Within one traffic scenario, several driving scenarios typically take place. Within one traffic scenario, several parallel service scenarios may also take place. One user behaviour scenario may apply to one or several user scenarios.

If use of low-level scenario results is planned to address higher-level scenarios, it is advisable to plan it at this stage. This may involve scaling up to regional estimates or societal scenarios. Scaling up refers to estimating the impacts over a broader region and a longer time period compared to the lower-level scenarios. See the separate guideline on scaling up.

If scaling up from low-level scenario results to higher-level scenarios is considered, this should be planned at this stage. Scaling up refers to estimating impacts over broader regions and longer periods compared to the lower-level scenarios (see Guideline 3.14).

Example

Example of the process for defining **traffic scenarios**:

One impact assessment objective was to estimate the impacts of automated passenger cars on emissions. The societal scenario covered the European motorway network with 50% automated passenger cars in traffic, which included passenger cars and heavy goods vehicles. The baseline was the traffic and vehicle fleet of today.

Traffic simulations and an emissions tool were chosen for estimating impacts. The societal scenario specified European motorways, passenger cars and heavy goods vehicles, and the penetration rate of automated vehicles among passenger cars. Representative traffic scenarios were derived to align with the societal scenario by:

- Analysing the whole European motorway network to identify *speed limit* and *number of lanes* combinations covering at least 1% of the network length, resulting in 10 different combinations.
- Determining traffic volumes by calculating motorway capacities (2250 vehicles/hour/lane) and dividing the volume range into four simulation input flows (500, 1000, 1500, and 2000 vehicles/hour/lane).

- Determining the share of heavy goods vehicles from traffic data. It was found to vary with traffic volume.
- Including baseline (0% CCAM) and treatment (50% CCAM) conditions, the process resulted in 80 traffic scenarios (2 penetration rates * 10 motorway types * 4 traffic volumes).

Example of a **traffic scenario**: A 5 km section of a 3-lane motorway with an entrance and exit, 130 km/h speed limit, 1500 vehicles/hour/lane, and 8% of heavy vehicles.

Vehicles in traffic scenario simulations can perform various **driving scenarios** [16], such as following a vehicle, motorway merging or performing a lane change. Example of a driving scenario description of a discretionary lane change:

Examples of **service scenarios**:

1. Robotaxi service (shared and single-user rides), fully automated passenger cars, operating within city boundaries
2. Public transport service (shuttle buses), integrated with tourism tickets, operated between transport hubs and tourist sites
3. Logistics service (autonomous delivery robots), part of online delivery system, operating within 2 km of a supermarket

Examples of **user scenarios**:

1. Regular car commuter, low new technology acceptance, good income, older adult, suburban resident
2. Regular public transport user, multimodal mobility, high technology acceptance, low income, younger adult, urban resident

Examples of **user behaviour scenarios**:

1. Relevant for User scenario 1: Car commuter using automated driving system:
 - Activating the system when entering a motorway
 - Taking over control when approaching an exit ramp
2. Relevant for User scenario 2: CCAM-based on-demand public transport user:
 - Request a ride via app
 - Locating and entering the vehicle
 - Exiting the vehicle in an unfamiliar area

Guideline 3.12. How to define relevant indicators for impact assessment

There are two primary types of indicators: result indicators, which directly answer the research questions, and intermediary indicators, which are necessary for deriving the result indicators. Some research questions may require several intermediary indicators, while others can be directly determined through result indicators without intermediary indicators.

Evidence of the changes induced by CCAM is gathered by comparing indicator values under the same scenarios for both baseline and treatment conditions. Indicators can be assessed either quantitatively or qualitatively, depending on the available methods, tools, data, and resources.

In some impact areas, defining result indicators is straightforward. Specific indicators may already be specified in the project proposal and must be included in the evaluation plan. Policymakers may have set clear targets or policy goals for certain impact areas, such as the EU's objectives for reducing greenhouse gas emissions from transport. Therefore, if environmental impacts are within the evaluation scope, a suitable indicator for their assessment would be greenhouse gas emissions.

Result indicators should be contextualised with a denominator that clarifies the temporal and spatial scope, such as *per year in the EU* or *per kilometre driven*. This enables meaningful comparisons of indicator values between treatment and baseline conditions or across different scenarios. The choice of denominator depends on the research question and the nature of the indicator. The denominators can be an area (e.g. city, country or the EU), a specific road section or type, the total vehicle kilometres travelled (VKT), a specific user or population group, or a combination of these. Examples of result indicators include greenhouse gas emissions per VKT on motorways in the EU or number of passenger car trips per day per user. For intermediary indicators, the method usually provides the context.

In cases where identifying indicators is more complex, the following steps can be useful:

1. Break down each low-level research question into key concepts and dimensions to identify what needs to be measured. Note any information on scope or relevant user groups within the question.
2. For each key concept, identify indicators that effectively measure or describe the phenomenon. Choose indicators relevant to the project and consider those used in other studies for comparability. Expertise in the evaluation and impact area is essential, as is reviewing the recommended indicators for each impact area in Chapter 4.
3. From the identified indicators, select those that are measurable with the available data, methods, tools, and resources. This requires iteration with other evaluation planning steps and a feasibility check of the overall evaluation plan.
4. Contextualise the indicator with a suitable denominator, such as *emissions per VKT on motorways in the EU* or *passenger car trips per day per user*.

See Chapter 4 for recommended result indicators for each impact area.

Example

Research question: *What are the impacts of the CCAM system on the number of accidents?*

Result indicator: *Number of prevented accidents per year in EU27* (specified based on project scope).

Setting intermediate indicators:

1. Key concepts identified: *number of target accidents, accident risk, exposure, severity*.
2. The evaluation was based on the *number of target accidents*, with changes in risk, exposure, and severity reflected in this number.
3. Safety simulation software was chosen to estimate accident risk in simulated driving scenarios leading to the intermediary indicator: *accident risk per driving scenario*.

4. Intermediate indicators were similarly defined also for exposure (e.g. *total VKT* or *frequency of relevant conflicts*) and severity.
5. The result indicators defined in step 2 were calculated based on the intermediate indicators from steps 3 and 4.

Guideline 3.13. How to set a method for answering a research question

Each research question needs a method that can provide an answer. Selecting suitable methods and tools requires considering: a solid theoretical background, validity for the intended purpose, and feasibility within available resources.

For each evaluation and impact area, begin by drafting an overview of the evaluation process steps, including data sources and relevant tools and methods, to assess the required indicator values and effects. Ensure this overview covers all research questions within the area. Setting up this process and identifying potential gaps is iterative, continuously elaborated throughout the evaluation planning phase.

A single method or tool can answer one or multiple research questions with overlapping needs. Conversely, some research question may require multiple methods and tools.

The scope of each research question can guide important considerations, such as spatial extent or relevant user groups. For each question, start by conducting an overview of suitable evaluation methods and tools available to the project team. Describe the input requirements and output indicators of each tool. Then check whether these outputs match the input needs of subsequent evaluation steps.

Describe the **limitations and assumptions** of each method and tool, verifying their suitability for addressing the indicators to be evaluated. For example:

- Macroscopic traffic simulation can assess regional impacts but may lack sufficient detail for assessing specific changes in traffic flow level (see Chapter 4.3.5 for more on simulation approaches).
- Microscopic traffic simulation can assess traffic flow impacts but may not be suitable for accident analysis unless it aligns with the modelling of safety-critical situations.
- Conventional driver models in microscopic traffic simulations, describing human driving behaviour in normal traffic, may not accurately model automated driving in conflict situations.
- Expert assessment can provide qualitative insight but may lack precise and accurate quantitative estimates. The complexity of scenarios assessed by experts should not exceed their ability to reasonably employ pattern-matching based on past experiences.

Estimate the required resources (human resources, time, and budget) for applying each method or tool and producing indicator values. Check the feasibility of external data needs, including acquisition of the required data, its costs, and processing requirements. Designate responsible partners for each impact area and research question to ensure proper coverage.

Ensure the validity, meaning that indicators measure what they are supposed to measure, and reliability, meaning that the methods produce consistent results under consistent conditions, for all indicator-method combinations.

Prepare alternative plans for methods with potential uncertainties (e.g. in terms of success of tool development, availability of input data, or sufficiency of resources). The plans may also change after feasibility checking (see Guideline 3.8). If direct inputs for a method are unavailable or unreliable, consider proxy indicators from other measurements or literature-based estimates, or use qualitative assessments to estimate the magnitude and direction of changes.

It is recommended to test the methods as early as possible to verify that they function as intended and are feasible within the resource constraints. Chapter 4 provides further details on methods applicable to different

research questions for different evaluation and impact areas, as well as their strengths, limitations, and requirements.

Example

The impact of a CCAM system on CO₂ emissions is planned to be estimated using an emission calculation tool, which has been found valid for this purpose if the evaluation team has sufficient resources to use it. This tool requires output from microscopic traffic simulations used in the impact assessment of traffic flow efficiency. Adjusting simulation parameters requires input on the driving behaviour of automated vehicles, such as data derived from the analysis of field-experiment vehicle data.

The societal scenario sets the temporal scope to the year 2023. The emission calculation tool needs statistics on the vehicle fleet and its characteristics from 2023. The tool's output indicator, CO₂ emissions per VKT per vehicle category, aligns with the project's needs.

This process is illustrated graphically below, presenting data sources and steps in chronological order.

Guideline 3.14. How to consider the scaling up of results in the methodology

Scaling up is necessary when estimating impacts on the societal scenario based on results from lower-level scenarios. Different methods can be applied for scaling up of CCAM impacts, with the choice depending on the impact area and available tools. The main approaches include statistics-based and macroscopic modelling-based upscaling.

The **statistics-based** approach uses available data from statistics or other datasets to scale up impacts observed in lower-level scenarios. For example, data on vehicle kilometres travelled (VKT) by road type, vehicle category, and traffic conditions, on the frequency of certain events, or on the distribution of people across user population segments.

When using this statistics-based approach, it is recommended to set up lower-level scenarios that are representative of the region and timeframe targeted in the societal scenario. Defining representative scenarios requires determining the prevalence of each scenario, such as the frequency of a single scenario in the broader context.

Microscopic simulation can serve as an intermediary step when using VKT for the prevalence of traffic scenarios. The effects of CCAM observed in the simulations of the traffic scenarios can then be scaled up to the region targeted in the societal scenario by weighting the prevalence of these scenarios across space, time, and population. Identifying the necessary external data or statistics early is important to ensure sufficient time for sourcing, accessing, collecting, and formatting the data if required.

If a **macroscopic model** is available for the region targeted in the societal scenario, it can directly provide results on CCAM impacts, provided that the implications of CCAM can be adequately represented in the model. However, this approach requires the availability of a suitable model for the area of interest, and such models can be difficult to develop or obtain.

Both statistical and modelling approaches can require substantial effort if no existing dataset or model is available. However, they provide insights that field experiment data and expert judgement alone cannot achieve. Often, the evaluated scenarios do not cover the full societal scenario spectrum, requiring assumptions to fill in the gaps. Basic sensitivity analyses are recommended to estimate the influence of these assumptions, and all assumptions must be transparently reported along with the results of the sensitivity analyses.

Example

Examples of data needs for scaling up CCAM impacts:

- **Traffic safety impact assessment:** Data is needed on the frequency, type, and severity of accidents within the CCAM operational domain during the period of interest. Scenario-specific effects can be weighted using the share of target accidents per scenario to scale them up. Official accident databases, such as national or in-depth accident databases, are valuable data sources.
- **Traffic flow impact assessment:** Data on typical traffic volumes in the target region and network is required to weigh and scale the traffic scenario-specific effects to regional level. This data can be obtained, for example, from national or regional road operators.
- **People mobility impact assessment:** Data on travel patterns and needs of different socio-demographic groups in the target region is needed to scale the user scenario-specific effects to the entire population of interest. Regional or national travel surveys are common data sources.

Guideline 3.15. How to consider intended direct impacts, indirect and unintended impacts, and the impacts on non-users

Ensuring a comprehensive evaluation of the effects of CCAM requires considering intended and unintended, direct and indirect, short-term and long-term impacts, as well as impacts on both users and non-users. The evaluation process should incorporate the nine impact mechanisms identified for CCAM [17]. It is recommended that these mechanisms are used in all impact areas of CCAM studies:

1. Direct modification of the driving task, driving behaviour or travel experience
2. Direct influence of infrastructure
3. Indirect modification of CCAM user behaviour
4. Indirect modification of non-user behaviour
5. Modification of interaction between CCAM systems and other road users (non-users of CCAM)
6. Modification of exposure/amount of travel
7. Modification of modal choice
8. Modification of route choice
9. Modification of consequences due to different vehicle design

The evaluation team should explicitly identify in the evaluation plan which mechanisms can be addressed in the project, specifically:

- The impacts of which mechanisms can be measured in the field experiment.
- The impacts of which mechanisms can be addressed by simulation or by other data collection methods.
- The impacts of which mechanisms are relevant for the CCAM system under evaluation but should be addressed by other means.

If some mechanisms cannot be addressed quantitatively, a qualitative assessment of likely long-term impacts could be feasible. This can involve expert insights from system developers and testers or findings from the literature. Even if a study cannot address each mechanism, acknowledging all relevant impact mechanisms is advised. By combining quantitative assessments with supporting evidence from the literature, it is possible to estimate the implications of all mechanisms, at least on a qualitative scale (e.g. direction of impact: increase, decrease or no change; estimated magnitude: small, medium or large).

Example

The evaluation team of a large-scale project on automation of passenger cars mapped how the nine impact mechanisms [17] were considered in traffic safety impact assessment. Some mechanisms were addressed through simulations or driving simulator studies, while others were covered by results of other impact areas or external literature. These results were then qualitatively analysed for the direction of the impact (*increase, no change, decrease*) and its size (*small, medium, large*).

Further reading

Innamaa, S., Smith, S., Barnard, Y., Rainville, L., Rakoff, H., Horiguchi, R., & Gellerman, H. (2018). Impact mechanisms. In *Trilateral Impact Assessment Framework for Automation in Road Transportation: Version 2.0* (pp. 15–24). Trilateral Impact Assessment Sub-Group for Automation in Road Transportation Working Group. https://www.connectedautomateddriving.eu/wp-content/uploads/2018/03/Trilateral_IA_Framework_April2018.pdf

Bjorvatn, A., et al. (2021). L3Pilot Deliverable 7.4: Impact Evaluation Results. Annex A1.6. https://l3pilot.eu/fileadmin/user_upload/Downloads/Deliverables/Update_14102021/L3Pilot-SP7-D7.4-Impact_Evaluation_Results-v1.0-for_website.pdf

3.4. Data specification and data tools

The guidelines for data specification and data tools outlined in this chapter facilitate alignment of the data collection and processing with the requirements of the evaluation. The outcome of this planning phase provides guidance on:

- What data needs to be collected
- Why the data is collected
- How data is processed and stored
- Who are the actors involved.

This ensures that the collected data¹⁴ will support the evaluation.

The data specification and data tools guidelines in this chapter are relevant if any of the cases below apply:

1. An evaluation method has specific requirements for its input data to be collected within the project, and the evaluation partner is not directly collecting that data.
2. It is planned that multiple partners will collect comparable data.
3. Data is shared between partners.

The data specification and data tools step may not be as relevant when a dataset is collected by an evaluation partner to support their own work and is not shared among multiple partners, as the data harmonisation aspect is less critical in these cases.

Data specification describes what kind of data the project collects, how it is formatted, and how it is stored. It ensures that data can be exchanged and used seamlessly among project partners. While data specification does not describe the experimental design of the data collection (see Chapter 3.5), it should describe contextual data that facilitate correct understanding of the design and usage and interpretation of the data. This includes whether the data was collected under baseline or treatment conditions, and situational variables relevant for the planned method (see Chapter 3.3). The data specification is the basis for a common data format,¹⁵ which is used for storing and processing the data with common tools.

Data collection tools refer to devices and programs used for data collection, such as data loggers installed in vehicles. In some cases, partners must agree on using common tools and how they are calibrated and configured to ensure comparable results. In other cases, simply harmonising the data format may be sufficient.

Data processing tools refer to a chain of scripts or programs used to process the data. Processing includes converting logged data into the common data format and calculating derived measures.¹⁶ A project may also need to agree on data storage and exchange tools. Examples of data storage tools are (federated) databases and data spaces which facilitate the exchange of data between stakeholders. Interfaces for uploading and downloading data may also be part of the tools.

It is recommended that data specification and tools are clearly documented, either as part of the evaluation plan or in a dedicated data management document. Version control systems are highly recommended to ensure that every partner is using the same version of the specification and tools at all times. A documented data specification and a description of data tools is essentially an agreement between the data providers and the evaluation team on the technical characteristics of the data.

The guidelines in this chapter do not mandate any specific data formats or data handling methods, leaving it for each project to decide. The CCAM Data Sharing Framework [18] gives detailed advice on data sharing, both from technical and contractual perspectives.

¹⁴ Collected data: Data collected with sensors, questionnaires or by other means. Also called acquired data. The collected data is also often referred to as 'raw data', but the term might be misleading, because some data processing might be performed by the sensors or other devices collecting the data.

¹⁵ Common data format: Provides the data specification in a manner that allows for computer-readable and writable implementation. It defines variables, their units, data types and other relevant specifications (see Guideline 3.17)

¹⁶ Derived measures: Measures not directly collected but calculated from the collected data.

The guidelines below cover the following topics:

- How to set up a process for defining data specification and data tools
- How to define common data formats
- How to define the roles and access rights related to data
- How to define the data flow in the processing chain
- How to overcome common pitfalls related to data

These steps may be interconnected and require iterations; they are not necessarily hierarchical or sequential. Note that the best chronological order of tasks may differ from the sequence of guidelines below, depending on the project.

Guideline 3.16. How to set up a process for defining data specification and data tools

A documented data specification and a description of data tools is essentially an agreement between the data providers and data users on the technical characteristics of the data. To ensure that all perspectives are included, it is recommended that the evaluation team establishes a working group with representatives from partners responsible for providing, processing, and using the data. This group must also include partners working on the evaluation methods, not just data owners. Thus, the members of a data specification working group include:

- **Data user** (evaluation team): Specifies the data needs of evaluation and understands dependencies between methods and data.
- **Data provider**: Assesses the feasibility of providing requested data and under which conditions.
- **Data processor**: Develops or uses scripts to process shared data into an agreed format.
- **Database developer**: Implements and maintains a database for storing the agreed data.

The process of defining data specification and tools is likely to be iterative. Use version control to track all changes, ensuring every partner is aware of what has been agreed upon, when, and by whom.

Data specification and tools must be aligned with the evaluation plan. Therefore, the starting point for defining data specification is the data requirements identified for the planned evaluation methods (Chapter 3.3). It is important to:

- Determine the data required (including combinations of data) and the contextual data (metadata) needed.
- Engage in iterative discussions to balance what data providers can collect with what is required for calculating indicators and conducting evaluations.
- Be flexible and open to alternatives if specific data is unavailable. On the other hand, sometimes available data collection or processing technologies may inspire new evaluation approaches.
- Facilitate continuous dialogue between the technical team and evaluation team throughout the project to mitigate risks of failing to deliver suitable data for evaluation. Early dialogue helps align expectations and clarify data needs between providers, processors, and users.

Request that data providers share an example dataset in the common data format to the evaluation team as early as possible. This ensures a shared understanding and verifies that the workflow functions correctly. Likewise, the evaluation team should provide an example of the preferred data format. Early conversion of collected data into the common data format can help identify inconsistencies between collected and required data.

Harmonisation and agreement on the common data format and test data help data processing and evaluating partners to better anticipate what is achievable with the collected data. Therefore, test the data flow as soon as possible.

It is essential that the agreed data specification and tools are also communicated to all data providers, clearly outlining the requirements and providing the rationale behind specific data formats. For each data provider, identify the operational point of contact, ensuring someone familiar with the data collection process, specifications and tools is available to address issues. Once the agreements are established, any deviations from the agreed specifications should be documented and communicated.

Example

Data specification process:

1. **Specification of data requirements:** Identification of the necessary data for the planned evaluation methods, translation of the needed indicators and related contextual data into a list of signals to be collected, specification of the preferred data format.
2. **Explanation of data requirements:** Detailing what will be evaluated with the requested data and the consequences of missing data.
3. **Discussion on feasibility:** Assessment of whether the collected data and relevant contextual data can be shared in the specified format and under what conditions.
4. **Iteration if needed:** Return to step 1 if data cannot be provided (e.g. due to a lack of suitable sensors or critical data sensitivity).
5. **Communication of agreements:** Sharing of the final data specification and tools with all data owners, allowing for questions and feedback.
6. **Refining if necessary:** Revisit step 1 if critical issues are identified.
7. **Provision of sample data:** Sharing data samples in the agreed format to verify understanding and a functioning workflow, and to spot inconsistencies between collected and required data.
8. **Maintaining dialogue:** Ensuring continuous communication between data providers and users, documenting any deviations from the agreements until all data has been provided.

Guideline 3.17. How to define common data formats

A common data format provides the data specification in a manner that allows for computer-processable implementation. Various file formats can be used, including ASAM MDF, HDF5, XML or CSV, sometimes referred to as data formats. In EU-CEM, the file format is only one aspect of the common data format.

The definition of the common data format includes at least the following:

- File format
- Name of variables
- Description of variables
- Data types of variables (e.g. integer, floating point number, text), size (if applicable)
- Unit, frequency, and resolution of variables
- Upper and lower limits of possible values of variables
- Coordinate systems in which the variables are to be interpreted (e.g. the version of GPS coordinates, ego-centric or allocentric, direction of axes)
- Timestamps used
- Coding of missing values (e.g. NaN, -1)
- Coding of categorical values (e.g. response options in a questionnaire, 1 = Yes, 0 = No)

Establishing common file naming conventions is recommended to facilitate data usage. File names might include identifiers such as experiment identifications (IDs), driving scenarios, use cases or vehicle IDs.

The common data format may also include details such as calibration values used in data collection or interpolation methods for handling missing values (e.g. zero-order hold, linear interpolation). For complex

data processing, it is advisable to develop and share common data processing tools (e.g. as scripts) to ensure consistency in data handling.

Multiple common data formats may be necessary within a project. For example, one format may be used for collected data and another for the derived measures used in evaluation after the data processing chain has been applied.

The CCAM Data Sharing Framework [18] gives recommendations on the file formats.

Example

An example is the L3Pilot Common Data Format [19], which includes the following elements:

- Top Level (name)
- Second Level (name)
- Datatype
- Size [byte]
- Size on top level [byte]
- Description (written description, explanation for the coding, e.g. 0 = baseline, 1 = treatment)
- Unit
- Frequency (Hz)
- Resolution
- Lower limit (minimum value)
- Upper limit (maximum value)
- n/a (coding of the missing values, e.g. NaN or -1)
- Interpolation (the method which should be used to replace missing values, e.g. zero-order hold or linear)

The L3Pilot Common Data Format can be implemented, for example, using the HDF5 file format.

Guideline 3.18. How to define the roles and access rights related to data

Defining the actors involved in the data flow¹⁷ clarifies responsibilities and ensures everyone knows who does what and who has access to the data. Typically, at least three roles are defined:

- **Data providers** collect the data, for example through field experiments, participant interviews or simulations.
- **Data processors** convert the collected data into usable formats for evaluation, such as by cleaning the data and calculating derived measures.
- **Data users** utilise the data within the project; these may be members of the evaluation team.

A single partner may take on multiple roles, but not all stakeholders need equal access rights, even when the data is stored in a common database. For example, data providers, and possibly a specified data-processing partner, may only have access to their own data.

Some data may be too sensitive to share with the data-processing partners or data users. For example, data containing personal information may be subject to data protection regulations such as the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) [20]. Additionally, data may affect the business interests of partners if it is commercially sensitive and enables benchmarking the tested system against competitors.

¹⁷ Data flow: The process where collected data are transformed for and within the evaluation process through a chain of processing scripts utilising common data formats.

The CCAM Data Sharing Framework [18] provides detailed guidance on establishing agreements between stakeholders in a project and on ensuring the privacy of the data.

Example

The roles assigned in a project with confidential data [20]:

Each data-providing partner selected a **dedicated data processor** from the evaluation team. Each data processor had full access to the data from the respective data provider. This arrangement allowed the development and testing of common data processing scripts without requiring the data provider to repeatedly run the scripts on behalf of the evaluation team.

The data-processing partners converted the collected data into the agreed common data format. Before sharing the data with the evaluation team, all processed data were pooled across data providers to prevent benchmarking between them. This role assignment ensured that the data were reviewed by someone other than the data provider without revealing potentially confidential data across all partners.

In projects with non-confidential data, data providers can directly upload their data to a data sharing platform for processing and evaluation.

Guideline 3.19. How to define the data flow in the processing chain

The data flow process may include multiple processing and storage steps, and it should be thoroughly documented and reproducible.

A key principle is ensuring that all analyses can be rerun easily if the original data are updated. In practice, this means all processing steps should be implemented as **software scripts**, avoiding manual modifications or interventions. Scripts should be maintained in a version control repository (e.g. GitLab) to ensure that all developers and users work with the same versions. Common databases or collaboration platforms can be used for data exchange among partners.

It is recommended to split the processing into a series of modular scripts with clearly defined inputs and outputs, rather than using one large script. This simplifies maintenance, allows parallel development, and facilitates the creation of alternative scripts if necessary. If different partners are responsible for different parts of the data processing chain, intermediate outputs and inputs should be included in the data specification, with a common data format to ensure compatibility.

Quality checks should be integrated into the data flow. These can include:

- **Data quality checks**, such as visual inspection (i.e. “everything looks good”) or automatic checks to ensure that values fall within expected ranges and that the amount of missing data remains acceptable.
- **Script quality checks**, such as unit tests for individual script functions and integration tests for combined modules, using both test data and real project data.

These checks should flag any issues with the data or with the data processing before the data is used for evaluation.

Filtering, such as signal smoothing, is often necessary during data processing and must be clearly defined within scripts, as it can significantly affect results. Consistent filtering criteria should be applied across all data sources, and data users must be informed of any filtering performed on the data to ensure correct interpretation.

In some projects, additional processing steps before data sharing, such as anonymisation and pseudonymisation, may be required to avoid exposing the origin of the data or personal information of the participants. This step can be performed by data providers or by dedicated data-processing partners under

appropriate non-disclosure agreements if needed. Sometimes this is only necessary when data is shared externally. The Data Sharing Framework [18] gives detailed guidance on this.

Example

A dedicated working group maps the whole data flow of the project, detailing each step from data collection and conversion into a common data format to quality checks, filtering, annotation, and calculation of indicators. The indicator data are then stored in a cloud database accessible to all relevant partners with appropriate access rights.

Next, each step of the mapped flowchart is established as a project in Gitlab, enabling the creation of small, manageable, and modular scripts to automate the data flow. Inputs and outputs of each script are explicitly defined, and version control ensures that only data processed with the latest script versions are accepted for subsequent steps. Quality checks cover both data and scripts, with unit and integration tests verifying functionality.

Clear documentation for each script details its purpose, functionality, and usage instructions. The documentation is stored both as README files within the version control system and in a collaborative document management tool accessible to all project partners.

This approach enables partners to apply the scripts regardless of their involvement in software development, ensuring data are shared in a harmonised format and processed in an automated, transparent, and reproducible way. The final processed data are stored in a cloud database, allowing the entire evaluation team to access them for evaluation purposes.

Guideline 3.20. How to overcome common pitfalls related to data

CCAM projects often encounter specific pitfalls related to data collection, processing and usage:

1) A derived measure required for evaluation cannot be calculated from the collected data.

Involve the evaluation team early in the data specification process to allow them to specify what collected data or derived measures they need. The data providers should assess whether they can meet these requirements. Flexibility from both sides is required if adjustments are needed. See Guideline 3.16 for how to handle this situation.

2) Collected data lack sufficient contextual information on the data collection conditions for correct interpretation.

Data specification must include contextual data such as weather conditions, road and infrastructure characteristics, traffic conditions, and user groups involved. This information is essential for selecting relevant data, understanding variability in the results, and determining the extent to which they can be generalised to other contexts.

Document any deviations from the data specification and unexpected events during data collection, as they may influence data interpretation. For example, minor deviations from a designated route may not render the data unusable, but determination of this requires documenting the deviations.

3) Data collected or processed by different partners is not comparable.

Ensure that all partners follow the agreed experimental design (see Chapter 3.5), use a common data format (see the Guideline 3.17), and apply shared, version-controlled processing scripts.

Example

Common pitfalls and solutions:

Pitfall: The derived measure cannot be calculated from the collected data.

- **Example:** The evaluation team requires a derived measure “distance to lane markings” to study the lane-keeping performance, but the field test vehicles do not detect lane markings and instead follow a pre-determined centre line from a high-definition map.
- **Solution:** After discussions, the data providers agreed to share the vehicles’ deviations from the centre line. With an assumed lane width, the evaluation team estimated the distance to the lane markings from this information.

Pitfall: The conditions under which the data were collected are not sufficiently known to ensure accurate interpretations when calculating a derived measure.

- **Example:** Speed measurements show significant differences between days, but without contextual data (e.g. traffic conditions during the experiments) it is unclear whether the differences result from vehicle behaviour or external factors like congestion. Therefore, the measurements are less valuable for evaluation purposes.
- **Solution:** Collect and document contextual data to ensure accurate interpretation of collected data.

Pitfall: Data collected by different partners are not comparable.

- **Example:** Data was collected on roads with different speed limits, or one experiment collected data only in free flow situations and another in congestion.
- **Solution:** Harmonise experimental design and document all variations to ensure comparability.

Pitfall: Data processed by different partners are not comparable.

- **Example:** When filtering outliers, one partner applies strict conditions for a “valid” data point, while another filters only the clearly “wrong” measurements. This difference leads to different results.
- **Solution:** Agree on standardised data processing protocols and filtering criteria across all partners.

3.5. Experimental design

This chapter provides guidelines for designing appropriate experiments to collect the data needed to answer each research question. Selecting methods for data collection—whether through field experiments, simulations or other approaches—requires careful planning to ensure the validity and reliability of data. Key considerations include defining treatment and baseline conditions, determining sample sizes, selecting participants, and structuring data collection phases.

Agreement on the experimental design is important for the feasibility of the evaluation plan execution in CCAM projects. Real-world testing opportunities are often limited to systems of low technology readiness level (TRL), making it impossible to accommodate every preference of the evaluation team. Some experimental design elements may have been established during the project preparation phase, particularly if they are also key project characteristics. This chapter focuses on selecting suitable design elements that can still be determined during the project.

The experimental design must support the **data collection** required for each research question. If not, iterative adjustments to the evaluation plan are necessary (see Figure 4 and Guideline 3.8). For example, if a research question requires data from ordinary drivers but regulations prohibit such testing on public roads, alternative sources, such as test track experiments, should be considered.

A single CCAM project may involve multiple **experiments**, each potentially involving several teams, such as a technical team, a test site team, and an evaluation team. Early and consistent communication is key to ensure a feasible evaluation plan and efficient use of resources, and to avoid a mismatch between evaluation needs and the practicalities at test sites. Establishing standardised working procedures with clearly defined roles, responsibilities, goals and schedules early on is highly beneficial. Additionally, ensuring a common understanding through test site visits or direct discussions between evaluation and test site teams is recommended.

The experimental design must specify the **baseline and treatment** conditions. In some cases, the baseline may reflect future rather than current conditions. Factors such as demographic shifts (e.g. aging population or more non-motorists), increased adoption of automation, and vehicle fleet electrification can significantly alter the results if unaccounted for. Predicting these shifts when defining a future baseline helps ensure that the experimental design captures the emerging impacts caused by CCAM only.

The guidelines below cover the following topics:

- How to choose the experimental approach for a research question
- How to consider the elements of the experimental design in the evaluation plan
- How to plan the experimental design of field experiments
- How to plan the experimental design for virtual environments with participants
- How to select participants for your experiment
- How to provide participants with the most realistic user experience possible
- How to define the treatment and baseline conditions

These steps may be interconnected and require iterations; they are not necessarily hierarchical or sequential. Note that the best chronological order of tasks may also differ from the sequence of guidelines below, depending on the project.

Guideline 3.21. How to choose the experimental approach for a research question

Evaluating a single research question may utilise data from several approaches. CCAM projects typically use several approaches for data collection, including:

- Field experiments (from limited to full CCAM system experience)
 - On test tracks
 - In confined zones
 - On public roads
- Virtual environments, such as virtual reality or (mechanised) driving simulators.
- Modelling and simulations, including microscopic or macroscopic traffic simulations, activity-based modelling, emissions models, and air quality and noise models.
- Subjective approaches, such as written descriptions, user studies, expert consultations, and citizen engagement.

Field experiments can be complemented with other approaches like virtual environments, modelling, and subjective studies to assess the potential impacts at higher CCAM penetration rates than currently possible in field experiments or to cover a wider range of conditions. Each method's implications for the validity of the results must be understood. Field experiments can also complement other approaches, for example, by offering input for impact assessment simulations or other virtual environments to improve their realism.

Ideally, **field experiments** would use CCAM systems of high technology readiness level in real-world conditions. This includes testing on public roads or in an environment where the future systems will be deployed, with potential future users of the system. However, since this is often not yet possible, alternatives like controlled environments, test tracks, simulated environments, or on-road tests with safety drivers or

operators are used. If local regulations permit public road testing, it is possible to collect data on driving behaviour and automated vehicle interaction with other road users in real traffic. Still, acknowledge that safety drivers are part of the safety protocol and have a different role and behaviour than future CCAM users.

If real-world CCAM testing with real users is not possible, alternatives like test rides with vehicles driven by safety drivers, use of test-tracks, or in extreme cases use of storyboards, videos or written descriptions can be used to describe the system to participants, with opinions gathered through interviews, questionnaires or focus groups.

The experimental design should ideally cover the CCAM system's entire **operational design domain** (ODD) with sufficient variability in conditions. At minimum, it should cover key parts of the ODD relevant to the societal scenario addressed by the research questions. If comprehensive coverage is not possible, the evaluation plan must clarify which ODD conditions were included in the experiment and how the data collected reflect those conditions.

See Chapter 4 for details on different approaches per impact area.

Example

Example research question: *What is the impact of CCAM on the accident risk?*

The consortium initially considered collecting real-world data from automated passenger cars on public roads. However, due to the safety protocols of the data providers, only safety drivers were permitted, and safety-critical situations had to be avoided. Thus, the field experiments alone would not provide sufficient data for a thorough assessment of the impacts on accident risk.

To overcome this, simulation of the safety-critical events was identified as the main method to complement the field experiments. Field data would provide information on incident frequency in regular driving conditions and support the parameterisation and validation of the simulation model, which would then assess accident risk across various driving scenarios.

Guideline 3.22. How to consider the elements of the experimental design in the evaluation plan

The experimental design consists of several elements, each of which must be considered during evaluation planning. Research questions and data needs determine the essential (*must-have*) and desirable (*nice-to-have*) requirements for each element, alongside external constraints such as:

- Local and national regulation related to location, driver type, timing, border-crossing, permissions, insurance constraints or data protection
- Ethics and safety procedures
- Available resources, including equipment, budget, time, people, and skills
- Technology readiness of the CCAM system

Each element should be optimised to fulfil the research question requirements within these constraints. Backup plans should be developed, and the impact of alternative choices on results validity and applicability must be assessed and documented. Describe the non-ideal factors and how they affect the results in the report that describes the evaluation method.

Iteration between experimental design, evaluation methods, and data specification is necessary until a suitable evaluation plan is achieved.

The table below lists the elements of the experimental design and their consequences on the evaluation. The experiment is a Field Operational Test (FOT) when all its elements are on the more complex or larger scale of the range.

Element	Range	Consequences on evaluation
Sample size	Small to large	<p>Smaller sample sizes in terms of e.g. number of participants, observations, vehicles, test environments, or scenarios, allow in-depth analysis of complex interactions.</p> <p>Larger samples provide more generalisable results and statistical power. Power analysis can determine appropriate sample size.</p>
Sample demographics	Limited to diverse	<p>Limited demographics allow focusing on specific user segments. Diverse demographics enable population-level estimates.</p>
Nature of data	Subjective to objective	<p>Subjective data are often qualitative, more open to interpretation, and time-sensitive, but can provide rich insights. Objective data are often quantitative, consistent, and repeatable. They can be more constrained by CCAM TRL than subjective data.</p>
Data measurement	Proxy to direct	<p>Direct measurements are preferable, but proxy measurements can be used when direct data are unavailable or unreliable. Proxy methods must be well-documented (see Chapter 3.4).</p>
Degree of realism of the experience	Written description to real-life experience of CCAM use	<p>Higher realism (e.g. real-world tests) improves reliability but depends on technology readiness. Virtual environments (simulators, virtual reality) can mimic reality but have limitations in participant responses. Written descriptions offer lowest realism but can be easily provided to large populations.</p>
User experience in field experiments	Single demonstration ride to non-supervised automated vehicle use	<p>Safety protocols limit testing possibilities. Ideally, participants would use CCAM unsupervised over longer periods. However, sometimes it is only possible to provide single demonstration rides. These offer limited but valuable insights.</p>
Experimental environment	Short fixed test route to extensive road network	<p>Short, fixed test route limit generalisability. Extensive road networks provide broader insights under varied conditions.</p>
Technology readiness level (TRL)	Low to high TRL	<p>Low TRL may not fully reflect the future system but can offer preliminary insights.</p> <p>Gradual testing by incremental pilot phases can mitigate the gap between low-TRL technology tested in the real world and a high TRL assumed for impact assessment. Likely requires a sequence of projects.</p>

Duration	Short to long (e.g. from single drives to several months or more)	Longer durations provide more depth and can capture changes in user behaviour over time and more varying conditions. Short durations are more cost-effective but less comprehensive.
Baseline and treatment condition	Multiple alternatives (see Guideline 3.27)	Baseline and treatment conditions are required for impact assessment. Without them, impacts cannot be determined. Other evaluation areas, such as technical functioning and user evaluation, do not always require baseline data.

Example

Decisions for an experimental design and the reasoning behind the choices, to answer research questions addressing subjective experience of CCAM use:

Element	Decision	Reasoning
Sample size	At least 100 observations per topic	Power analysis indicates this sample size is sufficient for statistical power.
Sample demographics	Three age categories with a similar number of participants	Novice, experienced, and older drivers are important for the evaluation scope. Thus, representative groups are included.
Nature of data	Combination of objective and subjective data	Objective CCAM measurements on interaction are collected and, to address limitations in field user studies, focus groups are used to explore reasons behind the observed behaviour.
Data measurement	Proxy	Mental challenges with CCAM interaction cannot be measured. Thus, time needed for different activities during CCAM use is used as a proxy for ease of use.
Degree of realism of the experience	Real-world CCAM vehicle but not used in a real-life situation	A large-scale FOT is beyond available resources, but a smaller-scale real-world experience is provided to assess participants' interaction with the CCAM system.
User experience in field experiments	Single demonstration rides	Maximises the number of participants while providing direct CCAM exposure.
Experimental environment	Short fixed test route	Harmonises the experience across participants. Supports comparability in focus group interviews.
TRL	Medium TRL	Fairly realistic experience, sufficient for planned evaluation focus.
Duration	Short	Cost-effective.

Baseline and treatment conditions	Treatment only	Baseline data is not needed to assess participants' behaviour without CCAM. Participants reflect directly on the difference between their CCAM experience compared to their current mobility.
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Guideline 3.23. How to plan the experimental design of field experiments

The test site team responsible for field experiments and the evaluation team should engage in **continuous dialogue** to define the experimental conditions and assess how much these can be adjusted to provide data suitable for evaluation, balancing the evaluation needs with test site practicalities. Research questions, the CCAM system's operational design domain (ODD) and testing permission determine the feasible condition for field experiments, while the scale of the field experiment depends on factors such as the resources available at the test site.

The evaluation team should prepare for this dialogue by:

- Collecting preliminary plans from the test sites early.
- Defining must-have and nice-to-have requirements for evaluation.
- Identifying methodological challenges if the optimal design cannot be implemented.

This preparation helps balance evaluation needs with the practical constraints of field testing.

Elements of the experimental design for field experiments and related guidelines:

Element	Description	Guidelines
Geographical location/size	City or region, shuttle route, typical journeys, operational domain, number of kilometres	The test location should represent the operational domain of future CCAM use. A limited test area may affect the generalisability of results.
Road types	Road category, such as motorway, single carriageway road, one-way road, urban road, rural road	Road classifications differ between countries, no standards exist. A map and a database with harmonised descriptions should be established for the roads included in the field experiments.
Traffic conditions, interactions with other road users	Congested/free flow/ sparse traffic; vehicle categories and non-motorised road users present in the test area	Traffic conditions should represent typical CCAM operating conditions. Document any changes or unusual events to ensure correct data use.
Road/infrastructure features	Pavement condition, signage, lane markings, intersection types	Record road condition and other infrastructure features to ensure similar conditions in analysis. Define boundaries for intersection and other elements.
Weather conditions	Precipitation, cloud cover, visibility, temperature; road	If specific weather conditions are required by research questions or ODD, consider their

	surface condition (snowy, icy, wet)	likelihood when planning experiment timing and location.
Temporal conditions	Date, time, day of week	Temporal conditions should represent the envisaged CCAM operation (e.g. operation in peak hour conditions).
Baseline and treatment conditions	See Guideline 3.27	Both conditions should ideally occur under similar conditions.

If **user tests** are planned, participants should ideally use CCAM frequently or over extended periods, in an operational domain as close as possible to the intended future use. The main characteristics of real-world experiments are often determined during project preparation.

In **field experiments**, not all conditions can be controlled; some must be logged and considered during analysis (see Chapter 3.4). The experimental design should control for the most relevant conditions per research question.

The elements above also apply to **test track and confined space** experiments, but some elements may be dictated by the restricted environment. Experiments should represent the intended use case as closely as possible.

Securing **permissions for public road testing** [22] is often time-consuming but can be streamlined with early preparation. Identify and contact the municipal, regional or national authorities responsible for granting permits. Prepare a concise but thorough description of the test procedure, safety measures, and insurance coverage. Engage in early dialogue with the authorities to reduce last-minute surprises. Conduct risk assessment of potential system failures and user hazards.

Example

Elements considered during the planning of the experimental design:

Element	Specification	Rationale
Geographical location/ size	Medium-sized city with mixed urban and suburban areas. ~50 km of test routes.	Represents expected CCAM operational environment. Sufficient size for capturing varied traffic conditions and infrastructure.
Road types	Urban and rural roads, urban motorway segment with on/off-ramps.	Reflects the ODD, which includes different road types.
Traffic conditions, interactions with other road users	Data is collected during both peak and off-peak hours.	Captures relevant varying traffic conditions.
Roads/infrastructure features	Good lane markings (urban roads), missing lane markings (suburban roads), various traffic signs and	Mapped with detailed coordinates for map-matching during data processing and alignment with the ODD.

	intersections, bike paths and bike lanes	
Weather conditions	Experiments run on sunny, rainy, and foggy days.	Allows evaluation under varied weather conditions, aligned with the ODD.
Temporal conditions	Tests conducted during weekdays, at different times of day but office hours only.	Covers peak and off-peak hours, constrained by personnel work hours.

Guideline 3.24. How to plan the experimental design for virtual environments with participants

Driving simulators and virtual reality offer a safe and controlled environment for studying road user interaction with infrastructure, other road users, and CCAM systems. They can also help evaluate user acceptance and behavioural adaptation. Field experiment observations can guide virtual environment design by incorporating real-world driver, pedestrian, and cyclist interaction behaviour.

The realism of virtual environments depends on the available tools, resources, and the fidelity of the CCAM system representation. It is important to consider the level of fidelity required for meaningful results. Include as many elements of the operational design domain (ODD) as possible in the virtual environment.

While many considerations for virtual experiments are similar to those for field experiments, virtual environments also have unique elements, as shown in the table below.

Element	Description	Guidelines
Scenario authoring	Virtual environment conditions	Consider test area size, road types, traffic conditions, road infrastructure, weather conditions, lighting conditions, etc., in accordance with Guideline 3.23. Use established scenario formats (e.g. OpenDRIVE, OpenSCENARIO) or consistent naming conventions to facilitate data exchange and scenario re-runs.
Scenario control	Critical events in scenarios	Include critical events unfeasible in real-world situations, such as take-over control or safety-critical situations.
Repeatability	Consistent participant experience	Simulators offer the ability to re-run identical scenarios. Expose participants to identical scenarios and control for variability.
Replicability	Real-world fidelity	Virtual environments do not need to perfectly replicate the real world but should provide sufficient fidelity for findings to be validated through real-world testing.
Peripheral devices	Eye trackers, biometric sensors	Augment experiments with peripheral data collection devices, like eye trackers or biometric sensors; enrich the data, provided they do not create unrealistic operating conditions for the participant.

Example

Example specification for the experimental design of a virtual experiment. The experiment was designed to address a research question on the driving performance of human drivers during sudden events on motorways.

Element	Specification	Rationale
Scenario authoring	Model of a 20 km segment of a real motorway. Three lanes, two speed limits, low to high traffic volumes.	Replication of a real-world motorway environment for increased realism and relevance.
Scenario control	Sudden lane closure, following a vehicle that performs a harsh braking manoeuvre, foggy weather conditions.	Controlled safety-critical events that can be challenging for a CCAM system.
Repeatability	All participants exposed to the same scenarios under the same conditions.	Ensures consistent and comparable data across participants.
Replicability	High-fidelity environment (textures, vehicle dynamics, traffic behaviour) but not an exact replica.	Balances realism with simulator capabilities and resource constraints.
Peripheral devices	Head-tracking and steering force feedback.	Data gathering for control precision and reaction times. Resource constraints did not allow for other equipment.
Limitations	Lack of eye trackers, limited motion simulation, limited set of safety-critical events.	Focus on core aspects of the research question without compromising the validity of the results.

Guideline 3.25. How to select participants for your experiment

Determine the expected future users of the CCAM system—ordinary drivers, passengers, professional drivers (e.g. truck drivers) or specific user segments—and ensure that participant recruitment covers these user profiles. Research questions may specify particular participant groups, such as older adults, mobility-impaired, general population, people living in a certain area, or truck drivers. Recruit participants who represent these relevant characteristics. If it is not possible to recruit participants from these exact target groups, select those with characteristics as closely aligned as possible.

For specific user groups, such as people with disabilities, involve representatives during the planning phase to ensure their needs and constraints are reflected in the experimental design.

Ensure that the sample is representative of the expected future CCAM users in terms of demographics like socio-economic status, gender, and age. Also, consider whether other road users potentially affected by the CCAM system should participate in the experiment. They could be observers of the experiment or participants in qualitative studies on acceptance, expectations, and perceived impacts.

Balance the number of recruited participants with the sample size needed for the planned evaluation methods and the available resources. Include an attrition rate, as participants may withdraw from the study before it concludes.

Maintain open dialogue with test sites to assess their feasibility of recruiting the desired participants. Initiate recruitment planning early, including outreach methods, media coverage, participant remuneration, and inclusion/exclusion criteria.

Example

The CCAM shuttle service project aimed to provide first- and last-mile access to a train station, encouraging mode shifts to public transport on work, school, errand, and leisure trips. Participants were recruited to represent the general population of the region, ensuring diversity in terms of age, gender, and socio-economic status to reflect the future user base of the shuttle service.

Guideline 3.26. How to provide participants with the most realistic user experience possible

Providing a realistic user experience of the CCAM system can be achieved through various methods, including real-world experiments, driving simulators, virtual reality, real-world demonstrations, videos, storyboards, and written descriptions. The aim is to provide sufficient context for user evaluation while adhering to safety regulations. Provide users with an experience that is as immersive and contextualised as possible, even when real-world experiments are not feasible.

The most realistic user experience is achieved when the participants drive or ride in a real-world experiment, ideally with the participants seated in their intended role within the automated vehicle. However, safety regulations may require a safety driver, placing the participant in the passenger seat. In such cases, the safety driver should not assist or converse with the participant, as the aim is full immersion of an automated vehicle. This also applies to public transport vehicles intended to be driverless and operatorless. Consider the scope and detail of instructions and information provided to the participants before the experiment, to ensure they are sufficiently prepared without introducing bias.

Achieving full realism is challenging for systems with low technology readiness level or constrained public road testing. In such cases, controlled experiments can offer a realistic experience. One approach is the Wizard of Oz method, where a hidden driver operates the vehicle while the participant, seated in the driver's seat, believes the vehicle is driving itself. This can provide preliminary user feedback while the technology is under development.

More details on the pros and cons of different approaches in user evaluation can be found in Chapter 4.2.1.

Example

A project aimed to evaluate user performance during take-over control situations in automated vehicles but was not granted permission to perform this experiment on public roads with automated vehicles. The project team considered using a test track or a driving simulator but prioritised the presence of real-world traffic. Thus, they opted for the Wizard of Oz approach.

Participants were seated in the driver's seat with the safety driver concealed behind a partition, leading participants to believe they were in an automated vehicle. During the drive, participants were instructed to perform a secondary task and respond to take-over alerts presented via in-vehicle displays and auditory clues designed to mimic those in automated vehicles.

Before the experiment, participants were briefed on automated vehicle concepts, including take-over procedures and secondary tasks. They were not made aware of the safety driver.

Guideline 3.27. How to define the treatment and baseline conditions

The baseline serves as the reference point for comparison with the treatment condition during impact assessment. Defining both conditions and determining indicator values for them is essential. The treatment condition refers to the CCAM system operating in a defined environment or context, while the baseline condition refers to the situation against which the impacts of CCAM are assessed, such as a situation without the CCAM system.

Baselines can be established in several ways:

- A baseline without CCAM compared to a treatment with CCAM.
- A current operational design domain (ODD) baseline compared to an extended ODD treatment.
- Multiple baselines for comparing different levels of automation.

Treatment conditions can be set in several ways, such as varying CCAM penetration rates or with multiple CCAM service variants.

The experimental design should ensure that the planned differences between treatment and baseline conditions are the only differences present, avoiding other systematic differences which might bias the results. In field experiments, the baseline and treatment periods should ideally be of equal length and in similar conditions. This allows the baseline period to capture the same variations that occur during the treatment period. These variations could concern seasonal effects, time of day or inexperience of the test subjects.

Collecting more data for both baseline and treatment conditions strengthens result robustness. Conducting a statistical power analysis prior to data collection helps determine the required volume of data for reliably detecting a specified minimum detectable effect size. Rough estimation of the effect size can be based on prior studies, preliminary data or domain expertise.

Pre-existing data, like naturalistic driving studies from prior projects, might serve as viable baselines in some specific instances. However, ensuring that the existing data is comparable to the treatment data collected in field experiments requires careful consideration of the vehicle, traffic environment, environmental conditions, driver population, data logging details, and so on.

There are several ways to set the baseline and treatment conditions of **societal scenarios**. Multiple alternative baselines may be suitable. Choosing an appropriate baseline and treatment conditions for societal scenarios requires balancing between realism, workload, available resources, and the uncertainties involved.

A present-day societal scenario requires that both baseline and treatment conditions reflect the current situation in all respects except for CCAM presence. This involves considering the region's travel patterns and vehicle fleet using statistics, travel surveys, and other similar sources. Although assuming widespread CCAM adoption today may be unrealistic, it eliminates the need for uncertain predictions.

Societal scenarios employing a future baseline can be more complicated, as they require forecasting the development of traffic systems and travel patterns for the specified future period. Be aware of the consequences of the baseline choice. For example, predicting future baseline conditions adds workload if suitable predictions are not available from existing sources.

Each impact area and data type may require specific baseline definitions, such as:

- **Accident data:** Number of accidents in traffic without automated vehicles.
- **Traffic data:** Total vehicle kilometres travelled in the region by the current vehicle fleet
- **Energy and environment impact area:** Engine types for emission calculations as predicted for year 20xx.
- **Mobility impact assessment:** Public transport service offering in the area before the introduction of CCAM.

A baseline may not be required when only observing behaviour or technical performance, like in **user evaluation** or **technical functioning**. Expertise is required to select the relevant elements of baseline and treatment conditions for each research question and impact area.

Example

Case #1: Automated shuttle bus service in city centre

- **Treatment:** Automated shuttle bus service transporting people between public transport hubs and points of interest in the city centre.
- **Baseline:** Current mobility services in the area.

Case #2: Automated shuttle bus service in a newly built business park

- **Treatment:** Automated shuttle bus service in a newly built business park.
- **Baseline:** No direct baseline can be collected from the business park, as it is new and has had CCAM since its completion. Alternatives include performing observational studies or finding comparable data from similar business parks.

Case #3: SAE L4 motorway automated driving for passenger cars

- **Treatment:** Passenger cars with motorway ADS of SAE L4 at 10% penetration of traffic flow.
- **Baseline A:** Traffic flow of human-driven cars, no automation.
- **Baseline B:** Traffic flow of human-driven cars with adaptive cruise control (ACC).
- **Baseline C:** Traffic flow of 10% ACC-equipped and 90% non-automated cars.

Case #4: Societal scenario: Automated passenger cars

- **Treatment:** 20% automated cars in traffic, projected 10 years into the future.
- **Baseline:** Traffic prediction for same period without CCAM.

3.6. Evaluation plan compilation

This chapter provides guidelines for compiling an evaluation plan, which integrates all the steps of the planning phase: CCAM system description (Chapter 3.1), research questions (Chapter 3.2), evaluation methods (Chapter 3.3), data specification and tools (Chapter 3.4), and experimental design (Chapter 3.5).

Given the multiple iterations involved in the planning process, it is recommended to compile the formal report on the final evaluation plan only after completing the iterative process and establishing a feasible plan. This prevents unnecessary revisions when making adjustments during the planning phase.

The evaluation plan serves as a guide for the evaluation work throughout the project. It is recommended that the evaluation plan be published as a public report of the project, specifying the final list of research questions and the methods for answering them. This facilitates dissemination of the planned evaluations and allows for concise method descriptions in the evaluation results report.

Despite thorough planning, adjustments to the methodology may be necessary during its execution. It is important to document any changes and the rationale behind them in the evaluation results report, particularly if the evaluation plan has already been published. This ensures that the final methodology is accurately documented for future use and correct interpretation of the results. If the evaluation plan is included in the final results report, only the executed methodology is published.

Any deviations from the EU-CEM guidelines, along with their justifications, should be specified in the reports. Additionally, explain the reasoning behind the selection of evaluation and impact areas.

The guidelines below cover the following topics:

- How to compile the evaluation plan
- How to describe the linkages between different evaluation and impact areas
- How to ensure resilience of the evaluation plan

Note that the best chronological order of tasks may also be different from the sequence of guidelines below, depending on the project.

Guideline 3.28. How to compile the evaluation plan

Describe the decisions and outcomes of all elements of the evaluation plan (Chapters 3.1 to 3.5) in a concise and coherent report. Briefly explain the rationale behind decisions and assumptions, including references used or expert assessment made within the project.

Below is a suggested outline for the evaluation plan report:

- **Overall aim and scope of evaluation**, including impact areas covered and a description of the CCAM system under evaluation (see Guidelines 3.1, 3.2, 3.3, 3.4).
- **Experimental design(s)** applied.
- **Societal scenarios** in both baseline and treatment conditions (see Guidelines 3.10, 3.27).
- **For each evaluation and impact area:**
 - Overall approach and how the common scope is applied in this context (see Guidelines 3.5, 3.13, 3.14, 3.15).
 - Research questions and indicators used to answer them (see Guidelines 3.6, 3.7, 3.8, 3.12).
 - Evaluation methods for each research question, including tools, experimental design, input data, and the scenarios addressed (see Guidelines 3.11, 3.13, 3.14, 3.15, 3.17, 3.23, 3.24, 3.25, 3.27).

It is advisable to draw a timeline of the different evaluation phases, such as a Gantt chart for internal project use, though it does not need to be published.

Since developing the evaluation plan involves iterative refinement, the report should include only the final specifications and their justifications. When reporting the results of the evaluation after its implementation, document any changes made to the original plan and the reasons behind them (see Chapter 5.1), especially if a separate evaluation methodology report was published earlier. Final methodological details are often refined during implementation and must be included in the evaluation results report.

Example

Example outline of an evaluation plan report:

- Overall scope of evaluation and impact areas covered
- Description of the CCAM system(s), ODD, and service concept
- Common societal scenarios in baseline and treatment conditions
- For each evaluation and impact area (where relevant):
 - Overall approach and scope, including what impacts are in and out of scope.
 - Research questions and indicators used to answer them
 - Experimental design per research question
 - Evaluation method per research question, including tools, input data, and relevant traffic, driving, user, and user behaviour scenarios
 - Data formats used
- Comply or explain—describe deviations from the EU-CEM guidelines and their justifications.

Further reading

Innamaa et al. (2020). Evaluation plan. L3Pilot Deliverable D3.4.

https://l3pilot.eu/fileadmin/user_upload/Downloads/Deliverables/Update_07102021/L3Pilot-SP3-D3.4-Evaluation_plan-v1.0_for_website.pdf

Vater et al. (2023). Effects evaluation methods. Hi-Drive Deliverable D4.5. <https://www.hi-drive.eu/app/uploads/2023/09/Hi-Drive-SP4-D4.5-Effects-evaluation-methods-v1.0-.pdf>

Guideline 3.29. How to describe the linkages between different evaluation and impact areas

Each research question requires its own evaluation, but synergies often exist within or across impact areas. Multiple research questions may rely on the same input data, while some require outputs from other impact areas as input. Identifying and accounting for these interdependencies early ensures consistency of evaluation results and a coherent, timely evaluation process for all impact areas and research questions.

Begin by listing the necessary input data and expected output indicators for each evaluation and impact area, considering all relevant methods and tools. A visual sketch of these linkages is recommended to help illustrate the processes and dependencies.

For each impact area, specify whether the required inputs come from within the project—either directly produced or collected—or from outputs or interim results of other evaluation and impact areas. Identify any external sources if applicable. Clearly define the expected contributions from each partner and the tools involved.

When compiling the evaluation plan, consider the time required for each step in the methods used to produce results for each evaluation and impact area. Allocate sufficient time for each step, especially when an evaluation area depends on outputs from another area. Both areas need adequate time for tool setup, data collection and processing, analysis, validation, and feedback loops.

Avoid overly tight scheduling to accommodate potential delays or adaptations in methods or tools. Identify critical steps early and set additional internal milestones for their completion. These internal milestones are complementary to project-level milestones and serve to monitor progress.

Example

Linkages between impact areas:

- **Driving behaviour impact assessment:** Evaluates the impact of driving automation on the average headway during car following.
 - Analysis of headway differences between manual and automated driving using field experiment data.
- **Traffic flow efficiency impact assessment:** Evaluates the impact of different headways on total delays in a region.
 - Simulations estimate the impact of headway differences on traffic flow at high penetration rates, using headway results from driving behaviour assessment when setting up the simulations.
- **Socio-economic impact assessment:** Monetises total delay impacts for use in cost-benefit analysis.
 - Traffic-flow impact results are monetised and used as input in cost-benefit analysis.

Guideline 3.30. How to ensure resilience of the evaluation plan

Resilience of the evaluation plan refers to its ability to withstand minor changes during the project without requiring significant adaptations. A resilient plan minimises reliance on single experiments, development of new tools, individual team members, or tools available to only one partner. Feasibility and resilience are distinct concepts: a plan can be feasible without being resilient, or resilient without being feasible. Both should be assessed separately.

The evaluation plan should be designed to accommodate unforeseen challenges, including issues with data collection, changes in project personnel, and timeline adjustments. To strengthen resilience:

- Involve multiple team members in each topic area, even if one plays a smaller role, to ensure continuity in case the primary responsible person leaves the project.
- Establish contingency plans for all new developments, using existing tools and methods as backup, even if they yield less reliable results or require adaptations, such as reducing the number of scenarios or altering result indicators.

Additional recommended measures include:

- Assigning clear responsibilities early on, ensuring that all partners can plan necessary resources for method and tool development.
- Appointing responsible persons for each evaluation and impact area, research questions, and phase of the evaluation. Assign them the task of timely plan development and execution.
- Verifying that all partners have sufficient resources (time, budget, tools) to meet their commitments, and conducting risk analysis of method and tool development to assess different levels of success and consequences of failure.
- Piloting the methodology in advance to confirm that each step works as intended, that outputs align with subsequent needs, and that all required data sources are verified.
- Agreeing on the priority of research questions and scenarios, while ensuring that high-priority items are addressed first in case the project runs out of time and evaluation cannot be completed.
- Presenting the methodology to the consortium, especially the research questions and data needs, and finding solutions to any potential disagreements. Maintain dialogue throughout the process, but ensure that discussions take place before finalising the evaluation plan.

- Ensure that necessary ethical approvals, legal requirements, and risk assessments are in place. Although this may be the responsibility of the test site team, the evaluation team should verify this.

Example

Context: The project aims to study the impact of automated driving on car sickness using driving simulators.

Potential risks identified: Reliance on a single partner for simulator adaption; the motion sickness measurement tool might break or provide noisy data; a single data source for physiological measurements; limited time for data collection and analysis; high variability in participant susceptibility to car sickness.

Measures implemented:

- The consortium selected two partners with access to a driving simulator, with three additional partners collaborating in adapting the simulator software to the project's approach, allowing one to take over if another faced delays.
- Critical tasks were identified and backup partners assigned, and deadlines for the main tasks were set. Linkages within the project were explicitly established.
- A questionnaire was developed as backup for measuring car sickness if the primary tool failed.
- Additional physiological measurement devices were installed as proxies for car sickness.
- An early pilot test identified and addressed issues before the main data collection, ensuring adherence to the tight schedule and allowing for better control of simulator settings and participant variability.

4. Evaluation-area-specific guidelines

This chapter expands the generic guidelines for the development of the evaluation plan (see Chapter 3) with evaluation-area-specific guidelines. These 18 areas cover evaluation at the level of a vehicle, a human, a transport system, and the entire society (Figure 5). For each evaluation area, the following is provided:

- Introduction
 - Definition for the evaluation area and scoping of the chapter.
 - Background with explanation of the key concepts, how CCAM relates to these impacts and a short overview of the theory where applicable.
- Guidelines
 - Recommendations for common result indicators to be calculated by all CCAM projects. (A full list of recommended indicators is provided in Appendix with links to the corresponding chapters.)
 - Impact pathways that show the linkages with other evaluation areas.
 - Overview of different approaches and methods with their pros, cons, and requirements.
 - Pitfalls related to the methods and approaches and actionable best practices to address them.

The linkages between different evaluation areas are visualised in the impact pathways, which show aspects leading to the impacts of CCAM in each specific evaluation area.

Vehicle		4.1.1. Technical functioning	4.4.6 Sustainability
		4.1.2. Driving behaviour	
Human		4.2.1. User	
		4.2.2. People mobility	
		4.2.3. Quality of life	
Transport system		4.3.1. Services and operation	
		4.3.2. Logistics	
		4.3.3. Transport activity and fleet composition	
		4.3.4. Traffic safety	
		4.3.5. Traffic flow efficiency	
		4.3.6. Energy and environment	
		4.3.7. Accessibility	
Society		4.4.1. Land use	
		4.4.2. Liveability	
		4.4.3. Economic activity and employment	
		4.4.4. Socio-economics	
		4.4.5. Equity	

Figure 5. Evaluation areas addressed in Chapter 4.

Sustainability is placed under other impact areas as a cross-domain (Figure 5) which takes a holistic look at the impacts found for the environment, society and the economy, as most of the impact areas described in this handbook relate to it. EU-CEM makes a strong recommendation that all the projects reflect on their results from the viewpoint of sustainability, regardless of the impact areas chosen for evaluation. The guidelines for sustainability impact assessment can be found in Chapter 4.4.6.

4.1. Vehicle

4.1.1. Technical functioning

4.1.1.1. Introduction

Definition and scope

EU-CEM defines technical evaluation as follows:

Technical evaluation addresses the functioning of the software and hardware of a CCAM system.

In EU-CEM, technical evaluation is distinct from the technical validation and verification of CCAM systems and testing processes, such as data logging. Validation and verification are assumed to have been completed by the system developer or a third party prior to technical evaluation in EU-CEM. It is also assumed that the CCAM system has been built, tested, and is either deployed or deployment-ready before its use in the project.

In this chapter, CCAM system refers to either a vehicle or a system installed in or used by a vehicle. Consequently, the primary focus of the technical evaluation is the vehicle itself. However, technical evaluation may be conducted in stages—initially evaluating individual components and later expanding to evaluate the entire system as an integrated whole. Whenever this chapter references the evaluation of a CCAM system, it simultaneously pertains to the evaluation of its individual components.

Thus, the technical evaluation focuses on:

- **CCAM systems installed in vehicles:** For example, a newly developed and tested system integrated into a commercial or pre-existing vehicle.
- **CCAM vehicles themselves:** For instance, a new entire vehicle prototype.

Where relevant, the evaluation also includes the functioning of vehicle-to-infrastructure connectivity and vehicle-to-vehicle cooperation. User-related considerations are excluded from technical evaluation and are addressed in Chapter 4.2.1. Although technical functioning may have implications on driving behaviour, such aspects are addressed in Chapter 4.1.2.

Therefore, the scope of this chapter includes:

- Evaluation of a built, tested, and deployed or deployment-ready CCAM system.
- Objective and quantitative measures of technical parameters that address specific research questions.
- Guidance for evaluating technology-related aspects.

The scope of this chapter does not include:

- Pre-deployment verification and validation processes.
- Subjective or qualitative measures on perceived technical functioning.
- Driving-behaviour-related measures (see Chapter 4.1.2)
- User-related evaluation, such as user interaction with the technology or service (see Chapter 4.2.1).

Background

Technical evaluation focuses on the technology that makes the CCAM system functional, while **functional evaluation** examines the system's ability to produce the expected outcome under defined conditions and specified inputs. Additional perspectives may include performance-related evaluation, which investigates:

- How effectively the system produces the expected result.
- The system's tolerance—its ability to generate consistent results under varied conditions.
- Its sensitivity, that is, the degree to which changes in input affect the output.

Given the variability in complexity and technological readiness among CCAM systems, technical evaluation employs diverse approaches and methodologies. Ideally, it assesses objective indicators—whether numerical, categorical, or otherwise—that quantify a certain amount, value, quality or consequences of the system relative to the research question. Overall, technical evaluation is understood as a series of structured and systematic tests.

Technical evaluation shares conceptual similarities with the **verification and validation** [23] processes in systems development, yet there are subtle but notable differences:

- **Verification** is an internal process conducted by the system developer during the development phase, with the goal to evaluate the accuracy, robustness, and other technical aspects of the system. Verification often responds to the developer's question, "*Are we building the system right?*"
- **Validation** is an external process carried out during the testing phase by the system consumer, with the goal of evaluating the validity of the system against defined user needs. It responds to the user's question, "*Are you building the right system?*"
- **Technical evaluation** in EU-CEM is an external process conducted during the operational use of a built, tested, and deployed or deployment-ready CCAM system to evaluate the value, performance or other objective measurements of the system. It responds to the research question: "*How does this CCAM system perform?*"

Although the purpose of technical evaluation of EU-CEM differs from that of verification and validation, similar approaches and concepts can be applied. Without going into the specifics of software, hardware or other service-level processes, common evaluation approaches include:

- **Scenario-based evaluation:** The preparation of specific, manually created, purpose-built or pre-produced definitions of the environment, actors, expected sequence of actions, triggers, conditions, and other contextual information that constrains the evaluation to a controlled domain. These test scenarios may be derived from expert knowledge, accident databases (e.g. accidentology or dedicated scenario databases) or other documental sources.
- **Data-driven evaluation:** The utilisation of data generated during the operational execution of the system, or from an equivalent reference system, to evaluate its technical functioning.

Each approach has advantages and limitations. Data-driven evaluation tends to be more reflective of real-world conditions, since it captures live operational data; however, it may fail to capture infrequent but critical edge cases. Such edge cases can be challenging to encounter in real-world conditions due to their rarity, the expense or danger associated with replicating them, or ethical and legal constraints, implying unreasonable risks for the test site team or participants, especially pedestrians or other vulnerable road users. In these cases, scenario-based tests can efficiently target these edge cases, albeit with simplified representations of reality.

A combined approach—integrating both scenario-based and data-driven evaluations—may balance these benefits and drawbacks. Nevertheless, no single approach can entirely eliminate or fully quantify the gap between the evaluation stage and real-world functioning. Edge cases, by their very nature, are often unknown

because they have not occurred before, are difficult even for experts to imagine, or are too complex or rare to be thoroughly represented in current models.

The **testing method** used in the technical evaluation is an important consideration. In both scenario-based and data-driven approaches, various testing methods can be applied to achieve the same goal. Current verification and validation approaches often combine the following types of test methods either sequentially or in a customised manner:

- **Virtual testing:** Tests are conducted on a simulated system that employs virtual environments, virtual models of vehicles, and simulated actors. Virtual components may run independently or be integrated into a single simulation framework. In the latter, the tests follow a method or test definition procedure that establishes all the contextual information and captures the expected output variables to produce test results.
- **X-in-the-Loop:** The generalisation of specialised test methods such as Model-in-the-Loop, Software-in-the-Loop, Hardware-in-the-Loop, Driver-in-the-Loop, and Vehicle-in-the-Loop [24]. X-in-the-Loop implies that part of the evaluation is virtual while other parts are real (e.g. physical or in their final form). This requires specialised equipment or facilities that connect the virtual and non-virtual components. Representative tests for validating technical functioning require their natural co-existence. For instance, Vehicle-in-the-Loop systems connect real physical vehicles to a mechanism that mimics the road, environmental conditions or other aspects the vehicles may encounter in reality. Similarly, Hardware-in-the-Loop connects a physical device to interfaces for receiving simulated data, mimicking its actual deployment environment (e.g. an electronic control unit in a vehicle) [25].
- **Proving ground:** Controlled real-world settings where CCAM systems can be technically evaluated without facing live traffic situations. Controlled test tracks are closer to reality than virtual testing or X-in-the-Loop, but the tests are limited by the test track capabilities. Proving grounds can be prepared to emulate varied environmental and contextual conditions. These include different types of roads, dummies simulating real pedestrians, effects of water, rain and dedicated wireless communication networks.
- **Real-world testing:** The ultimate testing method for CCAM systems prior to their large-scale deployment in the real world. Real-world testing implies dedicated pilots or field operational tests (FOTs) that require careful preparation of permissions, analysis of routes, involvement of other actors, traffic conditions, and so on.

One or more of these testing methods may be necessary depending on the research question. Harmonisation of results across different methods is a challenge, as the results may vary per method, reflecting the gap between the testing method and the expected technical functioning of the system in reality. The harmonisation should address these gaps, either by trying to decrease them, trying to understand and interpret them, or at a minimum being aware of their magnitude.

Finally, technical evaluation can also be framed within the context of different technology development models:

- **V-Model:** Often associated with waterfall approaches, where user needs guide the requirements and specifications for development. This is followed by testing, including unit and system tests, and validation of user needs. In EU-CEM, the system is assumed to be already built and tested, so the V-Model may be applied to produce technical evaluations by developing and verifying the required components.
- **Agile (iterative):** A cyclical or iterative approach without beginning or end, with cycles of continuous development, testing, deployment, and monitoring phases, which can accommodate rapid adjustments and iterative improvements.

Five main factors are identified for the technical evaluation of CCAM systems: connectivity, data, security, hardware and software, and operational design domain (ODD) (see Figure 6). These factors are influenced by several external elements:

- **Environment:** Weather conditions and the characteristics of both the physical and digital infrastructure in which the CCAM system operates.
- **Vehicle:** Features and functions of the vehicle, the automation level associated with each function, equipped sensors, and overall system setup.
- **Society:** Regulations and technology acceptance levels that define rules and requirements for the CCAM system.
- **Road users:** The behaviour of other road users, traffic patterns, and unexpected events within the operational area, such as road works and personnel, emergency vehicles, and special events.

Figure 6. Main components of the technical functioning evaluation area.

4.1.1.2. Guidelines

Indicator recommendations

The indicators recommended to be evaluated by every project addressing technical functioning are listed in Table 2 below. They aim to cover general aspects of any technical evaluation process, such as latency, reliability, availability or cybersecurity. If producing some of the indicators is not possible, the reasons for this should be reported per the 'comply or explain' principle of EU-CEM. In addition to these indicators, each project should define its own indicators in line with Guideline 3.12. The table below may provide only absolute units, but to

communicate the results effectively and to allow for better compatibility between studies, it is recommended to calculate the indicators in relative units, such as percentages and values per vehicle kilometre travelled (VKT).

Table 2. Indicators recommended to be evaluated by every project addressing technical functioning.

Indicator short name	Definition	Unit
Frequency of system failures	Number of system failures per 100 km (i.e. errors). A system failure is any malfunction that prevents the automated driving system (ADS) from reliably performing a component of the dynamic driving task.	Count per km driven and description (i.e. report on the failure and possible causes)
Disengagement rate	Disengagement refers to situations where the ADS transfers control to the driver. These systems cannot adapt to all circumstances and challenging situations, usually leading to vehicle system disengagement, which could result in a traffic safety issue. The transfer can be initiated either by the vehicle or the human driver.	Count per km driven (or inverse, km per disengagement, e.g. 10 km between disengagements)
Frequency of minimal risk manoeuvres (MRM)	Number of MRMs per 100 km. MRM involves the vehicle taking action to minimise risk when it determines that the system cannot perform adequately. This includes bringing the vehicle to a safe stop or moving to a less risky position on the road. This indicator describes the frequency when the normal expected disengagement failed.	Count per km driven and description (i.e. report on the possible cause)
Current operational domain (COD) success rate	Success rate with which the CCAM system correctly identifies whether the COD is within the ODD (%). The current operational domain is expressed as a temporal sequence of ODD attributes, enabling determination of whether the CCAM system is within its ODD.	% of km driven

Disengagement is an intended behaviour of the ADS when the vehicle exits its ODD. In such cases, disengagement indicates proper system performance, and the disengagement rate reflects the fragmentation of the ADS' operational design domain.

Impact pathways

The technical functioning evaluation area is not directly influenced by factors addressed in other EU-CEM evaluation areas. Figure 7 shows the output indicators.

Figure 7. Output indicators of technical functioning.

Overview of approaches and methods

Technical evaluation approaches are similar to validation and verification approaches in a system’s testing phase. Therefore, the suggested methods for technical evaluation lean on testing methods, but with the specific purpose of addressing specific research questions. The different approaches and methods are described in the introduction to this chapter above.

Selecting the right method for evaluating technical functioning ensures relevant and reliable results. The choice is influenced by the project’s objectives and the resources available to the partners. Additionally, the available tools and data shape the feasibility and effectiveness of different approaches (see Chapter 3.3 for further details).

Table 3 provides an overview of various approaches used in technical evaluations. It highlights the strengths, weaknesses, and requirements of each method, helping to identify those that best align with the project’s objectives, resources, and specific evaluation aspects. It is important to note that even when the cons outnumber the pros, one pro can outweigh multiple cons.

Table 3. An overview of approaches and methods for evaluation of technical functioning.

Approach/method	Pros	Cons	Requirements
Virtual testing	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Cost- and time-efficient. Enables large-scale scenario coverage (including edge cases) relatively fast. High flexibility; easy to modify parameters like vehicle speed. Provides a safe and controlled environment. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Limited realism; may omit unpredictable real-world factors like unexpected human behaviour. May lead to bias in evaluation. May require substantial computing resources. Model development can be labour-intensive. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Simulation software and validated models for functions, vehicles, other road users, sensors, environments, scenarios, etc. Sufficient computing resources. Skilled personnel for modelling, setting up the

	Facilitates detailed data capture and measurement.	Potential modelling bias if insufficient real-world data for calibration.	simulations, and maintaining the computing infrastructure.
X-in-the-Loop	<p>Same pros as virtual testing, but with increased realism as one or more real components are incorporated into the loop.</p> <p>Testing can progress e.g. from Software- to Hardware- to Driver- to Vehicle-in-the-Loop.</p>	<p>Complex physical setups that require special testing equipment.</p> <p>Integration challenges in interfaces with virtual and non-virtual components.</p> <p>May not represent real-world conditions accurately.</p>	<p>Mechanism to interface the X (Software, Hardware, Driver or Vehicle) with the evaluation loop. Usually as a physical setup to immerse the X into the simulation.</p> <p>Specialised testing facilities or platforms.</p>
Proving ground	<p>Higher realism than virtual testing and X-in-the-Loop due to real vehicles and physical environment.</p> <p>Can be used to identify effects of reality not included in the virtual models.</p> <p>Safe environment compared to public roads.</p> <p>Allows for controlled tests and iterative testing.</p>	<p>Expensive and time-consuming to organise and operate.</p> <p>Coordination challenges, logistical complexities, specialised setups (dummies, simulating slippery conditions).</p> <p>May not be feasible to replicate all virtual scenarios or public road situations.</p>	<p>Test track or physical environment where the CCAM system can operate, representing the road type (i.e. motorway, urban, rural).</p> <p>Resources if the proving ground must be rented, travelling with all equipment if the test track is not close by.</p> <p>Physical simulated elements (e.g. dummies, environment).</p> <p>Trained staff to operate vehicles and set up the test track.</p> <p>Complex orchestration of test execution. Can be affected by weather if the test track is outdoors.</p> <p>Data collection instrumentation.</p>
Real-world testing (on public roads)	<p>Maximum realism with minimal bias.</p> <p>Exposure to new situations that cannot be simulated or controlled or that might be unknown.</p> <p>Necessary for large-scale deployment.</p>	<p>Expensive and time-consuming, especially when collecting data in rare but challenging scenarios.</p> <p>Elevated risk compared to controlled situations.</p> <p>Complex regulatory and ethical constraints.</p> <p>Data and results are hard to obtain.</p>	<p>Permissions to operate on public roads.</p> <p>Definition of privacy, ethical, accountability and other aspects related to conducting the experiment in the real world with the potential of affecting people and goods.</p> <p>Comprehensive instrumentation and logging to gather data for evaluation.</p> <p>Contingency plans for unexpected situations.</p>

Pitfalls and best practices related to different methods

Evaluation of technical functioning requires consideration of the methods and approaches used, as these can significantly influence the validity and reliability of the results. Overlooking potential pitfalls may lead to flawed conclusions, misinterpretation of findings or unintended biases. By proactively addressing the pitfalls these can be avoided.

Table 4 provides some common pitfalls of technical functioning evaluation and presents actionable best practices to address them.

Table 4. Pitfalls in evaluation of technical functioning and best practices to avoid them.

Topic	Pitfall	Related best practice
Virtual testing	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Using insufficiently realistic models, not validating models. Over-simplifying environments or contextual systems. Ignoring critical scenarios, potentially biasing towards overly favourable results. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Assess model realism and match with simulation engine capabilities, use real-world data to calibrate and validate models. Interoperate models via standard interfaces. Adopt critical-analysis methods to address or find edge cases within simulations.
X-in-the-Loop	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Simulated components are not sufficiently realistic. Non-standard interfaces between real and virtual components might cause delays. Insufficient calibration of sensors can lead to biased results. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Use real-world data to calibrate and validate the simulated components. Anticipate integration issues and perform pre-testing, use standard protocols for data exchange. Plan for expected measurement outcomes to notice anomalies and possible issues.
Proving ground	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Over-simplifying or narrowing environmental conditions and driving scenarios. Evaluation data differ in format, model, scope or other properties with respect to virtual testing or other methods, making harmonisation or comparison difficult. Partial or inconsistent scenario coverage. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Specify relevant ODD conditions that the proving ground will replicate. Establish consistent data collection mechanisms and protocols across testing methods. Document and log environmental conditions and test scenarios.
Real-world testing (on public roads)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Focusing on normal driving and missing edge cases or critical situations. Over-simplifying open world conditions by running evaluation on favourable environmental or system conditions. Insufficient attention to privacy, accountability or other ethical aspects, leading to unnecessary risks. Limited test duration that fails to capture a representative range of events. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Select diverse road routes and plan tests across various times, days, and conditions. Identify and define ODD conditions under which the evaluation is valid. Conduct ethical, legal, and privacy reviews prior to data collection. Extend testing duration if feasible to allow collecting rare events or edge cases or combine with targeted proving-ground or simulation-based tests.

All	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Diverse set of sensors, data sources, locations, and formats make it difficult to merge and analyse data. • Poor reutilisation of processing pipelines. • Unclear traceability of results to specific test conditions. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Enforce utilisation of standards or common procedures and formats, with certified equipment if possible. • Implement processing pipelines that are aware of possible data format heterogeneity. Include converters where needed. • Maintain comprehensive documentation of each test to ensure traceability from results to test conditions.
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4.1.2. Driving behaviour

4.1.2.1. Introduction

Definition and scope

EU-CEM defines the driving behaviour impact area as follows:

The driving behaviour impact area addresses the driving dynamics of single vehicles with and without CCAM system by examining their longitudinal and lateral movements and their interaction with the environment and other road users.

Driving behaviour evaluation focuses on the driving dynamics of the vehicle under study (the ego vehicle). These dynamics are the product of how the vehicle and driver interact with the environment and other road users. In other words, driving behaviour evaluation observes how a vehicle moves on the road within the traffic flow.

An automated driving system (ADS) may partly or completely replace the human driver. The vehicle may be driverless, or, when partially substituted, the human driver may take or be given back control of the vehicle. In this chapter, “*driver*” may refer either to a human or to the ADS; in other words, the entity responsible for deciding the vehicle’s longitudinal and lateral movements. In manual vehicles it is a human, and in automated vehicles operating in automated mode it is the ADS.

Driving behaviour can be observed in the real world in field experiments and, to some extent, with driving simulators and microscopic traffic simulations. Virtual methods allow for analysis of driving scenarios that are difficult to test in real-world conditions, such as safety-critical situations, platoons of automated vehicles, or near-capacity traffic flows. It is essential, however, to validate the extent to which the simulation accurately reflects the vehicle's real behaviour.

Often, the driving behaviour of automated vehicles is compared to that of fully human-driven vehicles. Additional comparisons can be made between the driving behaviours in different environments, including when entering and exiting the operational design domain, under varying sensor configurations, or with and without vehicle-to-everything communication. Finally, the evaluation can include both how the automated vehicle affects nearby road users and how the driving behaviour of other road users influences that of the automated vehicle.

Within the scope of this chapter are:

- Ego vehicle and how it drives through traffic: vehicle trajectories, speed and acceleration, lateral movement including lane change, position in lane, following behaviour, interaction with other road users and objects nearby.

- Frequency of and duration spent in specific driving scenarios: how often and for how long the automated vehicle engages in certain driving scenarios. For example, whether the vehicle makes fewer lane changes, more cut-ins occur, or the vehicle spends more time following a lead vehicle.

Not within the scope of this chapter are:

- Evaluation of the system's technical functioning (see Chapter 4.1.1), as the vehicle is expected to be functionally working as intended.
- Evaluation of human driving behaviour except as a baseline, or human driver states and traits (see Chapter 4.2.1).
- Interaction between the automated vehicle and entities beyond its immediate vicinity, including vehicles and other road users.
- Traffic flow efficiency (see Chapter 4.3.5).
- Accident¹⁸ investigation following an incident during real-world testing.

Background

Driving behaviour is often described as the result of interactions between the driver, the vehicle, and the environment (see Figure 8). In automated vehicles operating in automated mode, the driver is the automated driving system, and in manual vehicles, the driver is a human. Automated driving systems are anticipated to exhibit different driving behaviour compared to human drivers. Furthermore, different systems may vary in their characteristics or requirements, such as the operational design domains (ODDs). Automated vehicles may also differ from manually driven ones in terms of dimensions, mass, and equipment such as sensors and actuators. Relevant environmental aspects include infrastructure requirements and driving conditions, such as weather and traffic flow status.

¹⁸ During the writing of this handbook, it was noted that the terms 'a crash' or 'a collision' were often used interchangeably with 'an accident'. It is perfectly acceptable to use any of these terms.

Figure 8. Main components of the driving behaviour impact area.

Longitudinal and lateral movements of vehicles can be observed in the real world, or in virtual environments such as driving simulators. Determining the context around the movements is necessary for correct interpretation of the indicators and for justified comparisons. For example, comparing merging manoeuvres from a ramp onto the motorway with other mandatory lane changes on the motorway might be misguided due to different contexts in terms of urgency of the manoeuvre, even though both feature a mandatory lane change to the left.

The contextualisation requires examining trajectories, calculating indicators, and collecting data on vehicle properties, surrounding objects, and the environment (e.g. road infrastructure, weather). The data should allow for segmentation of driving scenarios. This can require knowing, for example, the road type, prevailing speed limit, traffic state (free flow vs. congestion), and weather conditions. In addition, the data can include human driver traits and states, but this is not covered by this chapter.

It is necessary to log the mode of the vehicle at every moment: manual driving, manual driving supported by ADAS, automated, or connected and automated (e.g. using vehicle-to-everything) or transitioning between these modes. These variables should also be logged in simulations, depending on the simulation complexity and availability of data and models.

Automated vehicles can influence the behaviour of other road users, for example by leaving larger gaps for other vehicles to cut in to due to minimum headway settings. The implications of these interactions for traffic flow efficiency are considered in Chapter 4.3.5, but they are not limited to changes in efficiency. For example, changes in the frequency of very short gaps can affect the number of critical situations. Note that for setting the driver models for the simulations in other impact areas, input is likely required from driving behaviour analyses.

4.1.2.2. Guidelines

Analysing and explaining field observations of driving behaviour requires understanding of the context around the observations. This includes the technological readiness level of all systems, the technical functioning of the CCAM system (see Chapter 4.1.1), considering the type of participants involved (e.g. are participants in the vehicles professional safety drivers or members of the general public?) and the openness or restrictions of the environment. Determine who is in control at each moment during a trip—the human or the ADS. That is, log whether the vehicle is in automated or manual mode at each point in time. In addition, identify the moments when control shifts between the modes. If remote operation of the ADS is involved, its status should be logged as well.

In virtual environments, it is important to know the limitations of all driver models. Determine which parameters are defined already in the automated vehicle model, and which parameters can be assessed in the virtual environment. For example, identifying the target headway of an automated vehicle during car following by simulation is redundant when the headway is a parameter in the simulation configuration. Rather, evaluate aspects arising from the changed parameter settings of the simulated vehicles, such as the frequency of cut-ins and lane changes in different traffic compositions.

Driving scenarios should be detected and segmented from the data on the ego vehicle’s longitudinal and lateral movements and its surrounding objects. Driving scenarios can be predefined or staged in controlled and virtual environments, or they can result from triggering events or interactions. Examples of events are harsh braking of a preceding vehicle, a request for take-over of control, an obstacle ahead, and a vehicle cutting in. An event can also be an interaction between the automated vehicle and an emergency vehicle or a human traffic controller overriding traffic signals or signs. These events can be predefined, generated or occur naturally during an experiment. When using real traffic data, the events and, thus, the driving scenarios need to be detected during post-processing.

Indicator recommendations

Table 5 lists the indicators recommended to be evaluated by every project addressing driving behaviour. They cover the main features of driving behaviour needed for simulations (speed and headway) and proxies for energy and environmental (acceleration sum) and traffic safety (harsh braking) impacts, as well as other changes in traffic flow dynamics, such as frequencies of different driving scenarios. In addition, each project should define indicators of their own in accordance with Guideline 3.12. Indicators should be calculated, when relevant, as both absolute and relative values (e.g. per vehicle kilometre). Impacts are differences or changes in these indicators between the baseline and treatment. Distinguish each indicator per relevant categories of situational variables, such as road type, traffic state, and weather conditions. For example, studying the average speed per speed limit can additionally focus on calculating it under different weather conditions. The ‘comply or explain’ principle of EU-CEM necessitates reporting reasons when some indicators are not evaluated.

Table 5. Indicators recommended to be evaluated by every project addressing driving behaviour.

Indicator short name	Definition	Unit
Average speed per speed limit	Average speed of the ego vehicle during free driving, categorised by speed limit. If privacy is a concern (e.g. the speed limit may reveal the vehicle’s location), the percentage difference between the vehicle’s speed and the speed limit can be calculated instead. [21]	m/s or km/h

Median headway during car following	The median value of the ego vehicle's headway (in seconds) to the preceding vehicle in car-following situations.	Seconds and %
Acceleration sum	Sum of positive longitudinal and lateral accelerations per vehicle-km, measured separately per driving scenario. Longitudinal accelerations allow studying forward motion behaviour, such as acceleration or deceleration patterns. Lateral accelerations help evaluate, for example, lane keeping during free driving and car following and handling and stability during side-to-side manoeuvres like lane changes or intersection driving.	m/s ² /vehicle-km
Frequency of harsh braking events	Number of ego vehicle decelerations exceeding a threshold of 5 m/s ² , measured per distance driven.	Number/vehicle-km or number/h
Frequency of and/or % of distance driven in driving scenarios	Both frequency and distance driven are relevant for several driving scenarios. For example, for lane change scenarios the frequency (number of occurrences per distance driven) is applicable. For prolonged driving scenarios (e.g. car following), the proportion of distance driven in that driving scenario provides more value.	Number/vehicle-km or % (of distance) per driving scenario

Data is assumed to be available on the automated driving mode status and whether tele-operation occurred. Additional indicators relevant for specific driving scenarios may include the number of take-over requests, position in lane, number of unscheduled or unnecessary stops, speed variation, and other indicators of longitudinal and lateral driving behaviour.

For more dynamic driving scenarios (e.g. a braking lead vehicle or when approaching slower traffic), recording conflict measures such as minimum Time-to-Collision (TTC) may be appropriate. Traffic conditions (e.g. free flow vs. congested traffic) affect many of the indicators and should be considered when known or obtainable.

Self-reported observational data can provide further valuable insights, while being less resource-intensive to obtain, compared to vehicle data analysis.

Impact pathways

The driving behaviour impact area is not directly influenced by factors addressed under other EU-CEM evaluation areas. However, the technical functioning of the system should be known (see Chapter 4.1.1). Figure 9 shows the output indicators of the driving behaviour impact area.

Figure 9. Output indicators of driving behaviour.

Table 6 provides examples of output from driving behaviour evaluation that serve as inputs for other impact areas. Some of these outputs overlap with the recommended indicators above, while others need to be added. Please note that the required input needs must be specified in detail, as they are unique to each project. The table below is not exhaustive.

Table 6. Outputs from driving behaviour evaluation required as input for other impact areas.

Impact area requiring input	Needed input	Impact area requiring input
User	Longitudinal and lateral driving behaviour related to comfort of driving. Frequency of take-over requests.	User
Traffic safety	Longitudinal and lateral driving behaviour, new types of situations (e.g. minimal risk manoeuvres) that did not occur before the introduction of ADS.	Traffic safety
Traffic flow efficiency	Longitudinal and lateral driving behaviour.	Traffic flow efficiency

Overview of approaches/methods

Selecting the right method for evaluating driving behaviour ensures relevant and reliable results. The choice is influenced by the project's objectives and the resources available to partners. Additionally, the available tools and data shape the feasibility and effectiveness of different approaches (see Chapter 3.3 for further details).

Table 7 provides an overview of various approaches used in driving behaviour evaluations. It highlights the strengths, weaknesses, and requirements of each method, helping to identify those that best align with the project's objectives, resources, and specific evaluation aspects. It is important to note that, even when the cons outnumber the pros, one pro can outweigh multiple cons.

Table 7. An overview of approaches and methods for evaluation of driving behaviour.

Approach/method	Pros	Cons	Requirements
<p><i>Observing driving behaviour of the ego vehicle (real world)—Objective measurements of the movements of the ego vehicle and the interaction with nearby road users— from the ego vehicle or from fixed locations.</i></p>	<p>True, real-world data representing actual system behaviour in traffic.</p>	<p>Limited variety of traffic situations in small field experiments.</p> <p>Extensive data collection required. Time-consuming and costly data processing (especially camera data).</p> <p>Lateral movement adds complexity, like lane line detection, for collecting enough context and for processing.</p>	<p>Extensive and high-quality data collection and logging capabilities.</p> <p>Access to vehicle data in an agreed format.</p>
<p><i>Segmenting the driving data into distinct driving scenarios (e.g. approaching a vehicle, cut-in, lane change, etc.) allows targeted comparisons between similar situations under different conditions.</i></p>	<p>Driving scenario segmentation allows for more precise, fair comparisons and easier indicator calculation for relevant events. It also makes combining data from different test routes easier.</p>	<p>Scenario segmentation can be complicated, especially when analysing sequential scenarios. Precise definitions and thresholds are necessary.</p>	<p>Advanced data processing pipeline.</p> <p>Collection of driving scenarios with precise definitions [16].</p>
<p><i>Observing driving behaviour of the ego vehicle (real world)—Self-reported measurements, e.g. the Driver Behaviour Questionnaire [26].</i></p>	<p>No need for monitoring equipment.</p> <p>Avoids time-consuming and costly data processing.</p> <p>Allows collection of subjective insights.</p>	<p>Entirely subjective data, depends on participant accuracy and honesty.</p> <p>Only certain traffic situations and indicators can be surveyed.</p> <p>Less accurate than quantitative measurements.</p>	<p>A well-designed questionnaire or interview protocol.</p> <p>A trained administrator or clear instructions if self-administered.</p> <p>Ideally combined with objective data for validation.</p>
<p><i>Observing situational variables (supplementary activity, part of other methods)—Measured by in-vehicle or roadside sensors or derived from external databases.</i></p> <p>For connected automated vehicles, it can be relevant to collect information on <i>incoming messages</i>.</p>	<p>Collecting situational variables allow for:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - avoiding bias in the results due to different conditions - contextualising the observed vehicle movements - defining proper comparisons (e.g. only 	<p>Costly to collect and process, especially situational variables.</p> <p>Matching data to external sources can be difficult.</p>	<p>Roadside or in-vehicle data logging capabilities.</p> <p>Accurate synchronisation of timestamps and geolocation.</p> <p>Procedures to match vehicle movement to situational factors, including</p>

	<p>compare under similar weather conditions).</p> <p>Useful for assessing whether the vehicle is driving within or outside its ODD, if that is not logged.</p>		<p>(map)matching with external databases.</p> <p>Compatibility between data formats.</p>
<p><i>Observing driving behaviour of the ego vehicle (in a driving simulator)—to investigate how the user influences the vehicle dynamics, including in potentially dangerous situations, and to analyse the transfer of control.</i></p>	<p>Allows studying the impact of the user on the vehicle’s driving behaviour in a controlled environment.</p> <p>Safe testing of rare or dangerous traffic situations that are difficult or unsafe to replicate in field experiments (e.g. if the user takes over control of the vehicle in a critical situation).</p> <p>Repeatable staged scenarios in a controlled environment allow for consistent data collection and comparison.</p>	<p>Emotional or cognitive responses of the users may differ from real-world driving, particularly in dangerous situations.</p> <p>A limited number of situations can be tested.</p> <p>Simulator fidelity can limit analysis of high-frequency, fine-grained driver behaviour (e.g. low-level control actions like steering corrections).</p> <p>Learning effects can invalidate repeated tests if not carefully designed.</p> <p>Some indicators equal simulator settings and are thus not meaningful to analyse.</p>	<p>A realistic, high-fidelity driving simulator (and scenarios) with realistic automated driving functions and user interface.</p> <p>Thorough and validated study design to ensure validity of results.</p> <p>Human factors and vehicle dynamics expertise for interpreting results and adjusting simulator parameters.</p>
<p><i>Traffic scenario simulation</i></p>	<p>Allows for analysis with higher or variable penetration rates, mixed-traffic, and different traffic conditions.</p> <p>Substantial data can be generated quickly.</p> <p>Good supplement to limited field experiments.</p>	<p>Costly to develop, calibrate, verify, and validate a model that realistically simulates automated and manual vehicle interaction.</p> <p>Indicators that match simulation settings provide no new insights. For example, setting a 1.6s target headway and analysing the data to find a median target headway of 1.6s.</p>	<p>Extensive traffic simulation knowledge.</p> <p>Realistic models for both automated driving and manual drivers (especially if take-over-control processes are simulated).</p> <p>Proper calibration with real-world data.</p>
<p><i>Simulation with Hardware- or Software-in-the-Loop – using a ‘real’ ADS as it would be</i></p>	<p>Realistic usage of the actual ADS in a simulated traffic environment.</p>	<p>Challenging to integrate real ADS into the simulation.</p>	<p>Team with extensive traffic simulation expertise and</p>

built into an automated vehicle.	Tests how the system performs in a variety of scenarios without risking safety in the real world.	May require support from the ADS developer that understands its internal workings. May require large computational power.	thorough knowledge of the ADS. Integration of the real ADS with the simulated traffic (e.g. object detection needed). Sufficient computational capacity.
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Pitfalls and best practices related to different methods

Evaluating driving behaviour requires consideration of the methods and approaches used, as these can significantly influence the validity and reliability of the results. Overlooking potential pitfalls may lead to flawed conclusions, misinterpretation of findings, or unintended biases. By proactively addressing the pitfalls, these can be avoided.

Table 8 provides some common pitfalls of driving behaviour evaluation and presents actionable best practices to address them. Many of the pitfalls could be avoided if the guidelines in Chapter 3 are carefully followed.

Table 8. Pitfalls in the evaluation of driving behaviour and best practices to avoid them.

Topic	Pitfall	Related best practice
Measuring driving behaviour	Unsuitable logging system. For example, insufficient resolution or frequency, or unreliable logging.	Reserve sufficient resources and planning for a suitable logging system. Pilot-test the logging early to confirm data quality.
	Undecipherable data from CAN-bus, automotive Ethernet, ROS messages, etc. For example, due to proprietary encoding, non-standard implementation, complex data structure, and safety measures like encryption or obfuscation.	Agree on the data format, content, and sharing protocol from test site to evaluation, in line with recommendations in Chapter 3.4. Reserve sufficient budget and expertise for data analysis.
	The logging system is not piloted, leading to late discovery of poor data quality.	Develop and follow a good piloting plan. Adapt the project timeline if necessary to allow for pilot tests.
	Unclear whether automated mode was active, or which automated driving functions were in use.	Log automation mode status explicitly, including transition of control: e.g. take-over requested, take-over completed, initiated by driver, at ODD border, within ODD, and so on. Verify correctness of the logging during piloting.
	Incompatible test routes with substantial differences in conditions and characteristics.	Collect baseline and treatment data from all test routes under similar conditions.

	<p>This makes combining data from all test routes difficult and comparison of calculated indicators misleading.</p>	<p>Segment the driving data into distinct, well-defined driving scenarios with accurate contextual metadata.</p> <p>Calculate indicators for the driving scenarios and find similar scenarios across the combined data.</p> <p>Compare the treatment and baseline indicators from similar scenarios. They should reflect the driving behaviour rather than the conditions around the vehicle.</p>
	<p>Comparing data of different lengths. For example, one car-following scenario can be very long, another very short, leading to e.g. incomparable variances.</p>	<p>Standardise scenario lengths.</p> <p>Split long scenarios into multiple ones of standardised lengths. For example, car-following scenarios of 40 s are split into two 20 s ones.</p>
Analysing video data	<p>Unclear video data annotation process, no video annotation tools, or insufficient resources for annotation.</p>	<p>Specify annotation requirements in advance. That is, what should be labelled, how, and why, per research question. Note what kind of video is required (internal, external, viewing angles, frame rates).</p> <p>Reserve sufficient resources for planning and performing the annotation work, including potential lane marking detection.</p> <p>Adhere to privacy requirements. For example, blur faces or licence plates and note restrictions for filming in sensitive areas.</p> <p>Ensure that appropriate software tools for video annotation are available and compatible with required input and output formats.</p>
Traffic scenario simulation	<p>Inaccurate vehicle models (both human- and ADS-driven)</p>	<p>Calibrate, verify, and validate models using real-world data. Use data from pilots and/or existing datasets.</p> <p>Collaborate with ADS developers to configure parameters that cannot easily be calibrated.</p>
	<p>Inaccurate or unrealistic driver, passenger or pedestrian models</p>	<p>Calibrate, verify, and validate models using real-world data. Supplement with literature for best-fit parameters.</p>
	<p>Insufficient time and resources for calibration and validation.</p>	<p>Include calibration and validation in the work plan with a dedicated budget and milestones.</p>
	<p>No data available for calibration and validation.</p>	<p>Plan reference data acquisition to be included in the agreement of data that the project will provide for evaluation.</p> <p>Formalise data sharing agreements early (see Chapter 3.4).</p>

4.2. Human

4.2.1. User

4.2.1.1. Introduction

Definition and scope

EU-CEM defines the user evaluation area as follows:

User evaluation addresses the interaction of people with the CCAM system: their opinions, expectations, and awareness of the technology, and how they use it.

Interaction with the CCAM system is understood broadly here. Users can be drivers interacting directly with the CCAM system, for example when taking over control of the vehicle when the ODD conditions are no longer met. Users can be passengers interacting with a CCAM system, for example via an app or screen, or even by just sitting in the vehicle. Users may also be receivers or senders of goods being delivered by CCAM systems. User evaluation may also address "non-users", namely people who are affected by CCAM but do not directly use it; for example, other road users (both motorised and non-motorised) and residents of an area where CCAM operates. User evaluation provides important input to many impact areas, such as people mobility and traffic safety. User evaluation results can also be used for further development of CCAM systems or for developing business cases and marketing.

The user evaluation chapter has the following scope:

- **User behaviour with a CCAM system**, for example take-over control situations (reaction time, take-over time, changes in driving behaviour like sudden deviation in speed or position in lane), use of time in the vehicle (non-driving-related activities), observation or measurements of interaction via interfaces and in-vehicle systems, and observation or measurements of the effects on behaviour of "non-users".
- **Experience**, for example the user experience (pleasant, easy, useful, etc.) and the physical and mental state during the drive or ride (comfort, convenience, stress, motion sickness, feelings of safety and security, concerns about cybersecurity, data protection and privacy, etc.), trust in the system, suitability of the system for specific target groups (disability, age groups, etc.), and feelings and experiences of "non-users" confronted with CCAM.
- **Expectations**, for example, on willingness to use the CCAM system, concerns about societal impacts and consequences for users and non-users, usefulness for individuals in their envisaged future situations, or usefulness for specific groups.

User evaluation in EU-CEM does not include:

- Technical validation of user interfaces (see Chapter 4.1.1) or usability testing.
- Financial implications or business models—See Chapter 4.3.1.
- Experiences or opinions of service providers, managers, operators, and other stakeholders—See Chapter 4.3.1.
- Equity impacts for different user groups—See Chapter 4.4.5.

Background

The three components of the user evaluation (Figure 10) have a rich and diverse theoretical background. Behaviour, experience, and expectations of users are studied in many disciplines like behavioural science, social science, economics, human factors, engineering, marketing, and so on. Each of them has their own focus,

theories, and methods. User evaluation usually requires a multi-disciplinary specialist team. Some examples of factors of interest are given below.

- Behaviour with the system (take over control, non-driving-related activities in the car, gaze direction, engagement, etc.), which is observable and measurable once the vehicle is 'ready'. Various psychological theories or models can be applied to explain and predict the behaviour, such as mental models, situation awareness, models of visual attention or multitasking.
- Subjective experience (comfort, ease of use, stress, etc.), which can be measured by subjective scales in questionnaires, interviews, and so on.
- Expectations toward the system (technology acceptance, willingness to use, etc.), which can be measured by subjective scales in questionnaires, interviews, focus groups, and so on.

Figure 10. Main components of the user evaluation area.

4.2.1.2. Guidelines

Experiments must always be safe for the participants. Participants should give informed consent to participate in the experiments. Ethical approval must be obtained when required and the data collection and processing must be compliant with applicable data protection legal frameworks, such as the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR).

A challenge in user evaluation of CCAM is that the systems may not be fully mature when tested (see Chapter 3.1). Thus, the user experience may be partial or patchy, and users may encounter technical problems when interacting with the CCAM system. User evaluation specialists must work closely with the technical team to obtain a true overview of the capabilities of the system and its issues and agree when the system is ready for user evaluation.

Additional methods may be required when a full user experience cannot be provided, such as simulations, videos or storyboards. These can complete the picture of how the system is supposed to function.

When a project has different test sites aiming to have the same evaluation activities, coordination is needed to ensure that the user experience is comparable and that data gathered is compatible (see Chapters 3.4 and 3.5).

Indicator recommendations

Indicators recommended to be evaluated by every project conducting a user evaluation are listed in Table 9. Most indicators may be ascertained using standardised questionnaires. As there are many questionnaires, and new ones are being developed regularly, it is not possible to recommend one over another to be used by all projects. Questionnaires or scales should be described and selected in the method specification (see Chapter 3.3). If it is not possible to evaluate some of the indicators below, the reason for this should be reported as part of the ‘comply or explain’ principle of EU-CEM. The indicators listed below are not exhaustive; in addition to them, each project should define indicators of their own in accordance with Guideline 3.12.

Table 9. Indicators recommended to be evaluated by every project addressing user evaluation.

Indicator short name	Definition	Unit
Behaviour with the system	Users’ interaction with the system, covering both intended and unintended use.	Report, mix of qualitative and quantitative data.
Acceptance	Willingness of users to adopt and continue using the CCAM system in the future. There is a variety of acceptance and usefulness questionnaires/scales.	Measure on a relevant scale. Measure on a standardised scale, if possible.
User experience	Users’ experience of the interaction with the system (e.g. pleasant, easy, workload, perceived safety and security, etc.). There is a variety of standard scales to measure this.	Measure on a relevant scale. Measure on a standardised scale, if possible.
Non-user experience	Views and experiences of non-users affected by the system.	Measure on a relevant scale. Measure on a standardised scale, if possible.

Impact pathways

Impact pathways illustrate how changes caused by CCAM, and assessed in other impact areas, affect the outcomes of this impact area. Mapping these cause-and-effect relationships helps scope the evaluation by grounding it in established theories or empirical findings. It clarifies how localised effects can escalate to larger scale impacts, shows whether one area influences another, and reveals how these changes ripple through vehicles, individuals, the transport system and beyond. Using these pathways can help identify where additional information is needed or where collaboration is required with other impact areas, or to acknowledge if certain aspects fall outside the assessment.

User behaviour with the CCAM system is influenced by the driving behaviour (Chapter 4.1.2) of the CCAM system. This is depicted in the impact pathway below (Figure 11). The figure offers a general overview that can be adapted or extended to specific CCAM systems studied. Each project should adapt it by specifying relevant indicators and units.

Figure 11. Input needed from the other impact areas for user evaluation and its outputs.

Table 10 shows examples of outputs of user evaluation that serve as inputs for other impact areas. Some of these outputs overlap with the recommended indicators above, while others need to be added. Please note that the required input needs must be specified in detail, as they are unique to each project. The table below is not exhaustive.

Table 10. Outputs from user evaluation required as input for other impact areas.

Impact area requiring input	Needed input
People mobility	Acceptance
Traffic safety	Use of system including take-over situations, behavioural adaptation
Accessibility	Needs and preferences
Equity	Subjective experience Subjective ideas about potential use

Overview of approaches and methods

Selecting the right method for user evaluation ensures relevant and reliable results. The choice is influenced by the project's objectives and the resources available to the partners. Additionally, the available tools and data shape the feasibility and effectiveness of different approaches (see Chapter 3.3 for further details).

Table 11 provides an overview of various approaches used in user evaluations. It highlights the strengths, weaknesses, and requirements of each method, helping to identify those that best align with the project's

objectives, resources, and specific evaluation aspects. It is important to note that, even when the cons outnumber the pros, one pro can outweigh multiple cons.

Table 11. An overview of approaches and methods for user evaluation.

Approach/method	Pros	Cons	Requirements
Use of standardised questionnaires, e.g. technology acceptance scales.	<p>Results can be compared across projects or studies.</p> <p>Lower resource needs for questionnaire design.</p> <p>An established theoretical framework.</p>	<p>May not precisely fit all project-specific research questions.</p> <p>Adding or translating questions may invalidate the questionnaire or scale.</p>	<p>Use a standardised questionnaire but recognise when it is not appropriate and use additional measures (dedicated questionnaire, interviews, etc.).</p> <p>If no standard questionnaires are available, then a questionnaire may be designed based on an established tradition or theory, e.g. Unified Theory of Acceptance and Technology Use (UTAUT) [27] or Technology Acceptance Model (TAM) [28][29], rather than starting from scratch.</p>
Driver and Occupant Monitoring with in-cabin sensors	<p>Provides highly detailed information about user status and intentions, potentially in real time.</p>	<p>Resource intensive.</p> <p>May be perceived as intrusive.</p> <p>Analysis of behavioural or physiological data can be complex.</p>	<p>Observable physiological variables of the driver and other passengers, including low-level features. For example, body posture, eye tracking, heart rate, and so on. Additionally, high-level features computed from low-level features using models or regressions, e.g. stress level, fatigue level, attentiveness, emotional state.</p>
Observation, inside and outside vehicle, e.g. video	<p>Provides contextual understanding of the interaction with the system and between other road users.</p> <p>Can provide qualitative cues like gestures that questionnaires can miss.</p>	<p>Video data requires significant resources for storage and analysis.</p> <p>Potential issues in compliance with data protection regulations, such as GDPR [20].</p> <p>Infrastructure for privacy protection can be costly and time-consuming. Especially when collecting data outside the vehicle.</p>	<p>Observational instrumentation of vehicle, infrastructure, etc.</p> <p>Suitable data post-processing tools.</p> <p>Ethical and legal approval for data collection.</p> <p>Plan for data protection.</p>
Virtual and augmented reality, driving simulators	<p>Can generate a wide variety of controlled situations, including rare ones.</p>	<p>The user experience is less realistic and may elicit different emotional or cognitional</p>	<p>A sufficiently realistic simulator environment.</p>

	Allows safe testing of dangerous events.	responses than real-life driving.	Skilled simulation engineers and human factors experts for scenario design.
Participatory approaches: surveys, focus groups, interviews	Relatively easy to organise and administer. Provides insight into the ideas, concerns, and emotions of users. Flexible.	Highly subjective data. May have limited correlation with real CCAM experience if participants have not used or encountered the system extensively.	Well-structured methodology. Moderation or interviewing skills. Expertise in analysing qualitative data and designing surveys and focus groups.

Pitfalls and best practices

User evaluation requires consideration of the methods and approaches used, as these can significantly influence the validity and reliability of the results. Overlooking potential pitfalls may lead to flawed conclusions, misinterpretation of findings, or unintended biases. By proactively addressing the pitfalls, these can be avoided.

Table 12 provides some common pitfalls of user evaluation and presents actionable best practices to address them.

Table 12. Pitfalls in user evaluation and best practices to avoid them.

Topic	Pitfall	Related best practice
User experience	System underdeveloped or absent.	Provide a rich context and description to focus the user on the CCAM experience with approaches like using storyboards. "Fake" the system with techniques like Wizard of Oz.
	Technical problems during the experiment.	Proper technical validation and extensive piloting before the real experiment to identify potential problems and their workarounds.
	Insufficient information or CCAM experience to complete questionnaires and produce valid results.	Be careful with drawing firm conclusions. Ask questions that users can relate to from their own experience, without manipulating them with the given information.
Exposure time and frequency of use	Short exposure times do not allow users to fully experience CCAM, and the novelty factor is large. On the other hand, long exposure times with immature systems may lead to rejection of the system.	Aim to have users experience CCAM for a sufficient duration. Consider in the study design that the experience of the system may change over time.
Representativeness	Users are not representative of the target group.	Detailed analysis of the potential users and affected non-users of CCAM aiming to realise representative participants. Consider that the target service may operate relatively far into

		the future. For example, current older participants may not have the same attitudes or technological experience as those who will be elderly when the service is deployed.
Expertise of evaluators	Not enough expertise in human and societal factors within the team.	Experts or specialists are needed. They should have been selected during the proposal or consortium building phase. Think of disciplines such as psychology, sociology, and economics.

4.2.2. People mobility

4.2.2.1. Introduction

Definition and scope

EU-CEM defines the people mobility impact area as follows:

The people mobility impact area addresses how the CCAM system influences individuals' potential and actual mobility choices by examining effects on availability, access, quality, suitability, and affordability of mobility options.

People mobility refers to travel behaviour but also considers the reasons behind it—how individuals make the journeys to their chosen destinations. Therefore, the impacts of CCAM on people mobility are assessed from the perspective of different individuals.

The scope of this chapter includes:

- Travel behaviour from a single individual's perspective, encompassing for example mode choice, route choice, and amount of travel over distance or time.

The scope of this chapter does not include:

- The efficiency of traffic flow (see Chapter 4.3.5), although the level of congestion may influence an individual's travel behaviour.
- Goods deliveries (Chapter 4.3.2), although availability of goods delivery may influence an individual's mobility choices.
- Transport activity, vehicle and passenger kilometres travelled in total on a specific part of the road network, as it is covered in the transport activity and fleet composition impact area (see Chapter 4.3.3).

Background

Travelling is usually seen as a derived demand, as people need to move between locations to undertake activities and fulfil their daily needs. Travel behaviour is affected by individual needs and preferences, the location of residence and activities, and the opportunities and constraints of the transport system.

Opportunities refer to the travel options available to individuals. Constraints include the different kinds of costs travelling incurs, in terms of time, money, mental and physical effort, and the perceived safety and security of a travel mode, collectively known as travel resistance. The constraints can also be described as generalised transport costs (GTC). Generally, the lower the generalised travel costs, the higher the use of a mobility option.

The travel behaviour of individuals, such as the number of trips, trip timing, length, and mode choice, is affected by both general and trip-specific factors including:

- Personal situation in terms of financial means, (dis)ability, employment, family, etc.
- Residential setting and distance to activities, transport infrastructure
- Trip purpose, such as commute, leisure or shopping
- Availability of travel modes, vehicle ownership
- Habits, motivations, and attitudes toward travel modes
- Familiarity with travel modes, availability of information about travel modes
- (Perceived) quality, comfort, ease of use, safety and personal security of available modes
- Costs of available travel modes
- Weather
- Real-time traffic information, such as congested routes

CCAM may affect several of the above factors and their relevance to an individual’s travel choices. For example, if the generalised travel costs of personal cars drop, people may travel more by car. More flexible mobility services may lead to combining trips previously done separately. Better access to different locations may also affect the activities that people engage in, and new services can change the need for certain types of trips. For example, robot deliveries can replace trips to shops or restaurants. The most important components of the people mobility impact area are summarised in Figure 12.

Figure 12. Main components of the people mobility impact area.

People mobility impacts at the level of an individual traveller aggregate to impacts on the transport system level (see Chapter 4.3) in terms of modal split and amount of travel on the network over a longer period. They can have direct impacts on other areas as well, such as quality of life (Chapter 4.2.3), traffic safety (Chapter 4.3.4), energy and environment (Chapter 4.3.6), and traffic flow efficiency (Chapter 4.3.5). In the long term, changes in generalised travel costs influence the accessibility (Chapter 4.3.7) of different activities and their locations. This is can lead to changes in land use (Chapter 4.4.1) and the liveability of areas (Chapter 4.4.2). CCAM may not only

impact its users but can also influence the travel behaviour of non-users if, for example, increased car usage reduces the willingness to walk or cycle due to safety concerns.

Whether increasing people mobility is a societal goal depends on whether increased people mobility aligns with other outcomes that the society may have prioritised, such as economic vitality, improved environmental conditions, and equity. These objectives relate to questions such as whether CCAM will generate more (motorised) traffic or increase travel costs. The impacts of CCAM must be evaluated within the broader context of other trends in transport and mobility.

4.2.2.2. Guidelines

Indicator recommendations

Indicators recommended for evaluation in every project addressing people mobility impacts are listed in Table 13 below. The indicators describe individual choices and behaviours. Impacts are measured as differences or changes between the baseline and treatment scenarios for these indicators. Impacts can be reported as absolute values (with the unit below) or relative value (%). If certain indicators cannot be evaluated, the reason must be documented following the ‘comply or explain’ principle of EU-CEM. The listed indicators are not exhaustive; in addition to these, each project should define its own indicators in accordance with Guideline 3.12.

Table 13. Indicators recommended to be evaluated by every project addressing people mobility.

Indicator short name	Definition	Unit
Mode share	Share of trips of individuals by travel mode, potentially per trip purpose.	%
Amount of travel	Number of trips or kilometres or hours an individual travels in total within a specific time, like one year.	Number, kilometres, hours, minutes
Length of trips	Average distance or duration of trips.	Kilometres, hours, minutes
Timing of trips	Hourly distribution of trips (starting time).	Number of trips performed at defined time ranges
Value of travel time	Perceived costs of travel time; including accepted additional travel time with a CCAM system, change in the monetarised value of travel time.	€/time unit

Impact pathways

Impact pathways illustrate how changes caused by CCAM, and assessed in other impact areas, affect the outcomes of this impact area. Mapping these cause-and-effect relationships helps to scope the evaluation by grounding it in established theories or empirical findings. It clarifies how localised effects can escalate to larger scale impacts, shows whether one area influences another, and reveals how these changes ripple through vehicles, individuals, the transport system and beyond. Using these pathways can help identify where additional information is needed, where collaboration with other impact areas is required, or where certain aspects fall outside the scope of the assessment.

People mobility is influenced by impacts on users (Chapter 4.2.1), services and operation (Chapter 4.3.1) and economic activity and employment (Chapter 4.4.3). This is depicted in the impact pathway below (Figure 13).

The figure offers a general overview that can be adapted or extended to specific CCAM systems studied. Each project should tailor it by specifying relevant indicators and units.

Figure 13. Input needed from the other impact areas for people mobility impact assessment and its outputs.

Table 14 provides examples of people mobility impact assessment that serve as inputs for other impact areas. Some of these outputs overlap with the recommended indicators above, while others need to be added. Please note that the required input needs must be specified in detail, as they are unique to each project. The table below is not exhaustive.

Table 14. Outputs from people mobility impact assessment required as input for other impact areas.

Impact area requiring input	Needed input
Quality of life	Amount of active and sedentary travel
Services and operation	Travel behaviour and needs
Transport activity and fleet composition	Travel patterns, vehicle ownership
Traffic safety	Travel patterns
Traffic flow efficiency (macroscopic models)	Value of travel time
Accessibility	Destinations

Overview of approaches and methods

Selecting the right method for evaluating people mobility ensures relevant and reliable results. The choice is influenced by the project’s objectives and the resources available to the partners. Additionally, the available tools and data shape the feasibility and effectiveness of different approaches (see Chapter 3.3 for further details).

Table 15 provides an overview of various approaches used in people mobility evaluations. It highlights the strengths, weaknesses and requirements of each method, helping to identify those that best align with the project’s objectives, resources, and specific evaluation aspects. It is important to note that, even when the cons outnumber the pros, one pro can outweigh multiple cons.

Table 15. An overview of approaches and methods for people mobility impact assessment.

Approach/method	Pros	Cons	Requirements
Subjective methods (questionnaires, interview, focus groups, etc.)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Captures people’s subjective ideas, feelings, etc. Relatively easy and cost-efficient. Flexible. Existing or standard questionnaires enable consistency. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Subject to response biases: subjective bias, non-response, social desirability bias, interviewer bias, etc. Quality of data depends on participant honesty and recall. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Survey platform or tools (online or paper). Trained staff for designing and moderating focus groups.
Stated preference survey and choice modelling	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Can determine willingness to pay or use CCAM systems by characteristics. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Bias in answering and lack of representativeness. Stated preference answers may not provide reliable descriptions of how mobility-related habits would change. Potentially costly to recruit a representative participant group for data collection. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Large-scale participation from a representative population for reliable results. Expertise in design of stated preference experiment. Suitable expertise and software for modelling the data. Accurate description of CCAM system needed.
Modelling—Activity-based models	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Can run individual-trip-level simulations. Captures complex behaviours. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Data- and setup-intensive. Potentially long simulation run times. Model requires calibration to ensure realism. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Model needs to be developed or available and suitable for use. Sufficient data for calibration. Expertise in network simulation.
Modelling—System dynamics	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Handles scenarios representing long time periods (months or years). 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Aggregated population approach: less detail on individuals. Needs clear boundaries for model scope. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Established system dynamics tool. Model needs to be available and suitable for use.

	Once set up, quick scenario runs are possible. Includes feedback loops.	Requires historic data for calibration. Data- and time-intensive to set up.	Historic data for calibration. Expertise in system dynamics modelling.
Travel surveys, revealed preferences data, census data and other historical external data for understanding current mobility patterns (baseline)	Established methods. Long-term historic data. Often representative at a population level.	Typically population-aggregated; hard to obtain highly detailed data. Typically a "snapshot" and may be outdated.	Agreements for data provision. Carefully planned baseline for the societal scenario. Data privacy plan.
New and emerging data forms, such as mobile phone or social media tracking, for understanding current mobility patterns (baseline)	Can develop a contemporary and dynamic baseline of real-world behaviour. Can gather data on individuals' behaviour and preferences.	Limited representativeness. May lack personal details, like characteristics or trip purpose. Possible data privacy issues. Difficult to acquire access.	Agreement on data provision. Create synthetic populations alongside other data, such as census data. Data privacy plan.
Gamification, serious games	Can produce rich data without exposure to real CCAM. Interactive scenarios.	Development can require substantial resources. Game environment may not capture real-world constraints (time, cost, risk).	Developers for game design. Experienced facilitators. Pilot testing to confirm realism and data validity.

Pitfalls and best practices

Evaluating people mobility impacts requires consideration of the methods and approaches used, as these can significantly influence the validity and reliability of the results. Overlooking potential pitfalls may lead to flawed conclusions, misinterpretation of findings or unintended biases. By proactively addressing the pitfalls, these can be avoided.

Table 16 provides some common pitfalls of people mobility impact assessment and presents actionable best practices to address them.

Table 16. Pitfalls in people mobility impact assessment and best practices to avoid them.

Topic	Pitfall	Related best practice
Future mobility options	People may struggle to imagine new options or accurately assess their future behaviour.	Aim to make the user experience as immersive as possible. Consider virtual reality and immersive experiences. Use stories and scenarios to make abstract ideas more concrete. Ask specific questions rather than 'what ifs'.

Subjective scales	Variations in how participants interpret scales, especially in large, multicultural or multilingual surveys.	Include guidelines or examples to anchor responses. Use standardised surveys. Use cross-cultural adaptation methods.
CCAM impact	Failing to distinguish between impact of the CCAM system being tested and other concurrent system impacts (that may occur without CCAM).	Define a societal scenario that clearly distinguishes what changes with the introduction of CCAM and what other transport developments may take place. If relevant, identify changes in the environment or socio-economic situation, or envisaged changes in personal life such as retirement.
Habits and cultural norms	Established habits and cultural norms may remain unchanged or shift slowly, while future generations could differ from current ones.	Recognise limitations and applicability of generalisations from specific population/socio-demographics of study participants.
Recruiting representative user groups	Difficulty in recruiting a representative user group relevant to the target population. Recruitment may skew towards people with interest in the technology and time available.	Adjust target population to characteristics of recruited respondents. Develop synthetic populations.

4.2.3. Quality of life

4.2.3.1. Introduction

Definition and scope

EU-CEM defines the quality-of-life impact area as follows:

The quality-of-life impact area addresses the holistic effects of the CCAM system on individuals' physical, mental, social, and financial well-being.

The quality-of-life impact area addresses the holistic effects of CCAM on individuals' physical, mental, social, and financial well-being. In the assessment, both objective and subjective perspectives are considered and interpreted relative to an individual's values and goals [30].

This chapter considers quality of life and describes how the concept can be assessed in the CCAM context. The well-being of communities is addressed in Chapter 4.4.2 (Liveability).

Background

Quality of life describes “*individuals' perception of their position in life in the context of culture and value systems in which they live and in relation to their goals, expectations, standards, and concerns*” [31]. Quality of life is a multidimensional construct, and its measurement is complex. It encompasses both subjectively experienced satisfaction and objectively measurable achievements [32]. A simple sum of positive and negative factors does not adequately capture quality of life, as individuals may experience identical conditions differently depending on their perception of what they could achieve in life [33].

The concept of quality of life emerged to address the shortcomings of more simple measures. For example, in the medical literature, quality of life emphasises the fact that just extending the length of life might not be a meaningful goal if the remaining life is of poor quality [34]. Within the transport domain, it could be similarly argued that minimising fatalities and injuries sustained in traffic is not enough for ensuring a good level of quality of life. For example, replacing a zebra crossing at a busy road with a bridge may prevent accidents between cars and vulnerable roads users, but at the same it may reduce convenience and accessibility, if using the bridge means additional climbing or taking a detour. This means that such a traffic safety measure may strengthen the *community severance* effect of the road. Community severance means that a transport infrastructure creates a physical or psychological barrier between two areas, which impairs the well-being of people moving between them [35][36].

Quality of life can be studied in terms of individuals' physical, mental, social, and financial well-being. Physical well-being refers to fitness, or the ability to perform everyday tasks in daily life, and years lived without illness or disabilities. Mental well-being refers to positively experienced mental states and the perception of being able to reach goals, whilst having positive expectations towards life and experiencing a good standard of life. Social well-being means having meaningful and supportive relationships and feeling a sense of belonging to groups. Finally, financial well-being means having sufficient financial assets or purchasing power to meet personal needs, and being able to earn more assets, for example by working. The main components of the quality-of-life impact area are summarised in Figure 14.

Figure 14. Main components of the quality-of-life impact area.

The four dimensions of well-being (physical, mental, social, financial) are influenced by accessibility or access to needed locations, the built environment, and traffic [30]. Therefore, CCAM systems may affect all these well-being dimensions. For example, automated cars could improve access of individuals to specific locations and thus improve their economic, social, and mental well-being. On the other hand, increased car usage might lead to more sedentary travel and a reduction in active travel [37]. As active travel is an important source of physical activity [38], CCAM systems could thus decrease the physical well-being and possibly also mental well-being of

its users. Automated driving could also change what activities can be performed while travelling [39] (see Chapter 4.2.1). This can make multitasking while travelling easier than before. The ability to engage in activities during travel may increase flexibility but may also induce stress by creating an expectation to use travel time productively. This may reduce the ‘positive utilities’ of travel time, such as relaxation or time off [40]. This can have complex influences on mental, social, and financial well-being.

CCAM systems could also change the amount of time people spend travelling (see Chapter 4.2.2). Some people might perceive the travel time as enjoyable or relaxing on its own [41]. Therefore, minimising travel time may not be an important objective for everyone [42]. However, excessive travel time has a negative effect on the subjective experience of commuting and overall well-being [41].

Satisfaction with life is a related (but narrower) concept than quality of life. It focuses on subjective experiences of well-being [43], which are positively correlated with objectively measurable factors recognised as relevant to well-being. For example, severe injuries from crashes often reduce both subjectively experienced and objectively measured well-being. Thus, the subjective experience of well-being can reflect tangible, objectively measurable factors. Consequently, satisfaction with life or travel could be used as a proxy for quality of life.

Subjective experiences while travelling, access to activities, and activities performed while travelling can influence subjective well-being [44]. Satisfaction with travel can be relevant for the acceptance of CCAM systems. Low satisfaction with the current mode of travel is linked to a greater willingness to use automated vehicles [45].

4.2.3.2. Guidelines

Indicator recommendations

EU-CEM does not currently provide recommendations for quality-of-life indicators that should be used by all projects. It is recommended that the projects measure quality of life with scores calculated based on published, previously validated questionnaires and scales and that they are explicit in how the scores have been calculated. Standardised scores are useful when comparing quality of life between groups of people, for example when assessing the equity impacts (Chapter 4.4.5). Projects could also conduct qualitative assessment of the quality-of-life dimensions, such as expected changes in physical, mental, social and financial well-being.

Impact pathways

Impact pathways illustrate how changes caused by CCAM, and assessed in other impact areas, affect the outcomes of this impact area. Mapping these cause-and-effect relationships helps scope the evaluation by grounding it in established theories or empirical findings. It clarifies how localised effects can escalate to larger scale impacts, shows whether one area influences another, and reveals how these changes ripple through vehicles, individuals, the transport system and beyond. Using these pathways can help identify where additional information is needed or where collaboration is required with other impact areas, or to ascertain whether certain aspects fall outside the scope of the assessment.

Quality of life is influenced by impacts on people mobility (Chapter 4.2.3), accessibility (Chapter 4.3.7), liveability (Chapter 4.4.2), and traffic safety (Chapter 4.3.4). This is depicted in the impact pathways below in Figure 15. The figure offers a general overview that can be adapted or extended to specific CCAM systems studied. Each project should tailor it by specifying relevant indicators and units.

Figure 15. Inputs needed from the other impact areas for the quality-of-life impact assessment.

Table 17 provides examples of quality-of-life impact assessment that serve as inputs for other impact areas require. Some of these outputs overlap with the recommended indicators above, while others need to be added. Please note that the required input needs must be specified in detail, as they are unique to each project. The table below is not exhaustive.

Table 17. Outputs from quality-of-life impact assessment required as input for other impact areas.

Impact area requiring input	Needed input
Liveability	Well-being of individuals
Equity	Distribution of quality-of-life impacts across different groups of people

Overview of approaches and methods

Selecting the right method for evaluating quality of life ensures relevant and reliable results. The choice is influenced by the project’s objectives and the resources available to the partners. Additionally, the available tools and data shape the feasibility and effectiveness of different approaches (see Chapter 3.3 for further details).

Table 18 provides an overview of various approaches used in quality-of-life evaluations. It highlights the strengths, weaknesses, and requirements of each method, helping to identify those that best align with the project’s objectives, resources, and specific evaluation aspects. It is important to note that, even when the cons outnumber the pros, one pro can outweigh multiple cons.

Table 18. An overview of approaches and methods for evaluation of quality of life.

Approach/method	Pros	Cons	Requirements
Focus groups and interviews	Allows for consideration of the multidimensionality and complexity of quality of life.	Participants may not have experience with the CCAM system. Only subjective results.	Participants should be provided a good experience or description of the CCAM system. Careful selection of participants.
Surveys	Previously validated survey instruments are available in the literature [46][47][48][49]. Validated questionnaire available.	Participants may not have experience with the CCAM system. Only subjective results.	Participants should be provided a good experience or description of the CCAM system.
Expert assessment of the impact pathways to quality of life	Efficient to implement. Can cover a wide range of impacts.	Limited to the impact pathways recognised by experts. Only subjective results.	Assessment of the relevant areas with impact pathways to quality of life. Multidisciplinary team of experts.

Pitfalls and best practices

Evaluating quality of life impacts requires consideration of the methods and approaches used, as these can significantly influence the validity and reliability of the results. Overlooking potential pitfalls may lead to flawed conclusions, misinterpretation of findings, or unintended biases. By proactively addressing the pitfalls, these can be avoided.

Table 19 provides one common pitfall of quality-of-life evaluation and presents actionable best practices to address them.

Table 19. Pitfalls in evaluation of quality of life and best practices to avoid them.

Topic	Pitfall	Related best practice
Limited viewpoint	Evaluation concerns only a few related impact areas, like traffic safety and people mobility, not enabling holistic assessment of the quality of life.	Quality of life is a broad concept that should not be evaluated from narrow perspectives. If a comprehensive evaluation is not feasible, it is more appropriate to discuss the potential impact on quality of life through the impact pathways rather than claiming to evaluate it.

4.3. Transport system

4.3.1. Services and operation

4.3.1.1. Introduction

Definition and scope

EU-CEM defines the services and operation impact area as follows:

The services and operation impact area addresses the impacts of CCAM on the business models and operation of vehicle fleets and transport services, as well as on the operation of traffic management of the network.

The area addresses the impacts of CCAM on individual companies or organisations that provide travel and transport services or manage vehicle fleets, as well as network-wide changes in traffic operations through traffic management measures.

The services and operation impact assessment evaluates how CCAM affects:

- The offering of travel and transport services for people and goods
- The operation and management of these services
- The value propositions of these services for all stakeholders
- Traffic management operations at the road network level.

This chapter discusses the impacts of CCAM on logistics service offerings and their operations, while the impacts on logistics itself are covered in Chapter 4.4.3.

The changing role of professional drivers and the potential for new professional roles, such as remote operators or monitors or on-board support personnel, are addressed in the ‘economic activity and employment’ impact area (see Chapter 4.4.3).

Impacts beyond the scope of this chapter are those on travel patterns resulting from changes in the availability and operation of mobility and transport services (see Chapter 4.3.1), on logistics (see Chapter 4.3.2), on fleet composition (see Chapter 4.3.3), and on traffic flow efficiency (see Chapter 4.3.5). Additionally, this chapter does not provide guidelines for describing CCAM services (see Chapter 3.1) or assessing how changes in service operation or traffic management affect other impact areas. For this reason, they must be addressed under the corresponding impact area, for example:

- Traffic safety impact assessment (Chapter 4.3.4) for a robotaxi service must consider ADS actions and advice from the fleet operation centre.
- Traffic flow efficiency impact assessment (Chapter 4.3.5) must consider differences in outcomes between CCAM-enabled traffic management and baseline situations.

Background

The viewpoints of several stakeholder groups are considered in this impact area: individual travellers, shippers and receivers of goods, freight and other fleet operators, public transport operators and other service providers, and traffic management operators.

The **service offering for people and goods** describes the available travel and transport services in a certain region or area. CCAM may allow for new service concepts that were not possible or feasible before, and existing services may be replaced or complemented with CCAM vehicles. For example, automated shuttles can complement the public transport offering, and CCAM vehicles can provide new ways to deliver goods. The entry of new

companies exclusively offering CCAM services into the market can reshape the business landscape. Assessing how these services meet market demands may offer valuable insights.

From an individual user's perspective, CCAM services can affect the travel and transport service offering, the costs of travel, and the travel experience. For example, automated shuttles can expand public transport coverage to previously unserved areas, enhancing the service offering from the user perspective. On the other hand, new types of considerations may be necessary for service providers. CCAM vehicles may have different constraints compared to conventional travel and transport services, requiring new operational practices and considerations, such as addressing the need for assistance with entering and exiting the vehicles, or ensuring perceived safety and security of passengers on board shared mobility services operated without personnel. CCAM may also influence the experience of multimodal travel chains, even when only part of them is operated with automated vehicles. These factors shape user perceptions of service quality and require careful consideration by service operators.

The impact of CCAM systems **on efficient operation of services** can be examined from the perspectives of individual services and fleet operators, as well as traffic management and network operators.

Regarding travel and transport services and fleet operators, the operational costs, vehicle utilisation and service reliability are of interest. Operating and managing fleets with CCAM vehicles may have different requirements than conventional fleets. On the other hand, it may also enable new more efficient practices related, for example, to route planning and navigation, vehicle and cargo tracking (location request, track and trace), vehicle deployment and summoning, pick-up and drop-off management, and remote monitoring and operation. More efficient operational and maintenance services for handling breakdowns, system failures, repairs, and rescues could be enabled. New practices may allow better utilisation of the fleet and optimising energy use.

From the road network operation perspective, CCAM may enable or necessitate the development and adoption of new **traffic management** practices, which could improve the efficiency of network management. At the network level, traffic management involves measures to maintain road capacity and improve the security, safety, and reliability of the entire road network [50]. These measures are traditionally implemented via physical infrastructure, such as road layout and traffic signs, but digital infrastructure is gaining in relevance as digitalisation and communications technology advance. CCAM vehicles could communicate up-to-date information on the traffic situation to the traffic management operators, or traffic management centres could provide advice on speeds and routes to CCAM vehicles or even coordinate their movements. Adjustments in operations may be needed, for example, if certain lanes are dedicated to CCAM vehicles, or if low-speed shuttles are introduced into mixed traffic. The future role of traffic management could also include participation in operating the distributed ODD attribute Value Awareness dataset [51].

The **viability and value proposition of CCAM services** for all stakeholders describes whether CCAM services can operate reliably at scale, are economically viable, and attract customers willing to use and pay for them. Here, viability refers to evaluating business-level benefits and their mid- and long-term financial viability. Businesses aim to generate sustainable value for stakeholders while remaining competitive in the evolving mobility market.

CCAM services are often first introduced on a small scale, such as in a limited city area or with only a few vehicles. A long-term goal to expand coverage requires scalable services and business models. Note that studying the viability of the scaled service, rather than the piloted one, may be more feasible. Additionally, the service concept and business model should be transferable and adaptable to different contexts or cities.

The viability of business models needs to consider, beyond financial viability, design principles, established business rules, and underlying assumptions. For example:

- *Viability in terms of value:* A business model is viable when it delivers sufficient value to all stakeholders, motivating their participation, and ultimately leveraging market adoption [52].

- *Technological viability*: A long-term viable business model with CCAM services requires a CCAM system of high technology readiness level (TRL 9) with long-term support.
- *Validity, coherence, and completeness*: The viability of a business model relies on valid, coherent, and complete business rules¹⁹ and agreements. Validity means they are realistic and capable of producing the desired outcomes. Coherence means they align with the objectives and expectations of all stakeholders, fostering a unified and purpose-driven approach. Completeness ensures the rules and agreements significantly affecting the business model’s viability are identified and analysed.

Figure 16 shows the main components of the services and operation impact area.

Figure 16. Main components of the services and operation impact area.

4.3.1.2. Guidelines

Indicator recommendations

Indicators recommended to be evaluated by every project addressing impacts on services and operation are listed in Table 20 below. Impacts are differences or changes between the baseline and treatment scenarios in these indicators. An impact can be reported as an absolute value (with unit below) or relative value (%). If it is not possible to evaluate some of the indicators below, the reason for this should be reported as part of the ‘comply or explain’ principle of the EU-CEM. The indicators listed below are not exhaustive; in addition to these and those listed in Chapter 4.4.3, each project should define indicators of their own in line with Guideline 3.12.

¹⁹ Business rules define conditions that govern a business model.

Table 20. Indicators recommended to be evaluated by every project addressing services and operation.

Indicator short name	Definition	Unit
Vehicle utilisation	Amount of tonne- or passenger-kilometres transported per vehicle, reflecting the efficiency of vehicle usage.	Tonne-km/veh/time unit or passenger-km/veh/time unit
Operational costs	Costs of operating a service	€/time unit
Quality of service	Perceived service quality from the users' perspective.	Measure on a relevant standard scale
Scalability and replicability	Potential to expand and replicate the CCAM service (model) to a wider area or other locations, evaluated from the service provider's perspective.	Description, with qualitative and quantitative metrics when applicable.
Viability of the business model	Business model's viability in terms of value creation, technological viability, and the validity, coherence, and completeness of business rules and agreements.	Description, with qualitative and quantitative metrics when applicable.

Impact pathways

Impact pathways illustrate how changes caused by CCAM, and assessed in other impact areas, affect the outcomes of this impact area. Mapping these cause-and-effect relationships helps scope the evaluation by grounding it in established theories or empirical findings. It clarifies how localised effects can escalate to larger scale impacts, shows whether one area influences another, and reveals how these changes ripple through vehicles, individuals, the transport system and beyond. Using these pathways can help identify where additional information is needed or where collaboration is required with other impact areas, or to ascertain whether certain aspects fall outside the scope of the assessment.

Services and operation are influenced by impacts on people mobility (Chapter 4.2.2), land use (Chapter 4.4.1), logistics (Chapter 4.3.2), and traffic flow efficiency (Chapter 4.3.5). This is depicted in the impact pathway below (Figure 17). The figure offers a general overview that can be adapted or extended to specific CCAM systems studied. Each project should tailor it by specifying relevant indicators and units.

Figure 17. Input needed from the other impact areas for evaluation of services and operation and its outputs.

Table 21 provides examples of services and operation impact assessment that serve as inputs for other impact areas. Some of these outputs overlap with the recommended indicators above, while others must be added. Please note that the required input needs must be specified in detail, as they are unique to each project. The table below is not exhaustive.

Table 21. Outputs from services and operation impact assessment required as input for other impact areas.

Impact area requiring input	Required input
People mobility	Mobility service offering
Accessibility	Availability and cost of travel and transport modes
Logistics	Vehicle utilisation, operational practices
Transport activity and fleet composition	Services and fleet, routing
Traffic flow efficiency	Traffic management measures, fleet management measures
Land use Liveability	Travel and transport services

Overview of approaches and methods

Selecting the right method for evaluating services and operation ensures relevant and reliable results. The choice is influenced by the project's objectives and the resources available to the partners. Additionally, the available tools and data shape the feasibility and effectiveness of different approaches (see Chapter 3.3 for further details).

Table 22 provides an overview of various approaches used in services and operation evaluations. It highlights the strengths, weaknesses, and requirements of each method, helping to identify those that best align with the project's objectives, resources, and specific evaluation aspects. It is important to note that, even when the cons outnumber the pros, one pro can outweigh multiple cons.

Table 22. An overview of approaches and methods for evaluation of services and operation.

Approach/method	Pros	Cons	Requirements
Methods of traffic flow impact assessment (see Chapter 4.3.5)	<p>Systematic study of the effects of different CCAM penetration rates and traffic scenarios, considering various traffic management or service design alternatives.</p> <p>Allows for sensitivity analysis.</p>	<p>Validity depends on the model's accuracy, including assumptions about traffic management, CCAM vehicle behaviour and interaction, and service usage.</p>	<p>Valid automated driving model or available data for its validation.</p> <p>Ability to model and simulate traffic management and services in sufficient detail.</p>
Real-time monitoring of (piloted) service operation	<p>Provides reliable real-world evidence, especially if the pilot deployment is realistic.</p>	<p>Time-consuming and resource intensive.</p> <p>May be limited to a specific location or operational context.</p>	<p>Real-world deployment of the CCAM service.</p> <p>Mechanisms for monitoring operational data.</p>
Interviews with service providers and operators	<p>Captures first-hand experiences and perceptions from various stakeholders.</p> <p>Provides views on CCAM impacts on the mobility market and related services.</p> <p>Can identify operational challenges and barriers to scalability or replicability.</p>	<p>Subjective results that may be biased towards the interviewees' perception.</p>	<p>Cover sufficient number of stakeholders that represent a diverse set of actors, roles, and perspectives.</p> <p>Preparation of structured interview protocols.</p>
Survey of end-users (CCAM users, customers of logistics using CCAM, etc.)	<p>Relatively easy to implement if contact with end-users can be established.</p>	<p>Subjective views influenced by multiple factors, some of which may not be fully captured by the survey.</p> <p>Low response rates can introduce bias,</p>	<p>Expertise in survey design and evaluation.</p> <p>Contact with end-users.</p> <p>Sufficient number of responses. All relevant</p>

		especially if some user groups are underrepresented.	user groups properly represented. Use of incentives or targeted outreach.
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Pitfalls and best practices

Evaluating impacts on services and operation requires consideration of the methods and approaches used, as these can significantly influence the validity and reliability of the results. Overlooking potential pitfalls may lead to flawed conclusions, misinterpretation of findings, or unintended biases. By proactively addressing the pitfalls, these can be avoided.

Table 23 provides some common pitfalls of services and operation evaluation and presents actionable best practices to address them.

Table 23. Pitfalls in evaluation of services and operation and best practices to avoid them.

Topic	Pitfall	Related best practice
Traffic management in mixed traffic	Changes in traffic management due to CCAM can affect other road users as well. A solution that is best for CCAM might be suboptimal for the overall network. Decisions on traffic management may vary between operators.	Evaluate both direct and indirect impacts on all road users across relevant impact areas, such as traffic flow efficiency and safety. Conduct sensitivity analyses to evaluate how different traffic management strategies influence outcomes. Carefully define the societal scenario and the scope of evaluation.
Confidentiality of business models	Stakeholders may be unwilling to share details of their business models for evaluation.	Carefully frame research questions to avoid confidentiality issues while still addressing the evaluation goals. Establish special partnerships between service providers and evaluators to maintain confidentiality while sharing valuable insights.
Insufficient stakeholder engagement	Evaluation results may lack depth or relevance if key stakeholders are not adequately involved.	Identify all relevant stakeholders early. Facilitate early and active involvement of all relevant stakeholders.

4.3.2. Logistics

4.3.2.1. Introduction

Definition and scope

EU-CEM defines the logistics impact area as follows:

The logistics impact area addresses how CCAM affects the efficiency, effectiveness, and adaptability of the logistics process. It examines how CCAM can change the freight transport, and material flows in supply chain processes.

The logistics impact area examines how CCAM can affect goods transport in different environments, including on public roads with mixed traffic and in confined areas such as ports and terminals. CCAM has the potential to improve the reliability of operations and increase their efficiency, for example by optimising energy use and allowing operations during off-peak hours. In addition, worker safety could be enhanced.

In this chapter, logistics covers at least the following use contexts:

- Operating environments
 - **Motorway driving in mixed traffic**, for example auto-follower, platooning, entering and exiting motorways, lane changing, managing lane closures, and navigating roadworks.
 - **Driving in confined areas**, for example ports, terminals, industrial areas, construction sites, and mining or quarry sites, which typically have limited and controlled access. Mixed traffic and the presence of vulnerable road users may be included.
- Functions
 - **Gate Access**, for example procedures for planning, approaching, parking, cargo unit identification, waiting, and managing entry and exit to confined areas.
 - **Inspections by customs and other authorities**, for example international border crossings, customs inspections, and other road controls (e.g. weight checks, goods inspections, smuggling control) and handling at international ports and terminals.
 - **Parking and movements of truck-and-trailer combinations** at slow speeds in narrow or confined environments.
 - **Charging**, for example automated charging processes for truck and trailers at both public and private locations.
 - **Automated loading and unloading** of containers and cargo, including connecting and disconnecting trailers.
 - **Remote operation**, for example remote monitoring, take-over, and control by fleet managers, transport managers or authorities.
- Logistics service concepts
 - **First-and-last-mile logistics** in urban, regional or rural transport using all types of road vehicles, including public service vehicles, such as waste collection and recycling.
 - **Hub-to-hub logistics**, covering both short- and long-distance operations on dedicated, restricted or public roads, often requiring permits.
 - **Intermodal and transshipment**, for example transfer of goods between different transport modes, particularly in ports and terminals.
 - **Logistics using new innovative concepts** with CCAM, for example low-speed transport using small vehicles and load units, 24/7 operations, and implications for warehouses, logistics hubs, and so on.

Across different use contexts, the impacts of CCAM on continuity in logistics operations should be considered. New situations potentially affecting continuity, such as changes in the ODD requirements of CCAM systems or system disruptions, may arise.

Several other impact areas address viewpoints complementary to this chapter. For example, impacts of CCAM on logistics services and their operation are addressed in Chapter 4.3.1 on services and operation, and the economic aspects in Chapter 4.4.3 on economic activity and employment. The environmental efficiency of transportation is addressed under environment and energy in Chapter 4.3.5.

Background

Logistics concerns “*the efficient transfer of goods from the source of supply through the place of manufacture to the point of consumption in a cost-effective way while providing an acceptable service to the customer*” [53]. Thus, it deals with the movement and management of materials, products, and resources in supply chains, from production to delivery to end customers. Effective logistics requires balancing supply and demand, managing inventories, and ensuring consumer satisfaction, whether the customer is another company or an end-consumer. The goal is to deliver the correct products on time, add value for customers, and minimise costs for all parties involved. Cost-effectiveness and customer service need to be balanced effectively.

Logistics is related to road transport, as a substantial part of goods is transported as road freight. Relevant considerations include vehicle and delivery operation choices, load planning, and route selection. Logistics vehicles such as trucks can require significant long-term investments. Logistics companies strive for efficient use of assets by utilising vehicles that are fit for purpose and optimising utilisation rates while minimising both fixed and variable costs.

Logistics encompasses different ways of moving goods, depending on the transported volume and type of goods, costs of transport, and transit speed. It includes (a chain of) physical flows between ports, terminals, hubs, warehouses, and distribution centres. Physical flows are supported by the flow of information, which is especially important in the context of automation and digitalisation.

CCAM impacts on logistics can be studied for entire logistics chains, or for their separate parts, for example logistics operations on public roads, in warehouses, terminals, ports, customs or interchanges (Figure 18).

Figure 18. Main components of the logistics impact assessment.

A transport chain typically includes multiple phases, each encompassing specific tasks [54]:

- **Composition:** Assembling loads on pallets, containers or tankers, depending on the type of cargo.
- **Modality and inter-modality:** Moving cargo along the transport chain using one or more transport modes. Intermodal transport includes terminals where trailers or containers are transhipped onto another transport mode, such as rail, ship or air. Rail terminals, seaports and airports serve as key facilities for these transfers.
- **Road transport:** Conducting line haul operations between depots or performing multi-stop trips originating and concluding at a depot.
- **Border crossing:** Managing the movement of cargo into another country, including customs inspections.
- **Last mile:** Refers to the final stage of the transport chain involving the distribution of goods to their final destinations, such as stores, consumers’ homes or pick-up locations. This segment has grown rapidly due to the rise in online sales. With the shift toward a circular economy, first-mile logistics activities, such as pick-ups at the beginning of the transport chain, have also gained increasing importance.

All phases of the transport chain include uncertainties related to transported volumes, delays, quality, demand, and access to information. One substantial challenge in logistics management is the complexity of the supply network, which involves multiple actors in different roles and various types of activities. Additionally, road transportation is continuously exposed to traffic and weather conditions that affect delivery times and routing, causing delays.

Workforce shortages, especially among drivers, and a disparity between required and available skills are affecting road transport capacity and efficiency. A consequence may be delays in deliveries, inefficient vehicle use, and high fluctuations in transport costs. Additionally, vehicles often remain idle due to mandatory driver rest periods. CCAM has the potential to address workforce shortages and mitigate inefficiencies associated with rest times.

Last-mile deliveries and first-mile pick-ups have distinct challenges, such as low delivery volumes, tight time schedules, and high costs per delivery. CCAM could offer new and more cost-efficient options for addressing the challenges of last- and first-mile deliveries.

4.3.2.2. Guidelines

Indicator recommendations

The result indicators recommended to be evaluated by every project addressing logistics are listed in

Table 24 below. Impacts are measured as differences/changes between the baseline and treatment scenarios for these indicators. Impacts can be reported as absolute values (with unit below) or relative values (%). If it is not possible to evaluate some of the indicators below, the reason for this should be reported as part of the ‘comply or explain’ principle of the EU-CEM. The indicators listed below are not exhaustive; in addition to these, each project should define indicators of their own in line with Guideline 3.12.

Table 24. Indicators recommended to be evaluated by every project addressing logistics.

Indicator short name	Definition	Unit
Transport efficiency	Tonne-km transported per vehicle-kilometre driven	Tonne-km/vehicle-km
Duration	Sum of transshipment time, waiting time, and driving time	Hours
Punctuality	Deviation from the targeted delivery time	% and time
Transshipment time	Change in transshipment time at terminals, ports, customs, interchanges, etc.	% and time
Waiting time	Change in waiting time at terminals, in road transport, etc.	% and time

Impact pathways

Impact pathways illustrate how changes caused by CCAM, and assessed in other impact areas, affect the outcomes of this impact area. Mapping these cause-and-effect relationships helps scope the evaluation by grounding it in established theories or empirical findings. It clarifies how localised effects can escalate to larger scale impacts, shows whether one area influences another, and reveals how these changes ripple through vehicles, individuals, the transport system and beyond. Using these pathways can help identify where additional information is needed or where collaboration is required with other impact areas, or to ascertain whether certain aspects fall outside the scope of the assessment.

Logistics is influenced by changes in operations, such as driving speed and accommodation of speed to the next logistics process, and use of infrastructure during off-peak hours. These are addressed under services and operation (Chapter 4.3.1). In addition, road transport is affected by traffic flow efficiency (Chapter 4.3.5). The demand for goods transport is affected by economic activity and employment (Chapter 4.4.3). These linkages are depicted in the impact pathway in Figure 19. The figure offers a general overview that can be adapted or extended to the specific CCAM systems studied. Each project should tailor it by specifying relevant indicators and units.

Figure 19. Input needed from the other impact areas for logistics impact assessment and its outputs.

Table 25 provides examples of outputs of logistics impact assessment outputs that serve as inputs for other impact areas. Some of them overlap with the recommended indicators above, while others need to be added. Please note that the required input needs must be specified in detail, as they are unique to each project. The table below is not exhaustive.

Table 25. Outputs from logistics impact assessment required as input for other impact areas.

Impact area requiring input	Needed input
Services and operation Traffic safety Energy and environment	Transport patterns
Transport activity and fleet composition	Transport patterns, vehicle fleet

Overview of approaches and methods

Selecting the right method for evaluating logistics ensures relevant and reliable results. The choice is influenced by the project's objectives and the resources available to the partners. Additionally, the available tools and data shape the feasibility and effectiveness of different approaches (see Chapter 3.3 for further details).

Table 26 provides an overview of various approaches used in logistics evaluations. It highlights the strengths, weaknesses, and requirements of each method, helping to identify those that best align with the project's objectives, resources, and specific evaluation aspects. It is important to note that, even when the cons outnumber the pros, one pro can outweigh multiple cons.

Table 26. An overview of approaches and methods for evaluation of logistics.

Approach/method	Pros	Cons	Requirements
Field experiment on public roads	<p>Involves real stakeholders and operations, yielding genuine, real-world data.</p> <p>Allows calibration and validation of simulations models.</p>	<p>Conducting a test in real traffic is difficult, time-consuming, and expensive.</p> <p>The safety of participants and other road users requires careful planning.</p>	<p>Equipped vehicles.</p> <p>Access to logistics areas and relevant road network.</p> <p>Permits to perform tests and collect data.</p>
Test track	<p>More controlled environment than on public roads.</p> <p>The safety of participants and other road users is easier to ensure.</p> <p>More realistic than a simulator.</p>	<p>Simplified environment.</p> <p>Less natural traffic flow.</p> <p>Test effect leading to participants being more alert, traffic rule compliant, or trusting the system more than in the real world.</p> <p>May still be difficult, costly, and time-intensive to arrange.</p>	<p>Equipped vehicles.</p> <p>A suitable test track with a layout to match the tested logistics operation.</p> <p>Budget for track rental, staffing, and setup.</p>
Simulation of logistics operations	<p>Systematically explores multiple scenarios with minimal risk.</p> <p>Low-cost iteration compared to field experiments.</p>	<p>The simulation depends on model accuracy.</p> <p>Model accuracy depends on correct assumptions about vehicles, the environment, and behaviours.</p>	<p>A realistic model of the logistics operation and operational domain.</p> <p>Accurate data for calibration.</p> <p>Simulation expertise.</p>

Pitfalls and best practices

Evaluating impacts on logistics requires consideration of the methods and approaches used, as these can significantly influence the validity and reliability of the results. Overlooking potential pitfalls may lead to flawed conclusions, misinterpretation of findings or unintended biases. By proactively addressing the pitfalls, these can be avoided.

Table 27 provides some common pitfalls of logistics evaluation and presents actionable best practices to address them.

Table 27. Pitfalls in evaluation of logistics and best practices to avoid them.

Topic	Pitfall	Related best practice
Simulations of logistics operations	Different models provide contradictory results due to inconsistent assumptions or incomplete datasets.	<p>Validate and calibrate models with real-world data.</p> <p>Involve domain experts to check the realism of assumptions.</p>

Test track	The test environment does not fully cover all the important aspects of the logistics operation under evaluation.	<p>Identify different alternative test environments and locations suitable for the operation under evaluation.</p> <p>If necessary, split the testing across different tracks to evaluate different aspects or parts of the logistics operations.</p> <p>Document any limitations due to controlled settings and consider additional validation if needed for realism.</p>
Field experiment on public roads	<p>The real world is complex, multi-fold, and unpredictable, making it challenging to capture all factors that affect logistics operations.</p> <p>Lack of permits and support from authorities and needed stakeholders.</p>	<p>Identify key corridors and demonstration sites where local stakeholders are invested in CCAM or logistics development.</p> <p>Collaborate with living-labs with an existing network of partners and regulatory pathways. Leverage these collaborations to ensure the results have real impact for users, stakeholders, businesses, and society.</p> <p>Allow sufficient time for permit applications and stakeholder agreements.</p>

4.3.3. Transport activity and fleet composition

4.3.3.1. Introduction

Definition and scope

EU-CEM defines the transport activity and fleet composition impact area as follows:

The transport activity and fleet composition impact area addresses the impacts of CCAM on the total amount of realised travel and transport as well as on the number and types of vehicles used.

Transport activity refers to the total amount of realised travel on a road network over a certain period. It can be expressed in terms of vehicle kilometres travelled (VKT) (also called mileage or kilometrage), passenger kilometres travelled (PKT), or tonne-kilometres travelled (TKT). It results from the movements of people (People mobility, Chapter 4.2.2) and commercial transport of goods (Logistics, Chapter 4.3.2) subject to the constraints posed by service supply (Services and operation, Chapter 4.3.1) and network conditions (Traffic flow efficiency, Chapter 4.3.5).

Transport activity covers potential effects of CCAM on the total VKT, PKT or TKT. This includes changes in modal split and spatial and temporal distributions both within and outside the operational design domain (ODD) of the CCAM system. Vehicle fleet composition focuses on how CCAM influences the total number and characteristics of the vehicles in the transport system.

Background

Van Wee [55] defines four main characteristics of the transport system:

1. The transport volume or total **transport activity**
2. The composition of traffic and transport in terms of **modal split and vehicle categories**
3. The **spatial division** of transport activity per vehicle category

4. The **temporal division** of transport activity per vehicle category.

Spatial division refers to how traffic is distributed across the road network, whereas temporal division describes when travel occurs, such as the time of day, week or month.

CCAM can affect these characteristics through several mechanisms, depending on which systems are introduced, how they operate, and how they are taken into use. The resulting changes in transport activity, whether an increase or a decrease in total VKT or shift between travel modes, can vary widely:

- People mobility (Chapter 4.2.2): Automation of passenger cars may cause travellers to use cars more often or over longer distances, leading to higher car VKT. Conversely, automated public transport could draw users away from personal cars, decreasing overall VKT.
- Logistics (Chapter 4.3.2): Shifting from larger vehicles to multiple smaller delivery robots can increase VKT, but the additional kilometres could be covered by smaller, electric vehicles.

CCAM may also change the spatial and temporal distribution of VKT. For example, limited operational design domains might lead to automated car users preferring motorways where automation can be used, even if travel times increase. Smaller delivery robots could shift freight traffic to new routes or to operate at different times of day compared to trucks and vans. The possibility of automated truck platoons driving at night or working while travelling could affect trip schedules.

Transport activity and fleet composition impacts have important consequences for other impact areas. For example, the overall impact of CCAM on energy use and emissions (Chapter 4.3.6) heavily depends on how VKT changes per mode. Automated personal cars may drive more efficiently than human-driven vehicles, but any gains could be offset if the total car VKT increase sufficiently to raise total emissions and energy consumption.

Figure 20 shows the main components of the transport activity and fleet composition impact area.

Figure 20. Main components of the transport activity and fleet composition impact area.

4.3.3.2. Guidelines

Indicator recommendations

The result indicators recommended to be evaluated by each project addressing transport activity and fleet composition are listed in Table 28 below. Impacts are differences/changes between the baseline and treatment scenarios for these indicators. An impact can be reported as an absolute value (with unit below) or relative value (%). If it is not possible to evaluate some of the indicators below, the reason for this should be reported as part of the ‘comply or explain’ principle of the EU-CEM. The indicators listed below are not exhaustive; in addition to these, each project should define indicators of their own in accordance with Guideline 3.12.

Table 28. Indicators recommended to be evaluated by each project addressing transport activity and fleet composition.

Indicator short name	Definition	Unit
Total kilometres travelled	The total kilometres travelled in a defined road network over a specified period of time, per travel mode and specified units of time and space within and outside of the operational design domain.	VKT, PKT, and/or TKT
Distribution of kilometres travelled over time	The distribution of total kilometres travelled over time (e.g. during and outside peak hours).	%
Fleet composition	Number (or share) of vehicles per category and per key characteristic. Categories are e.g. passenger vehicle, truck. Key characteristics are e.g. age, motive power, mass, dimensions, emission factors. Reported per region and per year, or for a specific road (type) at a specific moment in time.	Number of vehicles, % of total fleet
Modal split	Share of each travel or transport mode, per specified time and space of VKT, PKT, TKT.	%

Impact pathways

Impact pathways illustrate how changes caused by CCAM, and assessed in other impact areas, affect the outcomes of this impact area. Mapping these cause-and-effect relationships helps scope the evaluation by grounding it in established theories or empirical findings. It clarifies how localised effects can escalate to larger scale impacts, shows whether one area influences another, and reveals how these changes ripple through vehicles, individuals, the transport system and beyond. Using these pathways can help identify where additional information is needed or where collaboration is required with other impact areas, or to ascertain whether certain aspects fall outside the scope of the assessment.

Transport demand and fleet composition are influenced by impacts on people mobility (Chapter 4.2.2), services and operation (Chapter 4.3.1), as well as logistics (Chapter 4.3.2). This is depicted in the impact pathway below (Figure 21). The figure offers a general overview that can be adapted or extended to specific CCAM systems studied. Each project should tailor it by specifying relevant indicators and units.

Figure 21. Input needed from the other impact areas for transport activity and fleet composition impact assessment and its outputs.

Table 29 provides examples of outputs of transport activity and fleet composition impact assessment that serve as inputs for other impact areas. Some of these outputs overlap with the recommended indicators listed above, while others must be additionally considered. Please note that the required input needs must be specified in detail, as they are unique to each project. The table below is not exhaustive.

Table 29. Outputs from transport activity and fleet composition impact assessment required as input for other impact areas.

Impact area requiring input	Needed input
Traffic safety Traffic flow efficiency Energy and environment	Total kilometres travelled per mode, fleet composition

Overview of approaches and methods

Selecting the right method for evaluating transport activity and fleet composition ensures relevant and reliable results. The choice is influenced by the project’s objectives and the resources available to the partners. Additionally, the available tools and data shape the feasibility and effectiveness of different approaches (see Chapter 3.3 for further details).

Table 30 provides an overview of various approaches used in transport activity and fleet composition evaluations. It highlights the strengths, weaknesses, and requirements of each method, helping to identify those

that best align with the project’s objectives, resources, and specific evaluation aspects. It is important to note that, even when the cons outnumber the pros, one pro can outweigh multiple cons.

Table 30. An overview of approaches and methods for transport activity and fleet composition impact assessment.

Approach/method	Pros	Cons	Requirements
Travel surveys (Passengers: VKT, fleet, PKT)	<p>Relatively easy and cost-efficient to administer.</p> <p>Large samples can yield robust indicators.</p>	<p>Usually, only measure trips that actually occurred (with established modes of transport), without asking how CCAM would change travel habits, or how they have changed (this would require a very mature CCAM service to be available on a large scale).</p> <p>Respondents may struggle to estimate changes resulting from CCAM. For example, in their number of trips and choice of mode.</p> <p>Self-reported travelled distances can be imprecise.</p>	<p>Representative sample of target population.</p> <p>Conduct surveys before and after CCAM introduction.</p> <p>Clear instructions (e.g. defining a “trip” to increase distance reporting accuracy).</p>
Transport surveys (Freight: VKT, fleet, TKT)	<p>Relatively easy and cost-efficient to administer.</p> <p>Large samples can yield robust indicators.</p>	<p>Subject to survey bias.</p> <p>Challenging to cover several freight transport categories comprehensively.</p>	<p>Representative sample across freight categories.</p> <p>Conduct surveys before and after CCAM introduction.</p>
Statistics-based approach	<p>Relatively easy and cost-efficient.</p> <p>Utilisation of existing datasets.</p>	<p>Inconsistent definitions or data collection methods can limit the comparability of statistics.</p> <p>May lack detail for CCAM-specific questions.</p>	<p>Availability of detailed, standardised statistics.</p> <p>Verification of data sources and definitions.</p>
Four-stage macroscopic modelling (VKT, PKT, modal split in specific region)	<p>Can simulate and compare multiple scenarios with CCAMs of differing ODDs.</p> <p>Well-established method requiring moderate data input.</p> <p>Macroscopic models directly provide the required indicators.</p>	<p>Limited capacity reflects nuanced changes in personal activities and related travel.</p> <p>Requires a model of the region. May be difficult to obtain or develop.</p>	<p>Access to or development of a detailed, validated macroscopic model.</p> <p>Calibration with real data.</p> <p>Clear definitions of scenarios (e.g. specifying ODD constraints).</p> <p>Detailed demand segments needed.</p>

	Can cover impacts on multiple impact areas.		
Activity-based or land-use macroscopic transport modelling (modal split)	Can simulate and compare multiple scenarios with CCAMs of differing ODDs. Allows for modelling changes in personal activities and related travel.	Less established method. Model requires calibration. Often resource-intensive to set up and calibrate. Modelled rather than observed values. Requires careful interpretation.	Software capable of simulating activity-based or land-use macroscopic transport models. Access to or development of a calibrated and detailed model. Data for calibration.

Pitfalls and best practices

Evaluating impacts on transport activity and fleet composition requires consideration of the methods and approaches used, as these can significantly influence the validity and reliability of the results. Overlooking potential pitfalls may lead to flawed conclusions, misinterpretation of findings, or unintended biases. By proactively addressing the pitfalls, these can be avoided.

Table 31 provides some common pitfalls of transport activity and fleet composition impact assessment and presents actionable best practices to address them.

Table 31. Pitfalls in transport activity and fleet composition impact assessment and best practices to avoid them.

Topic	Pitfall	Related best practice
Travel surveys	Respondents find it hard to understand the CCAM concept and thus how it would change transport activity and fleet composition.	Put considerable effort into describing and visualising the CCAM system to make it understandable to respondents.
Data for generalising survey results to a societal scenario	Sufficiently detailed statistics not available for the targeted area.	Use the best available statistics, e.g. from similar cities or regions.

4.3.4. Traffic safety

4.3.4.1. Introduction

Definition and scope

EU-CEM defines the traffic safety impact area as follows:

The traffic safety impact area addresses the impacts of CCAM on the number of accidents²⁰ and injuries of different severities.

Traffic safety is measured by the number of fatalities or injured persons within or relative to a specific entity, such as area, road section, road user or population group, vehicle or vehicle kilometre travelled (VKT). These measurements are chosen because the traffic safety policy objectives of Vision Zero [56] aim to eliminate injuries and minimise the severity in road traffic accidents, even if they still occur. Here, road traffic accidents are defined as accidents occurring on public or private roads, involving at least one motor vehicle, and resulting in injury or property damage [57].

This chapter does not cover safety validation, as it falls outside the scope of EU-CEM, nor does it address the technical functioning of CCAM systems (for details on that, see Chapter 4.1.1). This chapter addresses the ex-ante evaluation of the safety impact in societal scenarios with CCAM of typically high technological readiness, assuming the systems have already been safety validated. Chapter 4.1.2 discusses differences in driving behaviour between manually driven and automated vehicles.

Procedures for accident investigation following real-world testing are beyond the scope of EU-CEM. In the event of an accident during real-world testing, test sites should adhere to the road accident protocols established within the jurisdiction where the accident occurred.

Background

The number of fatalities and injuries is determined by three key factors: exposure, risk and consequence [58]. Exposure refers to the amount of activity where an accident could potentially occur, like vehicle kilometres or hours travelled, number of vehicles or frequency of incidents. Risk is the expected number of accidents per unit of exposure. Consequence refers to the outcome or severity of the accident in terms of injuries or property damage. These dimensions have a multiplicative relationship, as shown in Figure 22, where the volume of the box represents the number of fatalities or injuries of a specific severity.

²⁰ It is acknowledged that terms ‘crash’ and ‘collision’ are used by many as synonyms for ‘accident’. Projects can use any of these synonyms.

Figure 22. Three dimensions of traffic safety (redrawn from Nilsson [58]).

Traffic safety can be influenced by changes in any of the three dimensions. Thus, the number of fatalities or injuries can be lowered by reducing exposure (E) or accident risk (R), or by mitigating consequences (C). Reducing exposure to accidents means, for example, reducing the amount of travel or shifting to travel modes with a lower accident risk (see Chapter 4.2.2). Changing driving behaviour (Chapter 4.1.2) can reduce accident risk. Mitigating consequences means reducing the severity of accidents, for example, by better protecting people from serious injuries or death [59]. Figure 23 illustrates the factors affecting the three dimensions of traffic safety.

Figure 23. Main components of the traffic safety impact area.

The three-dimensional viewpoint, derived from systems theory, states that traffic accidents result from failures in the interaction between the transport system's components: traffic environment, vehicle, and road users. Traffic safety interventions can directly or indirectly affect various parts of the transport system and the three dimensions. The direct impacts of CCAM result from short-term changes in driving or travel, such as differences in the desired time gap or target speed between automated vehicles and human-driven ones. Indirect impacts occur when road users, both CCAM users or non-users, inadvertently change their behaviour through adaptation. This can, in turn, compensate for the direct impacts. Behavioural adaptation due to CCAM includes changes in driving skills in the long term and imitation of CCAM driving behaviour among non-users or users driving in manual mode. These aspects must be considered when assessing the traffic safety impacts of interventions such as CCAM systems. The safety assessment framework, initially developed for intelligent transport systems (ITS) [60][61] and later refined for automated vehicles [17], covers both direct effects and behavioural adaptation, providing guidance for this assessment. The framework consists of nine impact mechanisms:

- 1) Direct modification of the driving task, driving behaviour or travel experience
- 2) Direct influence by physical and/or digital infrastructure
- 3) Indirect modification of CCAM user behaviour
- 4) Indirect modification of non-user behaviour
- 5) Modification of interaction between CCAM vehicles and other road users
- 6) Modification of exposure/amount of travel
- 7) Modification of modal split
- 8) Modification of route choice
- 9) Modification of consequences due to different vehicle design.

Traffic safety can be viewed through the traffic safety pyramid (Figure 24), which categorises events by their frequency and severity [62]. The broad base represents frequent, regular, low risk encounters and interactions. Moving up, events become less frequent but more severe. Potential conflicts such as near misses occupy a smaller layer above the base. The higher layers represent increasingly severe accidents, culminating in fatal accidents at the top. This hierarchical structure shows the relationship between frequency and severity in traffic situations. Interventions addressing the lower layers, such as promoting safer driving behaviour, can prevent more serious accidents. CCAM could be one such intervention.

Figure 24. Traffic safety pyramid (adapted from Hydén [62]).

A related concept is subjective safety, which refers to a person’s feeling of safety. The relationship between subjective and objective safety is complex [63]. Typically, better objective safety improves subjective safety, while decreased objective safety worsens it, but mismatches occur. For example, objectively safer conditions may still feel unsafe, while unsafe conditions might feel safe due to a lack of awareness. These changes can lead people to alter their behaviour, for example through risk compensation. In EU-CEM, subjective safety is addressed under user evaluation in Chapter 4.2.1.

4.3.4.2. Guidelines

Indicator recommendations

Result indicators recommended to be evaluated by each project addressing traffic safety are listed in Table 32 below. Impacts are differences or changes between the baseline and treatment scenarios for these indicators. An impact can be reported as an absolute value (with unit below) or relative value (%). If it is not possible to evaluate some of the indicators below, the reason for this should be reported as part of the ‘comply or explain’ principle of the EU-CEM. The indicators listed below are not exhaustive; in addition to these, each project should define indicators of their own in accordance with Guideline 3.12.

Table 32. Indicators recommended to be evaluated by each project addressing traffic safety.

Indicator short name	Definition	Unit
Road injuries or injury accidents	Number of road injuries or injury accidents, subdivided by severity (fatal, serious, slight). Often reported annually for the target societal scenario and fleet.	Number
Property damage only accidents	Number of property damage only accidents. Often reported annually for the region of the target societal scenario and fleet.	Number

Accident risk	Frequency of accidents relative to an exposure measure (e.g. vehicle kilometres travelled, hours driven, number of scenario instances). This quantifies how often accidents occur under specified conditions (vehicle type, environment, conflict scenario).	Number per exposure unit
Accident severity	Probability of a given accident severity level (fatal, serious, slight) once an accident has occurred. May be further broken down by environment (e.g. urban/rural/motorway) or scenario type (e.g. merging conflict, lane-change conflict).	%

Impact pathways

Impact pathways illustrate how changes caused by CCAM, and assessed in other impact areas, affect the outcomes of this impact area. Mapping these cause-and-effect relationships helps scope the evaluation by grounding it in established theories or empirical findings. It clarifies how localised effects can escalate to larger scale impacts, shows whether one area influences another, and reveals how these changes ripple through vehicles, individuals, the transport system and beyond. Using these pathways can help identify where additional information is needed or where collaboration is required with other impact areas, or to ascertain whether certain aspects fall outside the scope of the assessment.

Traffic safety is influenced by the impacts of CCAM on driving behaviour (Chapter 4.1.2), users (Chapter 4.2.1), people mobility (Chapter 4.2.2), and logistics (Chapter 4.3.2). This is depicted in the impact pathways below (Figure 25). The figure offers a general overview that can be adapted or extended to the specific CCAM systems studied. Each project should tailor it by specifying relevant indicators and units.

Figure 25. Input needed from the other impact areas for traffic safety impact assessment and its outputs.

Table 33 provides examples of outputs of traffic safety impact assessment that serve as inputs for other impact areas. Some of these outputs overlap with the recommended indicators listed above, while others must be additionally considered. Please note that the required input needs must be specified in detail, as they are unique to each project. The table below is not exhaustive.

Table 33. Outputs from traffic safety impact assessment required as input for other impact areas.

Impact area requiring input	Needed input
Quality of life Equity	Number of fatalities and injuries
Socio-economics	Number of fatalities, injuries, and property damage only accidents

Overview of approaches and methods

Selecting the right method for evaluating traffic safety ensures relevant and reliable results. The choice is influenced by the project’s objectives and the resources available to the partners. Additionally, the available tools and data shape the feasibility and effectiveness of different approaches (see Chapter 3.3 for further details).

Table 34 provides an overview of various approaches used in traffic safety evaluations. It highlights the strengths, weaknesses, and requirements of each method, helping to identify those that best align with the project’s objectives, resources, and specific evaluation aspects. It is important to note that, even when the cons outnumber the pros, one pro can outweigh multiple cons.

When analysing surrogate safety measures, the validity of the results also relates to the validity of the measure itself (i.e. it should be proven that the number of conflicts as specified in the study correlates with the number of accidents in the scenario of interest).

Simulating safety-relevant scenarios is a common method for assessment, with their main approaches detailed in Table 35. For more information about simulation-based approaches, see ISO 21934 ‘Road vehicles—Prospective safety performance assessment of pre-crash technology by virtual simulation’.

Table 34. An overview of approaches and methods for evaluation of traffic safety.

Approach/method	Pros	Cons	Requirements
Simulation of safety-relevant scenarios	Allows systematic exploration of a high number of safety-relevant scenarios.	The validity of the result depends on model’s validity, the assumptions made and the input data quality.	Software suitable for simulation of safety-critical situations. Road user behaviour model suitable for safety-critical situations. Valid model of the automated vehicle. Suitable injury risk functions to model change in accident severity.

Driving simulator, e.g. for studying human reactions in take-over situations (direct effect) or usage of automated driving systems (indirect effect).	Potential to safely explore safety-critical situations. Good control of conditions and repeatability.	The validity of the result depends on the simulator's validity enabling realistic perception of speed and the visual environment. People take more risks in simulators than in real life.	Simulator (hardware and software) suitable for testing of safety-critical situations, with potential additional features based on specific scenarios.
Analysis based on accident statistics for estimating impacts on fatalities or injuries, or target accidents potentially influenced by CCAM.	Allows scaling up to larger regions and longer time periods. Allows estimation of the maximum potential safety impact.	Poor data quality and quantity. Lack of contextual accident data to account for e.g. the ODD, various causes or underlying reasons for the accidents. The impact of new systems is not reflected in statistics until they are widely used.	Availability of suitable accident statistics. Effect sizes must be estimated in combination with accident statistics. Target accidents must be derived from accident statistics.

Table 35. An overview of approaches to simulation of safety-relevant scenarios.

Approach	Description	Pros	Cons
Baseline approach with Monte-Carlo sampling	Simulating all road users with sampling from existing distributions of pre-conflict situations.	Suitable for simulation of safety critical situations. Can consider surrounding traffic.	High simulation effort. Distributions of pre-conflict situations must be available.
Counterfactual Baseline approach	Simulation of variation of real-world accident with different objects: ego-vehicle and conflicting road user(s).	Suitable for simulation of safety-critical situations.	Not possible to consider surrounding traffic. Limited availability of detailed data of vehicle movements in real-world accident cases.
Microscopic traffic simulations and trajectory analysis tool (e.g. SSAM tool [64])	Analysis of conflicts based on trajectories from microscopic traffic simulations.	Good software availability. Possibility for scenario testing.	Software generally not suitable for simulation of safety-relevant situations, as models typically assume safe driver behaviour and may not accurately capture the complexities of unsafe driving. Unrealistic result if the software is not designed to simulate realistic behaviour in conflict situations.

Pitfalls and best practices

Evaluating traffic safety impacts requires consideration of the methods and approaches used, as these can significantly influence the validity and reliability of the results. Overlooking potential pitfalls may lead to flawed conclusions, misinterpretation of findings or unintended biases. By proactively addressing the pitfalls, these can be avoided.

Table 36 presents some common pitfalls of evaluation traffic safety evaluation and presents actionable best practices to address them.

Table 36. Pitfalls in the evaluation of traffic safety and best practices to avoid them.

Topic	Pitfall	Related best practice
Using appropriate simulation tools and models	Using tools and models not designed for simulating conflicts or safety-relevant situations, or outside their defined range, can lead to incorrect or invalid outcomes.	Use the simulation tool and model developed specifically for studying conflicts or safety-relevant situations, and only in the context they are defined for.
Using speed as a surrogate measure for safety	Using speed as a safety proxy only from a single-vehicle and not traffic-flow perspective. Lower driving speed is safer only if all vehicles drive slower.	Understand how different surrogate measures can and cannot be used. Select a surrogate measure that is valid for the situation.
Using conflicts as surrogate measure for safety	No validated specifications for conflicts for all traffic environments.	Understand how different surrogate measures can and cannot be used. Select a surrogate measure that is valid for the situation.
New safety-critical situations	Insufficient evidence of the frequency and nature of new safety-critical situations caused specifically by driving automation.	Estimate the impact as a function of frequency (per situation type) to show a range of results. If the frequency of the new accidents becomes known later, read the impact from these results.
Accident statistics	No access to suitable accident databases.	Include partners with access to necessary databases in the consortium, or acquire access.

4.3.5. Traffic flow efficiency

4.3.5.1. Introduction

Definition and scope

EU-CEM defines the traffic flow efficiency impact area as follows:

The traffic flow efficiency impact area addresses the impacts of CCAM on collective traffic patterns, travel times and throughput on a road network.

Traffic flow efficiency describes the ability of the road network to serve the required demand for travel and transport without unnecessary delays. This chapter covers the effects of CCAM on average travel times and delays of different road user groups, on the throughput of roads, and on the resilience of road networks in terms of recovery after interruptions. Traffic flow characteristics emerge from the behaviours of and interactions between individual drivers and vehicles (driver-vehicle units). The interactions create patterns that are independent of an individual's behavioural details. This impact area thus concerns the movement of a group of vehicles or the traffic stream as a whole, rather than individual vehicles alone.

Not within the scope of this impact area, but linked to it, are impacts on services and operations (see Chapter 4.3.1), people mobility (see Chapter 4.2.2), and logistics (see Chapter 4.3.2). The impacts of CCAM on mobility and logistics service provision influence travel and transport patterns, which in turn affect traffic flow efficiency. Additionally, changes in fleet operations and traffic management (see Chapter 4.3.1), such as platooning or signal control priorities, implemented alongside CCAM systems, may also impact traffic flow efficiency. As a result, the methods used to assess traffic flow efficiency impacts can help identify optimal traffic management or fleet operation measures and parameters.

Network theory, which describes the structure and dynamics of networks at different scales, can be combined with traffic flow analysis. For example, changes in network topology (can be addressed under impacts areas of land use (see Chapter 4.4.1) and services and operation (see Chapter 4.3.1)) can enable new links between locations and lead to reallocation of traffic, affecting also travel times on different links. Methods of traffic flow efficiency assessment can be used to plan these changes in topology if traffic flow optimisation is desired. Additionally, impacts on traffic safety (Chapter 4.3.4) directly affect the amount of congestion caused by accidents, but are beyond the scope of this chapter.

This chapter does not cover the effects of CCAM on the driving behaviour of individual drivers or vehicles, such as speed preferences, acceleration and deceleration abilities, and headway settings. These are part of the driving behaviour impact area (see Chapter 4.1.2). Impacts on emissions and energy use stemming from changes in traffic flow dynamics are covered in Chapter 4.3.5.

Background

Traffic flow theory studies the collective movement of vehicles on roads. Collective movement results from interactions between individual driver-vehicle units and their interaction with the road environment and can lead to emergent effects and traffic patterns [65].

The main levels of analysis are microscopic and macroscopic traffic theory, which differ in their scope and approach to representing reality [65]. The **microscopic level** describes each individual vehicle's behaviour separately, in terms of (targeted and actual) speed and headway (in space or time), lane changes and braking patterns. On the **macroscopic level**, traffic flow is analysed as a continuous flow, similar to how liquids behave in motion. Instead of individual vehicles, corresponding variables describe aggregated flow: density in terms of vehicles per road kilometre corresponds to space headway, flow in terms of vehicles per hour to time headway, and average speed to acceleration and deceleration dynamics of vehicles.

Traffic models based on the macroscopic and microscopic, as well as their intermediate mesoscopic, levels have been developed and are commonly applied in traffic simulation software to assess traffic flow efficiency on roads and networks, as well as to ‘predict’ potential changes with different interventions. The microscopic, macroscopic and mesoscopic levels of analysis include changes of the traffic state over time [66]. Another way to describe and analyse traffic flow is by **flow-density diagrams**, which can be used to study the average behaviour of driver-vehicle units, or to determine the level of service or roads and their capacity (maximum throughput) [65]. A special form of this diagram is the **fundamental diagram of traffic flow**, which describes the theoretical pairwise relationships between density, flow, and speed in stationary, homogeneous traffic, assuming identical driver-vehicle units [65]. Fundamental diagrams represent the traffic state at a certain road section. A related concept is the macroscopic fundamental diagram, or network fundamental diagram, which represents the relationship between area-wide traffic flow, density, and speed. It can be used when assessing the overall capacity and efficiency of a network.

Additionally, **resilience theory** can be applied to assess a network’s ability to withstand and recover from disruptions caused by external factors such as accidents or weather events.

In general, the **characteristics of traffic flow** on a road or network depend on several elements:

- The size and characteristics of vehicles and their variation among vehicles on the road network
- Driving behaviour and its variation among vehicles on the road
- The demand for road travel and transport distributed over space and time
- The road infrastructure and environment
- Environmental and other variable conditions.

Figure 26 shows the main components of the traffic flow efficiency impact area.

Figure 26. Main components of the traffic flow efficiency impact area.

4.3.5.2. Guidelines

Indicator recommendations

The result indicators recommended to be evaluated by each project addressing traffic flow efficiency are listed in Table 37. Impacts are differences/changes between the baseline and treatment scenarios in these indicators. An impact can be reported as an absolute value (with unit below) or relative value (%). If it is not possible to evaluate some of the indicators below, the reason for this should be reported as part of the ‘comply or explain’ principle of the EU-CEM. The indicators listed below are not exhaustive; in addition to these, each project should define indicators of their own in accordance with Guideline 3.12.

Table 37. Indicators recommended to be evaluated by each project addressing traffic flow efficiency.

Indicator short name	Definition	Unit
Travel time	Average travel time per vehicle kilometre travelled (VKT), per vehicle category.	Seconds/VKT
Delay	Difference between actual travel time and travel time according to speed limit.	Seconds/VKT
Throughput	Volume of vehicles per hour or passengers per hour that travel through a given section of a network.	Vehicles/h (per lane) or pax/h
Travel time reliability	Travel time reliability quantifies the variation of travel time for a given trip and time period over a selected time horizon [67].	50 th and 95 th percentile of travel time
Resilience	Resilience is measured as time to recovery, i.e. the time it takes for a traffic system to return to normal or acceptable operating conditions following a disruption, e.g. an accident. The time to recovery starts when the accident site is cleared and vehicles can move again (i.e. the time needed for emergency handling is not counted).	Minutes, hours

Impact pathways

Impact pathways illustrate how changes caused by CCAM, and assessed in other impact areas, affect the outcomes of this impact area. Mapping these cause-and-effect relationships helps scope the evaluation by grounding it in established theories or empirical findings. It clarifies how localised effects can escalate to larger scale impacts, shows whether one area influences another, and reveals how these changes ripple through vehicles, individuals, the transport system, and beyond. Using these pathways can help identify where additional information is needed or where collaboration is required with other impact areas, or to ascertain whether certain aspects fall outside the scope of the assessment.

Traffic flow efficiency is influenced by driving behaviour (Chapter 4.1.2), transport activity and fleet composition (Chapter 4.3.3), and services and operation (Chapter 4.3.1). This is depicted in the impact pathway in Figure 27. The figure offers a general overview that can be adapted or extended to specific CCAM systems studied. Each project should tailor it by specifying relevant indicators and units.

Figure 27. Input needed from the other impact areas for traffic flow efficiency impact assessment and its outputs.

Table 38 provides examples of outputs of the impact assessment of traffic flow efficiency that serve as inputs for other impact areas. Some of these outputs overlap with the recommended indicators above, while others must be additionally considered. Please note that the required input needs must be specified in detail, as they are unique to each project. The table below is not exhaustive.

Table 38. Outputs from traffic flow efficiency impact assessment required as input for other impact areas.

Impact area requiring input	Needed input
Services and operation Logistics	Travel time and its predictability
Traffic flow efficiency	Travel time, Delay
Energy and environment	Speed patterns
Accessibility	Travel time per mode

Overview of approaches and methods

Selecting the right method for evaluating traffic flow efficiency ensures relevant and reliable results. The choice is influenced by the project’s objectives and the resources available to the partners. Additionally, the available tools and data shape the feasibility and effectiveness of different approaches (see Chapter 3.3 for further details).

Traffic simulation is a widely used tool for analysing traffic flow efficiency and assessing changes resulting from different interventions, as it enables cost-effective study of the movements of large numbers of vehicles over a road or network. Impacts of changes to any of the elements, such as driving behaviour, road layout or traffic management measures on traffic flow characteristics, can be estimated. In line with the microscopic and macroscopic traffic flow theories, different simulation models have been developed with different application scopes.

Microscopic models describe trajectories of individual vehicles over space and time. They can, to some extent, model vehicles with a range of driving behaviours, and may therefore be suitable for studying the impacts of driving automation or connectivity on traffic flow efficiency [65].

Microscopic traffic simulation typically considers road sections or small networks, simulating single traffic scenarios. If the societal scenario requires assessing impacts on a regional scale, results from these traffic scenario simulations can be scaled up to the target region using available statistics and other data.

Macroscopic traffic models consider collective patterns across a network. These models can be used to estimate effects on the societal scenario directly, provided that a suitable model and required input are available on the macroscopic level of potential changes resulting from different microscopic behaviour.

The mesoscopic level combines elements of the microscopic and macroscopic viewpoints. Several questions related to CCAM services may require trip-based dynamic traffic models, which allow for changing mode and route while considering a traveller’s full day of movement. They also account for different modes and CCAM services for various trips throughout the day.

It is important to note that, since traffic is always influenced by human behaviour and external conditions, no model can achieve perfect accuracy. It is, therefore, necessary to be clear about the assumptions and limitations when interpreting the results of simulation studies, while making sure to employ the theories and models with best descriptive power for the research questions and scenarios set in the project [68]. This is especially true for CCAM systems that are not yet widely deployed, and several assumptions are required when implementing their behaviour into traffic models.

Table 39 provides an overview of various approaches used in traffic flow efficiency evaluation. It highlights the strengths, weaknesses, and requirements of each method, helping to identify those that best align with the project’s objectives, resources, and specific evaluation aspects. It is important to note that, even when the cons outnumber the pros, one pro can outweigh multiple cons.

Table 39. An overview of approaches and methods for evaluation of traffic flow efficiency.

Approach/method	Pros	Cons	Requirements
Field experiment	<p>Enables direct observation of the effects of CCAM on traffic flow, if the penetration rate under evaluation can be tested. Feasible in use cases where the number of CCAM vehicles is low also in the targeted societal scenario, such as public transport services.</p> <p>Can be used as a way to collect input for calibration</p>	<p>Quantitative observations of some traffic phenomena are challenging to reproduce consistently [67].</p> <p>Requires significant effort.</p> <p>Often, a sufficient penetration rate of automated driving in</p>	<p>Real-world implementation of CCAM system of sufficient TRL.</p> <p>Clear view on how tested situations link to traffic flow efficiency impacts.</p> <p>Similar baseline and treatment conditions (with respect to traffic</p>

	of the simulation models when the TRL of the CCAM system in the field experiment allows.	the traffic flow cannot be achieved. Accuracy of the results depends on the size of the test site (road km, vehicles, users) and duration of the experiment.	demand, weather etc.).
Microscopic traffic simulation for assessing impacts in different traffic scenarios (e.g. Vissim [69], Aimsun [70], SUMO [71])	Produces time-space trajectories of all individual vehicles. Describes movements of individual driver-vehicle units and interactions between them, road characteristics, and static and dynamic traffic control [68]. Effects of different CCAM penetration rates and traffic scenarios can be studied systematically. More resource-efficient for studying traffic flow than real-world measurements.	Highly dependent on the accuracy of driver models and assumptions. Models require input data that may not be available; often rely on assumptions. May not be accurate enough for describing all relevant aspects. Calibration can be difficult, e.g. due to lack of detailed driving pattern data, especially for CCAM vehicles (future driving patterns not known, proprietary issues).	Model for automated driving behaviour incl. realistic longitudinal and lateral behaviour. Modelling single vehicle behaviour correctly, for studying the effects of different driving styles on road capacity [65].
Scaling up of impacts from microscopic traffic simulation to a city or region by weighting the impacts per traffic scenario with the VKT in the area of interest.	Allows estimation of regional impacts when no suitable macroscopic models are available.	Required data may not be available and approximations are necessary.	Statistics on VKT per road and vehicle category in the area of interest.
Macroscopic traffic simulation for assessing impacts in a city or region (e.g. Visum [72], Aimsun)	Potential to explore systematically the impacts of CCAM at aggregated level. Offers the potential to study impacts on several impact areas in one model, as they can integrate elements of mode choice and travel patterns (Chapter 4.2.2) and traffic flow efficiency.	Approximates the results that would be obtained from analysing individual vehicle trajectories. Aggregation may decrease the accuracy of results and limit insight into the causes of impacts. The impact of CCAM should first be known at microscopic level to estimate the impact of traffic flow level on parametrisation of the macroscopic model (e.g.	Macroscopic model of the region of interest, including road network, travel modes and schedules, demographics, origins and destinations. Expected changes in traffic flow must be observable at macroscopic level. Results from microscopic simulations (or comparable data) needed as input, such as effects on driving

		in terms of passenger car units). Macroscopic models are costly to create or acquire.	behaviour in terms of passenger car units. Information on the change in value of travel time or attractiveness of the mode.
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Pitfalls and best practices

Evaluating traffic flow efficiency impacts requires consideration of the methods and approaches used, as these can significantly influence the validity and reliability of the results. Overlooking potential pitfalls may lead to flawed conclusions, misinterpretation of findings or unintended biases. By proactively addressing the pitfalls, these can be avoided.

Table 40 provides some common pitfalls of traffic flow efficiency evaluation and presents actionable best practices to address them.

Table 40. Pitfalls in evaluation of traffic flow efficiency and best practices to avoid them.

Potential Topics	Pitfall	Related best practice
Indicators: Travel time reliability and Resilience	These indicators are difficult to capture with current traffic simulation models, or in field tests with few CCAM vehicles.	Real-world implementation. For resilience impacts, qualitative assessment by interviewing relevant experts, e.g. from road authorities, can give an indication of the direction and magnitude of potential impacts.
Field experiments	Field tests rarely provide sufficient data to enable assessment of traffic flow impacts, especially with large penetration rates of CCAM vehicles and in a variety of traffic scenarios.	Combine field experiments with traffic simulation.
Microscopic simulation tools	Models may not be accurate enough to depict driving behaviour of automated and human-driven vehicles in all traffic situations, and especially their differences.	Include sensitivity analysis and variation in simulation parameters and assumptions. Use the expertise of the technical team in defining parameters. Consider the limitations of the models when analysing results and drawing conclusions.
Macroscopic simulation tools	Macroscopic models may not be able to accurately depict the differences in driving behaviour of automated and human-driven vehicles and resulting traffic flow patterns.	Limit the simulation to microscopic models or use results from microscopic models as input.
Prototypes	While CCAM technologies are in the advanced stages of development and undergoing real-world testing, field experiments may still involve rather low TRL prototypes. Thus, their	By combining a clear understanding of low readiness level aspects with insights from the technical team, a

	<p>impact assessment and evaluation using traffic models could be prone to inaccuracies and errors when the societal scenario under evaluation includes high readiness CCAM.</p>	<p>model can be developed for representing automated vehicles.</p> <p>It is beneficial to delineate the types of assumptions required, distinguishing between scenarios where real-world data inform the models and those relying solely on simulations, which might necessitate a broader range of assumptions.</p>
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4.3.6. Energy and environment

4.3.6.1. Introduction

Definition and scope of evaluation area

EU-CEM defines the energy and environment impact area as follows:

The energy and environment impact area addresses the impacts of CCAM on energy use and on emissions of vehicles, air quality, and noise pollution.

The impacts addressed under this impact area are:

- Greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions, such as carbon dioxide (CO₂), methane (CH₄), and nitrous oxide (N₂O)
- Energy use
- Pollutant emissions and air quality
- Noise exposure.

This area studies the potential of CCAM to reduce overall energy use, emissions, and noise from road traffic, and to contribute to related environmental goals. It evaluates whether CCAM offers better alternatives to current travel modes and mobility services, guiding policymakers on how (and how not) to implement CCAM.

Undesired environmental impacts, such as poor air quality and high noise levels, harm physical and mental health. These impacts are addressed in the quality of life (Chapter 4.2.3) and liveability impact areas (Chapter 4.4.2). Indirect environmental impacts also include those related to climate change like flooding, and resource extraction like cobalt mining.

Assessing the overall impacts of CCAM on energy use and the environment requires accounting for potential changes in travel behaviour (see Chapter 4.2.2), logistics (see Chapter 4.3.2), total vehicle kilometres travelled (VKT) and fleet characteristics (see Chapter 4.3.3), as well as driving behaviour (see Chapter 4.1.2). Impacts on sustainability are addressed in Chapter 4.4.6, which should be referred to for detailed guidelines.

Background

The main environmental impacts related to CCAM are:

- **Greenhouse gas emissions.** CO₂ and other GHGs (CH₄, N₂O) can be expressed as CO₂ equivalents using the global warming potential (GWP) index [73]. Since the role of non-CO₂ gases in road transport is often minimal, projects may choose to focus only on CO₂ emissions.
- **Energy use.** Includes energy for vehicle operations and physical and digital infrastructure, such as data centres. CCAM could increase VKT with electric vehicles, requiring higher charging station capacities

and potentially new station locations for better grid integration. Energy use of automation-enabling systems, such as sensors and back-end systems, should also be considered.

- **Pollutant emissions and air quality.** Includes tailpipe emissions and wear-related pollutants (e.g. brake and tire wear) such as carbon monoxide (CO), nitrogen oxides (NOx), particulate matter (PM10 and PM2.5), hydrocarbons (HC), and sulphur dioxide (SO₂).
- **Noise exposure.** Includes tire, engine, brake, acceleration, and aerodynamic noise.

Assessing a vehicle's greenhouse gas emissions and fuel or electricity use typically focuses on tank-to-wheel emissions ("tailpipe" emissions) during the usage phase. A comprehensive assessment should include well-to-tank emissions, which are indirect emissions from fuel or electricity production and distribution. Beyond GHG emissions, assessing pollutant emissions and air quality can be relevant.

Beyond the usage phase, other lifecycle stages such as manufacturing of vehicles and their components, and deployment and operation of physical, digital and operational infrastructure, also generate GHG emissions. Lifecycle assessment (LCA) is recommended for estimating emissions across all stages.

Tailpipe emissions can be further analysed by distinguishing between warm-phase and cold-start emissions, the latter being especially relevant for urban areas and short trips. Non-tailpipe emissions, such as those from evaporation and tire wear, may be relevant as well.

The role of material use becomes more prominent if CCAM is introduced alongside advancing vehicle electrification. New vehicle and infrastructure investments require assessing how resource use across manufacturing, maintenance, and physical and digital infrastructure implementation affect the environment. Additionally, CCAM components may increase energy demand, reduce electric vehicle range and battery life, and add to material waste.

Other potential²¹ environmental impacts of CCAM include soil and water quality, such as nitrogen deposition, and vibrations. Vibrations are especially relevant when heavy automated vehicles operate in residential areas at night.

Environmental agreements, policies, and directives at local, national, and European levels aim to reduce the environmental impact of transport by setting legally binding targets for climate, air quality, and noise reduction. Key European Agreements as of 2024 are the Paris Agreement,²² the European Green Deal,²³ the Zero Pollution Action Plan,²⁴ and EU Directives on air quality [77] and environmental noise [78].

GHGs and energy use of a road network over time are influenced by the carbon or energy intensity of vehicles, as well as the total travel and transport activity as visualised in Figure 28. CCAM can affect emissions and energy use through both direct and indirect mechanisms, with both long- and short-term consequences:

- **Driving behaviour** (see Chapter 4.1.2). Changes in speed patterns, acceleration, and other driving patterns can affect energy use and emissions per VKT.

²¹ Although relevant only for specific cases and, therefore, not addressed in detail in this chapter.

²² The Paris Agreement is an international treaty on climate change, covering climate change mitigation and adaptation with the long-term temperature goal of limiting the increase to 1.5°C [74].

²³ The European Green Deal is a set of proposals adopted by the European Commission with the aim to reduce net GHG emissions by 2030 by 55% compared to 1990 levels [75].

²⁴ The Zero Pollution Action plan sets key 2030 targets for reducing air, water and soil pollution by 2050 to levels that are no longer considered harmful [76].

- **Shared vehicles** (see Chapters 4.3.1 and 4.2.2). Changes in the use of shared vehicles can alter the total VKT if the occupancy rate is affected. Additionally, this may result in changes in the number of vehicles required for the same amount of passenger kilometres.
- **Logistics patterns** (see Chapter 4.3.2). Changes to delivery vehicle size, usage, and logistics operations can influence energy use and emissions per VKT, and tonne-kilometres travelled.
- **Travel modes** (see Chapter 4.2.2). CCAM can influence travel mode choices, impacting the number of people using each mode and altering the modal split (see Chapter 4.3.3). Emissions and energy use per person kilometre travelled vary between modes.
- **Travel options** (see Chapters 4.3.1, 4.3.7 and 4.2.2). Changes in available travel options influence trip counts, mode choice, routes, total kilometres driven and transported, and timing.
- **Vehicle fleet composition** (see Chapter 4.3.3). Changes in vehicle characteristics, such as the size and power chain, impact emissions and energy use, as they affect carbon intensity (second-order effects).

Figure 28. Main components of the energy and environment impact area.

4.3.6.2. Guidelines

Indicator recommendations

The result indicators recommended to be evaluated by each project addressing energy and environmental impacts are listed in Table 41. Impacts are differences/changes between the baseline and treatment scenarios in these indicators. An impact can be reported as an absolute value (with unit below) or relative value (%). If it is not possible to evaluate some of the indicators below, the reason for this should be reported as part of the 'comply or explain' principle of the EU-CEM. The indicators listed below are not exhaustive; in addition to these, each project should define indicators of their own in line with Guideline 3.12.

Table 41. Indicators recommended to be evaluated by each project addressing energy and environment.

Indicator short name	Definition	Unit
CO ₂ emissions	CO ₂ emissions divided by the metric of operation per vehicle category. The metric of operation can be e.g. the number of vehicle-, passenger- or tonne-kilometres travelled. Other GHG emissions can be considered by using CO ₂ equivalents instead of CO ₂ emissions.	g/VKT/vehicle category g/pax-km, g/tonne-km
Energy use	Required energy to operate vehicles per metric of operation per vehicle category. The metric of operation can be e.g. the number of vehicle-, passenger- or tonne-kilometres travelled.	kWh/VKT/vehicle category, kWh/pax-km, kWh/tonne-km
Pollutant emissions	Pollutant emissions divided by the metric of operation per vehicle category. The metric of operation can be e.g. the number of vehicle-, passenger- or tonne-kilometres travelled.	g/VKT/vehicle category, g/pax-km, g/tonne-km
Air quality exposure	Concentrations of pollutants in the air (or air quality levels) and exposure.	µg/m ³ Number of inhabitants exposed to concentration levels exceeding legal limits or defined thresholds.
Noise exposure	Noise levels at specific locations, expressed as L _{den} (day-evening-night level) and L _{night} and exposure.	dB(A) Number of inhabitants exposed to noise levels exceeding legal limits or defined thresholds.

Impact pathways

Impact pathways illustrate how changes caused by CCAM, and assessed in other impact areas, affect the outcomes of this impact area. Mapping these cause-and-effect relationships helps scope the evaluation by grounding it in established theories or empirical findings. It clarifies how localised effects can escalate to larger scale impacts, shows whether one area influences another, and reveals how these changes ripple through vehicles, individuals, the transport system and beyond. Using these pathways can help identify where additional information is needed or where collaboration is required with other impact areas, or to ascertain whether certain aspects fall outside the scope of the assessment.

Environmental and energy impacts are influenced by driving behaviour (Chapter 4.1.2), people mobility (Chapter 4.2.2) and logistics (Chapter 4.3.2). Additionally, transport activity and fleet composition (Chapter 4.3.3) can affect, either directly or indirectly, energy use and emissions of GHG, air pollutants, and noise. Figure 29 shows these main impact pathways. The figure offers a general overview that can be adapted or extended to specific CCAM systems studied. Each project should tailor it by specifying relevant indicators and units.

Figure 29. Input needed from the other impact areas for energy and environmental impacts of CCAM systems.

Table 42 provides examples of outputs of the energy and environmental impact assessment that serve as inputs for other impact areas. Some of these outputs overlap with the recommended indicators listed above, while others must be additionally considered. Please note that the required input needs must be specified in detail, as they are unique to each project. The table below is not exhaustive.

Table 42. Outputs from energy and environmental impact assessment required as input for other impact areas.

Impact area requiring input	Needed input
Quality of life	Noise exposure, pollutant emissions, air quality.
Socio-economics	Total CO ₂ (and/or greenhouse gas) emissions for area and period of societal scenario.
Equity	Noise exposure, pollutant emissions, air quality, energy use.

Overview of approaches and methods

Selecting the right method for evaluating energy and environmental impacts ensures relevant and reliable results. The choice is influenced by the project’s objectives and the resources available to the partners. Additionally, the available tools and data shape the feasibility and effectiveness of different approaches (see Chapter 3.3 for further details). The most feasible method to use depends on many factors, which relate to the specific scenarios, the research questions and the methods available for data collection.

While addressing emissions is important, prioritising what is feasible based on the expected impact is necessary. If data are difficult to retrieve or methodologies are challenging to execute, warm phase tailpipe GHG emissions should be prioritised, followed by cold-start emissions, other pollutants and air quality indicators.

Table 43 provides an overview of various approaches used in energy and environment evaluations. It highlights the strengths, weaknesses, and requirements of each method, helping to identify those that best align with the project’s objectives, resources, and specific evaluation aspects. It is important to note that, even when the cons outnumber the pros, one pro can outweigh multiple cons.

Table 43. Overview of different methods that can be used for evaluation of energy and environmental impacts.

Method	Pros	Cons	Requirements
Direct measurements (in-vehicle and roadside)	<p>Provides empirical, real-world values for energy use, pollutant and GHG emissions, and noise production.</p> <p>Conducted under real-world conditions. Reflects actual operational variability.</p>	<p>Cost-intensive due to sensor equipment and installation.</p> <p>Difficult to deploy (especially for emissions) and keep calibrated.</p> <p>Limited to specific vehicles and tested scenarios, making broader generalisation challenging.</p> <p>Experimental conditions are hard to control.</p>	<p>Deployed CCAM with sufficient TRL.</p> <p>Well-calibrated, robust sensor equipment.</p> <p>Comparable baseline and treatment conditions (e.g. traffic, weather).</p> <p>Long-term, diverse measurement periods to capture variety.</p>
Emission and energy use calculation tools (e.g. EnViVer [79], PHEM [80], Quartet [81])	<p>Resource-efficient alternative to field measurements for fleet-average impacts.</p> <p>Capable of simulating multiple scenarios, more detailed than macroscopic approaches (considers traffic conditions, driving styles, road topography, etc.).</p>	<p>Models can be hard to obtain, costly (licence fees), and resource intensive.</p> <p>Input data gaps require assumptions, which may affect accuracy.</p> <p>May not accurately represent future vehicle technologies (e.g. Euro 7) or real-world driving variability (e.g. speed patterns).</p>	<p>High-resolution microscopic driving data (e.g. 1 Hz speed data per vehicle) from either direct measurements or microscopic traffic simulations.</p> <p>Emission factors or functions for all vehicle categories.</p>
Macroscopic modelling of emission and energy use for aggregated traffic flows in the network (e.g. HBEFA [82])	<p>Effective for assessing impacts at regional level (by road type, vehicle category, or mode).</p> <p>Useful for evaluating changes in overall VKT and aggregated energy use.</p>	<p>Complex and resource-intensive models. Can be hard to obtain for large regions.</p> <p>May mask micro-level variations.</p> <p>Potential licence fees and computational demands.</p>	<p>Access to regional macroscopic traffic model with link-level outputs (volumes, capacities, speeds).</p> <p>Emission factors for all vehicle categories and road types.</p> <p>Sufficient computational resources and modelling expertise.</p>

<p>Air quality modelling (pollutant emissions) for aggregated traffic flows in the network</p>	<p>Allows studying pollutant dispersion and overall air quality changes due to CCAM without extensive field sensors.</p> <p>Integrates traffic emissions with environmental factors (buildings, terrain, population).</p> <p>Useful for policy assessment regarding air quality.</p> <p>Allows to assess impacts beyond what is feasible in the real world.</p>	<p>Often involves expensive software and model licence fees.</p> <p>Highly dependent on detailed, multi-dimensional input data.</p> <p>Model predictions can carry significant uncertainties in dispersion outcomes.</p>	<p>Comprehensive data on traffic emissions and detailed geographic data on buildings, terrain, and population exposure.</p> <p>Robust dispersion model validated against measured air quality data.</p> <p>Sufficient computational resources and modelling expertise.</p>
<p>Noise modelling for aggregated traffic flows in the network</p>	<p>Allows studying noise level changes due to CCAM without extensive field measurements.</p> <p>Can simulate noise impacts over diverse urban layouts and scenarios.</p> <p>Useful for policy assessment regarding urban noise pollution.</p> <p>Allows to assess impacts beyond what is feasible in the real world.</p>	<p>Requires advanced noise propagation models and high-quality input data on noise sources.</p> <p>Often entails costly software or licence fees.</p> <p>Model outputs can be highly sensitive to assumptions regarding source characteristics and environmental conditions.</p>	<p>Detailed data on traffic noise production (tire, engine, brake, etc.)</p> <p>GIS data on urban topography, building geometry, and population exposure.</p> <p>Validated noise propagation model.</p> <p>Sufficient computational resources and modelling expertise.</p>
<p>Expert judgement (based on outputs from other impact areas or from similar studies)</p>	<p>Provides qualitative insights when empirical data or models are lacking, for example into expected direction and size of impact.</p> <p>Allows integration of multidisciplinary knowledge.</p>	<p>Lacks quantitative precision and can be subjective.</p> <p>Outcomes may vary significantly between experts.</p> <p>Difficult to apply consistently in complex cases, multidimensional impact assessment.</p>	<p>Access to a panel of experts across relevant fields.</p> <p>Use of structured elicitation techniques to reduce bias.</p> <p>Availability of comparable outputs from other impact areas or studies.</p>

National legislation, guidelines, methods, and instruments should be considered or utilised when assessing the effects of CCAM on air quality, noise pollution, and carbon emissions. These are often applied at the macroscopic network level, such as using noise maps for cities or major roadways.

Pitfalls and best practices

Evaluating impacts on energy and the environment requires consideration of the methods and approaches used, as these can significantly influence the validity and reliability of the results. Overlooking potential pitfalls may

lead to flawed conclusions, misinterpretation of findings or unintended biases. By proactively addressing the pitfalls, these can be avoided.

Table 44 provides some common pitfalls of energy and environmental impact assessment and presents actionable best practices to address them.

Table 44. Pitfalls in the evaluation of energy and environment and best practices to avoid them.

Topic	Pitfall	Related best practice
Direct measurements	Field experiment emissions and energy use data considered too sensitive to share.	Instead of relying solely on sensitive data, integrate modelling of automated driving patterns with emission models. This hybrid approach helps in simulating real-world behaviour while protecting sensitive information.
Emission factors and models	Utilising outdated or unsuitable emission factors and models can result in inaccurate or misleading assessments.	Ensure that the latest versions of emission factors and models are used, including projections for future scenarios. Additionally, consult experts in emission factors and modelling to validate the selection and application of these factors.
Representativeness of outcomes	Drawing conclusions for the entire transport network based on data from small or specific sections, a narrow set of traffic scenarios, or only CCAM vehicles may lead to overgeneralisation.	Clearly define and specify the conditions (e.g. ODD) under which the results apply. Evaluate and document how representative these conditions are of the broader traffic environment.
Baseline comparison	Validity of comparisons compromised due to insufficient baseline data, such as ignoring existing fleet compositions, traffic flow patterns or travel demand.	Utilise available resources and diverse datasets from multiple locations. Adjust for discrepancies, model incomplete datasets by sampling from statistical distributions, and employ averages when detailed input is unavailable.
System boundaries in lifecycle assessment (LCA)	Neglecting indirect impacts in lifecycle assessment.	Define system boundaries carefully, including relevant lifecycle stages.
Overlooked indirect impacts	Focusing only on direct emissions or energy use and ignoring indirect effects, such as changes in travel demand, fleet composition or logistics patterns.	Include both direct and indirect impacts in the evaluation, considering factors like induced demand, modal shifts, and logistics changes.
Temporal and spatial scope	Neglecting variations in emissions and energy impacts over time (e.g. time of day, weather conditions) or across regions.	Ensure evaluation covers a variety of temporal and spatial conditions to capture variations and improve the generalisability of results.

4.3.7. Accessibility

4.3.7.1. Introduction

Definition and scope

EU-CEM defines the accessibility impact area as follows:

The accessibility impact area addresses the impacts of CCAM on the potential of population groups to reach destinations and services at different times of day, and the potential of businesses, facilities and other activity centres to receive people and goods.

Accessibility reflects how easily people can engage in activities at various locations and how efficiently goods be transported between them [83]. It shows how well the transport system connects individuals and businesses, enables participation in activities across varied places and times, and facilitates the exchange of information, goods, and services [84].

The level of accessibility is influenced by [83]:

- The location of activities
- The characteristics of infrastructure and available travel or transport options
- The needs and financial means of people and businesses.

Accessibility varies across different spatial locations and for different trip purposes. Accessibility assessment considers:

- **Travel resistance or disutility:** the ease, difficulty or affordability of reaching various locations.
- **Attractiveness of opportunities:** the appeal or desirability of activities and services available at those locations.

Accessibility represents the potential for interaction within the transport system. People mobility and logistics actualise this potential through actual travel, while travel activity aggregates these interactions into measurable outcomes.

Certain factors are beyond the scope of this chapter but are highly relevant for understanding the impact of CCAM on accessibility. These include changes in:

- Individuals' travel patterns (Chapter 4.2.2)
- Transport patterns of goods (Chapter 4.3.2)
- Service offerings (Chapter 4.3.1)
- Land use (Chapter 4.4.1).

Background

Geurs and van Wee [85] defined four key components of accessibility: land use, transportation, temporal, and individual.

The **land-use component** refers to the characteristics of land use in terms of:

- The amount, quality, and spatial distribution of opportunities such as employment, shopping, healthcare, recreational facilities, and education
- The demand for these opportunities in places where people live
- The juxtaposition of supply and demand for opportunities, which can lead to competition for limited resources.

The **transportation component** describes the transport network and the inconveniences, or disutility, of travelling between origins and destinations using chosen modes of transport. This includes travel time, waiting time, parking time, fixed and variable costs, and the effort related to reliability, comfort and accident risk. Disutility arises from the confrontation between supply (location and infrastructure features like speed limits, public transport schedules, fares) and demand (passenger and logistics needs).

The **temporal component** includes time-related restrictions, such as the availability of opportunities throughout the day, individuals' time for activities, and the specified delivery windows for goods.

Finally, the **individual component** reflects the personal factors like needs, abilities, preferences, attitudes and opportunities, significantly affecting access to different travel options and distant opportunities.

CCAM can affect all four components of accessibility.

Regarding **land use**, the impacts are indirect and long-term and are covered in the land use impact area (Chapter 4.4.1). Over time, CCAM could make remote locations more accessible, leading to a redistribution of opportunities. This may result in a reduced concentration of activities in urban centres and more dispersed spatial distribution of employment, shops, and facilities. Conversely, reductions in travel time or perceived travel time could encourage agglomeration, with businesses concentrating in areas with high customer flows and people travelling to large shopping centres that offer a variety of services in one location.

CCAM may affect the **temporal component** of accessibility by offering services at different times of day, such as 24/7 robot deliveries or automated shuttles, unlike conventional services with limited night-time availability. It may also change how people use their time, enabling work during travel, or broaden activities possible within a given timeframe through reduced travel times. Changes in trip timing (e.g. peak versus off-peak hours) can affect traffic flows. These temporal effects are discussed in the impact areas services and operation (Chapter 4.3.1), people mobility (Chapter 4.2.2), logistics (Chapter 4.3.2), and traffic flow efficiency (Chapter 4.3.5).

Regarding the **individual component**, CCAM might offer new transport options for underserved groups such as older adults, people with disabilities, and those in areas with limited public transport [86]. It may also make travel more affordable and offer personalised experiences that more effectively meet individual needs, abilities, and preferences. This relates to equity in access and affordability (see Chapters 4.3.7 and 4.4.5), user evaluation (Chapter 4.2), and people mobility (Chapter 4.2.2). Ensuring CCAM benefits are widely and equitably distributed is important for enhancing accessibility for all. Achieving this requires affordable, understandable, and easy-to-use mobility and transport options.

Of the four components, the **transportation component** most directly influences accessibility. CCAM can affect the disutility of travel in several ways:

- Changing the value of travel time by allowing engagement in activities besides driving during the trip.
- Removing the need for parking or enabling vehicles to park themselves at a distance.
- Changing affordability of travel through options like affordable public transport or taxi services.
- Enabling more flexible and efficient services, such as on-demand shuttles.
- Optimising traffic management and route planning by enabling automated vehicles to collaborate for better network performance.
- Reducing accidents and accident-induced congestion.
- In the long term, influencing transport infrastructure design, such as reducing demand for parking spaces.

Figure 30 shows the main components of the transport activity and fleet composition impact area.

Figure 30. Main components of the accessibility impact area.

4.3.7.2. Guidelines

Indicator recommendations

Result indicators recommended to be evaluated by each project addressing accessibility are listed in Table 45 below. Impacts are differences/changes between the baseline and treatment scenarios in these indicators. An impact can be reported as an absolute value (with unit below) or relative value (%). If it is not possible to evaluate some of the indicators below, the reason for this should be reported as part of the ‘comply or explain’ principle of the EU-CEM. The indicators listed below are not exhaustive; in addition to these, each project should define indicators of their own in accordance with Guideline 3.12.

Table 45. Indicators recommended to be evaluated by every project addressing accessibility.

Indicator short name	Definition	Unit
Reachable activities	Total number of activities of a given category reachable within a defined travel time from a person, household or business. Categories can be work, education, facilities, main economic locations, etc. An indicator can be broken down by target groups and regions. An acceptable travel time per travel mode can be defined, for example, as 30 min by car, 45 min by public transport or 30 min by bicycle.	Number
Reachable people, households or businesses	Number of people, households or businesses that can be reached from an activity centre within a defined travel time. Activity centres can be work,	Number

	education, facilities, main economic locations, etc. An indicator can be broken down by target groups and regions. An acceptable travel time per travel mode can be defined, for example, as 30 min by car, 45 min by public transport or 30 min by bicycle.	
Mobility options	Number of mobility options available within a specified distance (e.g. demand-responsive transport, automated taxi service) for trips from home to the desired destination.	Number
Understandability of mobility options	Percentage of users who struggle to use a specific mobility option (e.g. due to complexity, lack of clear information or digital access barriers).	%
Affordability	Average share of household budget spent on mobility.	%

Impact pathways

Impact pathways illustrate how changes caused by CCAM and assessed in other impact areas affect the outcomes of this impact area. Mapping these cause-and-effect relationships helps scope the evaluation by grounding it in established theories or empirical findings. It clarifies how localised effects can escalate to larger scale impacts, shows whether one area influences another, and reveals how these changes ripple through vehicles, individuals, the transport system and beyond. Using these pathways can help identify where additional information is needed or where collaboration is required with other impact areas, or to ascertain whether certain aspects fall outside the scope of the assessment.

Accessibility is influenced by impacts on users (Chapter 4.2.1), land use (Chapter 4.4.1), people mobility (Chapter 4.2.2), logistics (Chapter 4.3.2), services and operation (Chapter 4.3.1), as well as traffic flow efficiency (Chapter 4.3.5). This is depicted in the impact pathway in Figure 31. The figure offers a general overview that can be adapted or extended to specific CCAM systems studied. Each project should tailor it by specifying relevant indicators and units.

Figure 31. Input needed from the other impact areas for accessibility impact assessment and its outputs.

Table 46 provides examples of outputs of accessibility impact assessment that serve as inputs for other impact areas. Some of these outputs overlap with the recommended indicators listed above, while others must be additionally considered. Please note that the required input needs must be specified in detail, as they are unique to each project. The table below is not exhaustive.

Table 46. Outputs from accessibility impact assessment required as input for other impact areas.

Impact area requiring input	Needed input
Quality of life	Number of reachable activities
Land use	Reachable destinations
Liveability	Number of reachable activities, Number of reachable people
Economic activity and employment	Reachable destinations, Reachable people

Overview of approaches and methods

Selecting the right method for evaluating accessibility ensures relevant and reliable results. The choice is influenced by the project’s objectives and the resources available to the partners. Additionally, the available tools and data shape the feasibility and effectiveness of different approaches (see Chapter 3.3 for further details).

Table 47 provides a comparative overview of various approaches used in accessibility evaluations. It highlights the strengths, weaknesses, and requirements of each method, helping to identify those that best align with the

project's objectives, resources, and specific evaluation aspects. It is important to note that, even when the cons outnumber the pros, one pro can outweigh multiple cons.

Table 47. An overview of approaches and methods for accessibility impact assessment.

Approach/method	Pros	Cons	Requirements
Geographical analysis (travel duration maps/isochrone maps)	Provides objective measures.	Requires separate maps for different times of the day or week.	Availability of map data and GIS tools. If timing impacts are analysed, separate maps are needed for different times of the day or week. In this case, also hourly travel speed data is required.
Number of reachable activities: Geographical analysis based on measured or simulated travel data. Can be visualised on a map or given as a total number, for instance per zone	Objective measure. Can incorporate the mobility system and how it is operated.	Sensitive to the quality of available data.	Data on activities, their locations, trip requirements, and available travel modes.
Number of mobility options: Geographical analysis measuring distances between origins or destinations, and public transport stops or other entry/exit locations to mobility services	Objective measure. Can incorporate the mobility system and how it is operated.	Sensitive to the quality of available data.	Data on the location of origins and destinations. Data on mobility service offerings.
Affordability: Surveys	Relatively easy and cost-effective to evaluate.	Respondents may struggle to estimate affordability in terms of 'share of household budget spent on mobility' accurately when it consists of multiple elements.	Representative sample of respondents. Realistic cost estimates. Respondents need a good understanding of CCAM, preferably from real-world experience.
Understandability of mobility options: Survey	Relatively easy and cost-effective to evaluate.	Subjective responses on understandability might not always reflect real ability to understand options correctly.	Respondents need a good understanding of CCAM, preferably from real-world experience.

Pitfalls and best practices

Evaluating accessibility impacts requires consideration of the methods and approaches used, as these can significantly influence the validity and reliability of the results. Overlooking potential pitfalls may lead to flawed conclusions, misinterpretation of findings or unintended biases. By proactively addressing the pitfalls, these can be avoided.

Table 48 provides some common pitfalls of accessibility impact assessment and presents actionable best practices to address them.

Table 48. Pitfalls in accessibility impact assessment, and best practices to avoid them.

Potential Topics	Pitfall	Related best practice
Origin-Destination data	Available origin-destination (O-D) data is not detailed enough.	Create a synthetic population and O-D matrix using available travel survey data, demographic statistics, land-use data, etc.
Travel behaviour, mobility system, and operational data	No or limited data available on travel behaviour, mobility systems or their operation.	Use the best available data from similar regions or prior studies, adjusting as necessary to fit the context. Generate synthetic data using simulation models, such as activity-based simulations.
Temporal variability	Accessibility assessment fails to consider temporal variations, such as peak vs. off-peak travel times.	Incorporate time-of-day or seasonal variations into the assessment. Use dynamic modelling approaches to capture variations in travel patterns over time.
Lack of representativeness	Conclusions drawn from data that do not account for diverse demographics or spatial differences.	Ensure datasets represent key population groups and geographic areas. Weight data appropriately to reflect demographic or regional variations.
Limited mode-specific analysis	Accessibility analysis does not account for differences between travel modes (e.g. car, public transport).	Conduct mode-specific evaluations to assess accessibility for each mode. Ensure multimodal data are available, including travel times, costs, and service availability for each mode.
Equity and inclusion gaps	Accessibility impacts on vulnerable or underserved groups (e.g. older adults, people with disabilities) are overlooked.	Include equity-focused metrics to evaluate accessibility gaps for vulnerable or underserved groups. Use demographic data to model accessibility impacts on specific populations.

Misalignment with local context	Generic assumptions on mobility behaviour do not reflect local conditions (e.g. infrastructure, population density).	Adapt models and assumptions to reflect local transport infrastructure and population characteristics. Validate findings with stakeholders familiar with the local context.
Over-reliance on static data	Accessibility analysis does not account for real-time variations or future changes (e.g. new services).	Use dynamic or scenario-based modelling to account for potential changes in transport systems or user behaviour.

4.4. Society

4.4.1. Land use

4.4.1.1. Introduction

Definition and scope

EU-CEM defines the land use impact area as follows:

The land use impact area addresses the spatial and functional implications of CCAM by examining its effects on land utilisation patterns, including infrastructure development.

Land use describes how available land area is allocated for various purposes significant to the activities and functions of society. It is the socio-economic description of an area, or its functional dimension, including residential, industrial, commercial, agricultural, forestry, and recreational purposes [87]. Land use is closely tied to infrastructure investments and transport planning.

This impact area covers both direct and indirect effects of CCAM on land use over the short and long term:

- **Direct impacts:** Additional space required for construction of new lanes or pick-up/drop-off areas for CCAM systems.
- **Indirect impacts:** Improved accessibility through CCAM may encourage urban sprawl by dispersing activities into suburban or rural areas, supporting the viability of businesses and services in previously less accessible regions. Reduced need for parking spaces could free up land for other uses. Space may also be needed for digital infrastructure within the built environment.

While related, the liveability of areas (see Chapter 4.4.2) and accessibility (Chapter 4.3.7) are not included in the scope of the land use impact area.

Background

Two theoretical frameworks, the theory of urban fabrics and the land-use transport interaction theory, provide complementary perspectives on the relationship between land use and transport.

The **theory of urban fabrics** [88][89], focusing on urban land use, identifies three distinct categories or “fabrics” that shape the structure of cities: walking, public transport, and automobile fabric. These represent distinct systems in terms of mobility patterns, land use, and the associated infrastructure, environment, services, and businesses. The theory highlights the historical evolution of cities from compact, walkable centres to sprawling, car-dependent suburbs. Active travel modes such as cycling are recognised as important complementary modes

across all fabrics. The **walking urban fabric** represents the oldest, most compact urban form, typically located in and around city centres. It promotes walking as the primary mode of transport by keeping urban functions and services close together. Often, functions and elements of the walking fabric overlap with those of the public transport and automobile fabric.

The **public transport urban fabric** consists of areas shaped by public transport systems that expanded the reach of the traditional walking city, forming connected networks of neighbourhoods extending up to 20 km from the city centre. The fabric can serve as an alternative to car dependency in areas beyond the walking fabric. CCAM could improve the efficiency and accessibility of the public transport fabric.

The **automobile urban fabric** developed rapidly with the adoption of personal cars and is now ubiquitous in modern cities. Urban growth has largely been realised through car-dependent infrastructure and low-density suburbs. The automobile fabric often overlaps with, or supplants, the walking and public transport fabrics. The main challenge for CCAM is its potential to further reinforce the automobile fabric, potentially weakening the walking and public transport fabrics.

The theory of urban fabrics provides a framework for understanding and conceptualising the spatial structure of cities and its linkage to the transport system. This classification helps identify and understand the land use changes associated with or driven by CCAM.

The **theory of land use transport interaction** [90] conceptualises the bidirectional relationship between the transport system and land use, introducing the **land use transport feedback cycle** (Figure 32). It states that accessibility to locations affects land use patterns by influencing where investors, businesses, and households decide to locate. This in turn can lead to relocation of activities, affecting the demand for travel in the transport system. Based on systems theory, urban economics, and transport modelling, this theory is often applied in quantitative models to predict how transport patterns could evolve in response to changes in policies or investments.

Figure 32. Land-use transport feedback cycle (redrawn from Wegener & Fuerst [90])

According to this theory, the feedback cycle implies the following relationships [90]:

- The spatial distribution of land uses, including residential, industrial, and commercial areas, determines the locations of human activities, such as living, working, shopping, education, and leisure.
- The spatial distribution of **human** activities implies spatial interaction or trips in the transport system to overcome the distances between activity locations.
- The distribution of infrastructure in the **transport system** facilitates travelling and can be conceptualised as accessibility.
- The spatial distribution of accessibility partially determines location decisions, leading to changes in the **land-use** system.

The theory can be used to examine how CCAM might alter accessibility to various locations. Improved accessibility increases the attractiveness of locations for all types of land use, shaping the direction of urban development. Consequently, CCAM and land-use planning can significantly influence the design of future cities.

Increased use of CCAM may also vacate space for developing and expanding the infrastructure for pedestrians, cyclists and public transport or other city needs. For example, areas that become available through reduced need for parking space or multiple lanes for car traffic could be repurposed into public open spaces, residential areas or commercial developments.

The impact pathways of CCAM and land use suggest potential changes to land-use types, such as changes in urban density or the proportions of different density areas. These shifts may, in turn, affect housing and land prices. Figure 33 shows the main components of the transport activity and fleet composition impact area.

Figure 33. Main components of the land use impact area.

4.4.1.2. Guidelines

Indicator recommendations

A list of indicators recommended to be addressed by every project evaluating land use impacts is presented in Table 49. Impacts are differences/changes between the baseline and treatment scenarios in these indicators. An impact can be reported as an absolute value (with unit below) or relative value (%). If it is not possible to evaluate some of the indicators below, the reason for this should be reported as part of the ‘comply or explain’ principle of the EU-CEM. The indicators listed below are not exhaustive; in addition to these, each project should define indicators of their own in accordance with Guideline 3.12.

Table 49. Indicators recommended to be evaluated by every project addressing land use impacts.

Indicator short name	Definition	Unit
Land use distribution	Measures the allocations of land by type, such as residential, commercial, industrial, mixed-use, green space, and parking. Tracks the proportion and conversion of different land use types, such as converting parking to green space, as CCAM can alter the land use distributions through conversions.	Share of land use types within an area (%) or conversion ratios.
Density of housing	Evaluates the concentration of housing units in an area. Number of housing units in an area.	Housing units per km ²
Population density	Number of people living in an area.	Inhabitants per km ²
Housing and land prices	Average purchase price of housing per m ² Average purchase price of land per km ²	€

Impact pathways

Impact pathways illustrate how changes caused by CCAM, and assessed in other impact areas, affect the outcomes of this impact area. Mapping these cause-and-effect relationships helps scope the evaluation by grounding it in established theories or empirical findings. It clarifies how localised effects can escalate to larger scale impacts, shows whether one area influences another, and reveals how these changes ripple through vehicles, individuals, the transport system and beyond. Using these pathways can help identify where additional information is needed or where collaboration is required with other impact areas, or to ascertain whether certain aspects fall outside the scope of the assessment.

Land use impacts of CCAM are influenced by its impacts on accessibility (Chapter 4.3.7.1), services and operation (Chapter 4.3.1), as well as economic activity and employment (Chapter 4.4.3). This is depicted in the impact pathway below (Figure 37). The figure offers a general overview that can be adapted or extended to specific CCAM systems studied. Each project should tailor it by specifying relevant indicators and units.

Figure 34. Input needed from the other impact areas for land use impact assessment and its outputs.

Table 50 provides examples of outputs of the land use impact assessment that serve as inputs for other impact areas. Some of these outputs overlap with the recommended indicators listed above, while others must be additionally considered. Please note that the required input needs must be specified in detail, as they are unique to each project. The table below is not exhaustive.

Table 50. Outputs from land use impact assessment required as input for other impact areas.

Impact area requiring input	Needed input
Services and operation	Location of activities
Accessibility	Location of destinations
Economic activity and employment	Location of activities, Land use distribution

Overview of approaches and methods

Selecting the right method for evaluating the land use impacts of CCAM ensures relevant and reliable results. The choice is influenced by the project’s objectives and the resources available to the partners. Additionally, the available tools and data shape the feasibility and effectiveness of different approaches (see Chapter 3.3 for further details).

Table 51 provides a comparative overview of various approaches used in land use evaluations. It highlights the strengths, weaknesses, and requirements of each method, helping to identify those that best align with the project’s objectives, resources, and specific evaluation aspects. It is important to note that, even when the cons outnumber the pros, one pro can outweigh multiple cons.

Table 51. An overview of approaches and methods for land use impact assessment.

Approach/method	Pros	Cons	Requirements
Geographical modelling, land use and transport interaction modelling	Cost- and time-efficient. Allows evaluation in a controlled environment.	Limited applicability to the modelled area. Results are highly dependent on model accuracy and quality of input data.	Appropriate model calibrated for the research question and study area. Reliable input data (e.g. travel patterns, land use).
Scenario-based evaluation	Enables systematic exploration of different scenarios. Cost- and time-efficient.	Results depend heavily on assumptions and model accuracy.	Robust models for the research question. Expertise in setting relevant scenarios. Transparent documentation of assumptions for each scenario.
Visioning (e.g. “the superblock model” [91])	A visual approach makes it easier to communicate potential changes in land use. Facilitates exploration of how CCAM may support transition towards liveable and sustainable cities.	Some visioning models may not be feasible in real-world applications. High computing costs may limit their use.	Appropriate tools and software for visioning. Suitable model for the research question. Stakeholder input to validate feasibility and relevance.
Spatial analysis using the Geographic Information System (GIS)	Provides detailed spatial insights into land use changes and interactions. Effective for identifying areas suitable for new development or repurposing.	Requires high-quality spatial data which is not always available. May be time-intensive depending on the level of detail.	GIS tools and high-resolution spatial data. Expertise in spatial analysis to interpret results.
Stakeholder engagement (workshops, focus groups)	Captures qualitative insights on land use priorities and potential impacts. Encourages collaborative planning and decision-making.	Outcomes are subjective and may not align with the outcomes of objective data analysis.	Inclusion of diverse stakeholders (e.g. urban planners, policymakers, residents). Structured workshop protocols.

Pitfalls and best practices

Evaluating land use impacts requires consideration of the methods and approaches used, as these can significantly influence the validity and reliability of the results. Overlooking potential pitfalls may lead to flawed

conclusions, misinterpretation of findings or unintended biases. By proactively addressing the pitfalls, these can be avoided.

Table 52 provides some common pitfalls of land use impact assessment and presents actionable best practices to address them.

Table 52. Pitfalls in the land use impact assessment and best practices to avoid them.

Topic	Pitfall	Related best practice
Use of different modelling and visioning tools	The tools used are not capable of accurately simulating land use development or interactions with the transport system.	Use of simulation tools specifically designed for land use and transport interaction modelling. Leverage tools validated in similar projects or case studies.
Data quality and availability	Insufficient granularity of land use and transport data used as input for models, leading to inaccurate results.	Use the most recent and comprehensive data available. Combine multiple data sources (e.g. surveys, GIS data, census data) to improve data reliability.
Oversimplified scenarios	Scenarios fail to capture key variables, such as accessibility improvements, urban density or economic factors.	Develop detailed and diverse scenarios, incorporating a range of variables and stakeholder input.
Misalignment with local context	Generic models and assumptions do not reflect local land use and transport conditions (e.g. demographics, urban layouts).	Adapt models to the local context by calibrating with local data and stakeholder feedback. Validate findings against real-world conditions.
Neglecting indirect impacts	Non-transport-related indirect effects on land use, such as changes in urban sprawl or economic shifts, are overlooked.	Include indirect impacts in assessments.
Lack of stakeholder engagement	Stakeholders (e.g. urban planners, policymakers, residents) are not involved, leading to unrealistic assumptions.	Engage stakeholders through workshops, focus groups or surveys to gather diverse perspectives and validate assumptions.
Failure to account for temporal changes	Land use impacts are evaluated as static for the current situation without considering already known developments.	Use dynamic modelling to capture changes over short- and long-term horizons. Update models periodically to reflect new data and trends.
Over-reliance on one method	Reliance on a single modelling or evaluation method, limiting the scope of insights.	Combine multiple methods, such as scenario planning, GIS analysis, and stakeholder visioning, to provide a holistic understanding of impacts.

4.4.2. Liveability

4.4.2.1. Introduction

Definition and scope

EU-CEM defines the liveability impact area as follows:

The liveability impact area addresses the impacts of CCAM on the suitability or quality of living in the studied area(s) by analysing indicators from other impact areas to perform an integrated evaluation of their overall implications.

Although liveability is sometimes used interchangeably with quality of life, it focuses specifically on the collective characteristics of an area rather than on individuals' experiences. Liveability encompasses a wide range of environmental and socio-economic factors [92], reflecting what is often described as “the sum of the factors that add up to a community's quality of life—including the built and natural environments, economic prosperity, social stability and equity, educational opportunity and cultural, entertainment and recreational opportunities” [93].

Liveability is closely linked to transport, urban development, and public health. Consequently, its measurement requires a broad, multi-scale approach, including evaluations at local, city, and regional levels. Metrics typically span environmental conditions, public health outcomes, community cohesion and economic dimensions, considering both direct and indirect impacts.

This impact area does not directly assess:

- Land use distribution: See Chapter 4.4.1
- Individuals' quality of life: See Chapter 4.2.3
- Accessibility to goods and services: See Chapter 4.3.7
- Traffic safety: See Chapter 4.3.4
- Environmental impacts: See Chapter 4.3.6.

Background

Liveability encompasses the physical, social, and cultural factors that ensure all individuals have equal access to a sustainable and satisfying quality of life in their living environment [94]. Central to liveability is accessibility, the balance between the population's desire for life-enhancing opportunities and their access to resources. These factors include many sub-components of transport and urban systems potentially affected by new technologies like CCAM. Therefore, an important step in assessing CCAM's impacts on liveability is to identify the specific sub-components it influences.

Liveable areas provide affordable, diverse housing connected to employment, education, services, and recreation via convenient, safe, inclusive, health-promoting, and environmentally sustainable travel and transport modes [95]. Liveability is influenced by the level of urban development at transportation endpoints (i.e. high or low density of the area [96]). High density areas can more effectively support public transport and active travel modes, which can promote transport inclusiveness and provide accessibility to a wider population. Conversely, car-dependent urban sprawl tends to necessitate car ownership and reduce accessibility and transport inclusiveness for those without private vehicles.

The public health impacts of CCAM in a region depend on its effects on active travel, traffic safety, the environment, and access to health services. CCAM can lead to changes in travel times and local traffic volumes, affecting the liveability of these areas. To enhance liveability, CCAM systems with the potential to enhance active transport, accessibility, and environmental sustainability should be prioritised.

Assessing the liveability impacts of CCAM requires a holistic and integrative approach that incorporates inputs from multiple impact areas. The methods should combine these inputs into a unified assessment of feedback loops (Figure 35) and assess liveability across three key dimensions where transport plays a role: movement, place, and society [97] (Figure 36).

Figure 35. High-level summary of the causal loop diagram of CCAM impacts on liveability (redrawn from Harrison et al. [94]).

Figure 36. Main components of the liveability impact area (redrawn from Anciaes & Jones [97]).

4.4.2.2. Guidelines

Indicator recommendations

Result indicators recommended to be evaluated by each project addressing liveability are listed in Table 53. Impacts are differences/changes between the baseline and treatment scenarios in these indicators. An impact can be reported as an absolute value (with unit below) or relative value (%). If it is not possible to evaluate some of the indicators below, the reason for this should be reported as part of the ‘comply or explain’ principle of the EU-CEM.

Table 53. Indicators recommended to be evaluated by each project addressing liveability impacts.

Indicator short name	Definition	Unit
Quality of environment	Composite score representing the overall environmental quality of an area. Integrates indicators from other impact areas, for example: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Green access: Share of recreational land use relative to other land uses, accessibility of green spaces (e.g. number and area of green spaces relative to the population). - Environmental indicators: Air quality and perceived quality of open spaces. 	0 to 100
Public health	Composite score representing public health in the area. Integrates indicators from other impact areas related to direct health outcomes—such as fatalities, injuries, and severity—and	0 to 100

	environmental and behavioural factors including air quality, levels of active travel, and accessibility of health services.	
Community cohesion	Composite score representing the social bonds and collective identity within a community, integrating factors such as trust, civic participation, equity, accessibility, and perceived safety and security. Additional elements, including patterns of mobility and the usage of public or shared transport modes, contribute to understanding the strength of community ties. Alternatively, a qualitative assessment may be performed.	0 to 100 or a qualitative assessment
Economic vitality	Composite score representing the area's economic strength. Integrates indicators from other impact areas, such as employment levels, income metrics, business activity, and investment trends. Aggregates key economic performance metrics to reflect the overall vitality and growth potential of the local economy.	0 to 100
Local transport accessibility	Composite score representing the accessibility and efficiency of the local transport system. Integrates indicators from other impact areas, such as the availability and affordability of public transport, the density of reachable activities and destinations (households, businesses, services), the diversity of mobility options, and the prominence of active travel modes.	0 to 100

Liveability impact assessment can provide either a single liveability score, derived by combining the indicators in Table 53, potentially additional relevant indicators, or a set of individually compared indicators. In estimating these scores, relevant indicators should be normalised and weighted, then aggregated. The weighting for each indicator may differ. Guidance for establishing these weightings is beyond the scope of EU-CEM and must be determined on a project-specific basis.

Because many elements of liveability manifest at the local level and regional needs vary, assessing liveability impacts requires a localised approach [92], with the adoption of relevant indicators for each case [98]. Hence, the indicators listed above are not exhaustive; in addition to these, each project should define indicators of their own in accordance with Guideline 3.12.

Impact pathways

Impact pathways illustrate how changes caused by CCAM, and assessed in other impact areas, affect the outcomes of this impact area. Mapping these cause-and-effect relationships helps scope the evaluation by grounding it in established theories or empirical findings. It clarifies how localised effects can escalate to larger scale impacts, shows whether one area influences another, and reveals how these changes ripple through vehicles, individuals, the transport system and beyond. Using these pathways can help identify where additional information is needed or where collaboration is required with other impact areas, or to ascertain whether certain aspects fall outside the scope of the assessment.

Liveability is influenced by other impact areas, such as services and operation (Chapter 4.3.1), quality of life (Chapter 4.2.3) and accessibility (Chapter 4.3.7). The holistic nature of the liveability approach that covers all relevant areas is depicted in the impact pathways below (see Figure 37). The figure offers a general overview that can be adapted or extended to specific CCAM systems studied. Each project should tailor it by specifying relevant indicators and units.

Figure 37. Input needed from other impact areas for liveability impact assessment and its output.

Table 54 provides examples of outputs of liveability impact assessment that serve as inputs for other impact areas. Some of these outputs overlap with the recommended indicators above, while others must be added. Please note that the required input needs must be specified in detail, as they are unique to each project. The table below is not exhaustive.

Table 54. Outputs from liveability impact assessment required as input for other impact areas.

Impact area requiring input	Needed input
Quality of life	Quality of the environment (access to public open spaces, perceived quality of open spaces)
Economic activity and employment	Economic vitality

Overview of approaches and methods

Selecting the right method for evaluating liveability impacts ensures relevant and reliable results. The choice is influenced by the project’s objectives and the resources available to the partners. Additionally, the available tools and data shape the feasibility and effectiveness of different approaches (see Chapter 3.3 for further details).

Table 55 provides an overview of various approaches used in liveability evaluation. It highlights the strengths, weaknesses, and requirements of each method, helping to identify those that best align with the project’s objectives, resources, and specific evaluation aspects. It is important to note that, even when the cons outnumber the pros, one pro can outweigh multiple cons.

Table 55. An overview of approaches and methods for liveability impact assessment.

Approach/method	Pros	Cons	Requirements
Questionnaires	<p>Captures subjective ideas, feelings, and perceptions.</p> <p>Relatively easy, affordable, and flexible.</p> <p>Existing or standard questionnaires can ensure consistency.</p>	<p>Responses can contain subjective, social desirability, and non-response biases.</p> <p>May overlook underlying reasons for responses.</p>	<p>Survey platform or tools.</p> <p>Trained staff for design of questionnaire and analysis.</p> <p>Large pool of respondents.</p>
Focus groups, interviews, expert or stakeholder opinions	<p>Customisable to project needs.</p> <p>Can provide rich, qualitative data.</p>	<p>Time consuming for large or diverse groups.</p>	<p>Trained investigators.</p> <p>Willing participants.</p> <p>Sufficiently large and diverse subject pool.</p>
Multi-criteria analysis (MCA) to weigh different factors into one score	<p>Captures the holistic nature of liveability.</p> <p>Can combine multiple indicators into one score.</p>	<p>Quantifying all measures can be challenging.</p> <p>Difficulty applying appropriate weightings.</p> <p>May create an illusion of precision, as numerical scores and weightings may not fully capture real-world complexities.</p> <p>Result may be hard to communicate to the public.</p>	<p>Comprehensive access to data sources.</p> <p>Expertise in weighting and normalising indicators.</p> <p>Experts on each impact area involved.</p>
Indexation of liveability indicators (e.g. environmental sustainability, public health) over the years	<p>Tracks changes in liveability over time.</p> <p>Provides relative comparisons across selected variables.</p>	<p>Influence of the base year can distort trends.</p> <p>Challenges in obtaining high-quality, long-term input data.</p>	<p>Large scale, reliable data collection.</p> <p>Annualised data to support continuous indexation.</p>
System dynamics modelling	<p>Visualises feedback loops and dynamic changes in the system as variables change.</p>	<p>Complex and difficult to fully conceptualise and visualise.</p> <p>Challenges in obtaining high-quality input data.</p>	<p>Multidisciplinary team developing model.</p> <p>Brainstorming sessions to map system components and dynamics.</p>
Simulation of different areas in terms of liveability	<p>Enables comparison and conceptualisation of future scenarios on a macroscopic scale.</p>	<p>Highly dependent on scenario quality and input data.</p> <p>Developing robust scenarios requires significant effort.</p>	<p>Simulation capabilities and tools.</p> <p>Experts to develop detailed scenarios.</p> <p>High-quality input data for simulations.</p>

Qualitative assessment of community cohesion	Provides in-depth insights into trust, participation and shared identity within the community.	Subjective and may lack quantifiable results. Time-intensive for thorough assessments.	Engagement with community representatives. Structured methodology for qualitative evaluation.
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Pitfalls and best practices

Evaluating liveability impacts requires consideration of the methods and approaches used, as these can significantly influence the validity and reliability of the results. Overlooking potential pitfalls may lead to flawed conclusions, misinterpretation of findings or unintended biases. By proactively addressing the pitfalls, these can be avoided.

Table 56 provides some common pitfalls of liveability evaluation and presents actionable best practices to address them.

Table 56. Pitfalls in evaluation of liveability and best practices to avoid them.

Topic	Pitfall	Related best practice
Weightings of indicator scores	Weightings can heavily influence evaluation outcomes, introducing bias or inconsistency.	Hold stakeholder workshops to agree on appropriate weightings. Benchmark weightings against those used in similar projects.
Indicator availability	Lack of data or poor-quality data can skew liveability evaluations.	Refer to well-established indicators from similar projects. Identify and agree on indicators early in the project and prioritise their collection. Develop a plan for addressing missing data through proxy measures or reasonable assumptions.
Future scenarios	Defining medium- and long-term scenarios for surveys or focus groups may be difficult, as it can be challenging to identify the relevant elements and level of detail needed and to clearly describe the scenarios.	Develop multiple, flexible, and diverse scenarios. Conduct sensitivity analysis to assess how different assumptions about future scenarios affect the results.
Distinguishing CCAM impacts from those caused by other developments	Confounding variables (e.g. policy changes or socio-economic trends) can obscure CCAM-specific impacts, threatening the study's external validity.	Monitor and document external influences (e.g. policy shifts, economic changes) throughout the evaluation period. Apply analytical techniques to control for these confounding variables.

Subjectivity	Stakeholders might have different views on whether changes in indicators are beneficial or detrimental, leading to subjective interpretation of indicators. This can create inconsistencies in evaluations, introduce bias, and compromise the reliability of results, thus threatening the study's internal validity.	Conduct workshops to refine definitions and align stakeholder perspectives. Trial the test indicators and methodologies before final data collection.
Stakeholder engagement	Lack of involvement of key stakeholders can lead to unrealistic assumptions, misalignment with local priorities, or lead to uneven treatment of indicators.	Ensure active involvement of relevant stakeholders throughout the evaluation process. Clearly communicate the specific information needed and provide concise context, while being appreciative of the stakeholder's time constraints.
Over-simplification of liveability metrics	Aggregated scores may oversimplify the complexity of liveability, failing to capture nuanced impacts.	Supplement quantitative metrics with qualitative context. Present disaggregated data where possible to show the underlying dimensions of liveability.

4.4.3. Economic activity and employment

4.4.3.1. Introduction

Definition and scope

EU-CEM defines the economic activity and employment impact area as follows:

The economic activity and employment impact area addresses implications of the CCAM on economic development and labour dynamics by examining its influence on overall economic vitality, on the evolution of businesses and the job market, and on skill requirements of the workforce.

This area studies how CCAM could affect the economy in terms of employment, investment returns and total factor productivity. Changes in these factors have broader economic implications, which are addressed in the socio-economic impact evaluation (Chapter 4.4.4). Additionally, cost-benefit analysis, useful in estimating the optimal allocation of productive resources, is covered there.

Background

Economic activity is commonly measured by gross domestic product (GDP), which represents the total value of goods and services produced within a specific period and region. There are three main approaches for calculating GDP [99]:

- Expenditure approach: Aggregates total spending and investment by households, businesses and governments, along with net exports.
- Income approach: Sums the income generated within the economy, including workers' compensation and operating surplus.
- Output approach: Focuses on gross value added across different industries.

Fluctuations in GDP often reflect changes in productivity [100], which is usually measured as the ratio of GDP to total work hours over a given period. Productivity gains, for example from deployment of new technologies or improved logistics processes, allow the economy to produce more with less, maximising the value of scarce resources like capital and labour.

Economic activity and employment are linked, but their relationship is complex. Different economic theories aim to explain how jobs affect economic activities. For example, the *Keynesian theory*, developed in the 1930s by John Maynard Keynes [101], asserts that aggregate demand—the sum of household, business, and government spending—is the main force driving the economy. According to the theory, government spending is necessary to maintain full employment, and employed people (labour) have money to spend on goods and services, stimulating businesses to grow and create more jobs.

CCAM can impact economic activity across multiple industries, including:

- Automotive: Increased demand for CCAM vehicles sales.
- Software: Growth in development and integration of self-driving software.
- Data services: Expansion of data-driven revenue streams from CCAM systems.
- Telecommunications: Higher revenues due to increased connectivity requirements and data exchanges.

Other affected industries include vehicle and infrastructure maintenance, insurance, education, and medicine [102]. CCAM may also indirectly affect economic activity through the (re)allocation of productive resources of labour, capital and freed-up time. For example, fewer accidents would reduce the need for healthcare and vehicle repairs. These freed-up resources could then be reinvested into the economy or society.

Job markets could be impacted in several ways. Automation of vehicles might reduce or eliminate the need for drivers in certain roles or for specific segments of trips. However, CCAM can improve drivers' working conditions by relieving them of monotonous tasks, reducing stress and enhancing safety. Further, as some roles disappear, the remaining jobs and skill requirements are expected to undergo restructuring. Workers may need to develop new skill sets, such as overseeing automated systems, managing fleet operations or handling vehicle monitoring and maintenance.

At the same time, CCAM can create new jobs across various sectors. New roles will emerge in CCAM system development and design, particularly in manufacturing, construction, and related industries where the demand for more advanced vehicles and components drives job growth [103]. Additionally, the provision and operation of CCAM services could create new jobs in areas such as maintenance and management services. Employment opportunities in information technology, particularly software development, are also expected to grow rapidly to support the development, integration, and ongoing maintenance of CCAM systems.

In passenger transport, CCAM systems may require traffic managers with updated skill sets to ensure safe and smooth road traffic. New fleet or service operators may emerge to provide customer service and on-board safety supervision, and control centres might also require more employees for both passenger and freight transport.

In the insurance sector, new jobs are anticipated due to the emergence of new insurance classes for CCAM systems. The introduction of CCAM will require new insurance policies, resulting from product liability for CCAM hardware and software, as well as new cybersecurity risks (e.g. hijacking of vehicle controls) and infrastructure risks (e.g. cloud server malfunctions).

Additionally, increased connectivity of CCAM vehicles will create jobs in telecommunications, data management, and digital media services. Large amounts of data flowing between devices and infrastructure may lead to increased demand for specialists in these fields.

Figure 38 shows the main components of the economic activity and employment impact area.

Figure 38. Main components of the economic activity and employment impact area.

4.4.3.2. Guidelines

Indicator recommendations

Result indicators recommended to be evaluated by every project addressing the impacts of CCAM on economic activity and employment are listed in Table 57 below. Impacts are differences/changes between the baseline and treatment scenarios in these indicators. An impact can be reported as an absolute value (with unit below) or relative value (%). If it is not possible to evaluate some of the indicators below, the reason for this should be reported as part of the ‘comply or explain’ principle of the EU-CEM. The indicators listed below are not exhaustive; in addition to these, each project should define indicators of their own in accordance with Guideline 3.12.

Table 57. Indicators recommended to be evaluated by every project addressing impacts on economic activity and employment.

Indicator short name	Definition	Unit
Gross Domestic Product (GDP)	The total monetary value of all the goods and services produced within a specific region and period.	€
Productivity	Economic efficiency of goods or services production, calculated as output per unit of labour. For example, GDP divided by total hours worked over a given period.	€/h

Number of jobs	An indicator reflecting employment dynamics, including job creation, loss, retention, and transformation. Can be disaggregated by sector or industry.	-
Number of businesses	The total count of businesses operating within each sector or industry.	-
Labour market demand for skills	Assessment of workforce skill requirements due to CCAM, including shifts in the demand for different skill profiles and professional roles.	Number or qualitative assessment

Impact pathways

Impact pathways illustrate how changes caused by CCAM, and assessed in other impact areas, affect the outcomes of this impact area. Mapping these cause-and-effect relationships helps scope the evaluation by grounding it in established theories or empirical findings. It clarifies how localised effects can escalate to larger scale impacts, shows whether one area influences another, and reveals how these changes ripple through vehicles, individuals, the transport system and beyond. Using these pathways can help identify where additional information is needed or where collaboration is required with other impact areas, or to ascertain whether certain aspects fall outside the assessment.

Economic activity and employment is influenced by impacts on land use (Chapter 4.4.1), socio-economics (Chapter 4.4.4), accessibility (Chapter 4.3.7), liveability (Chapter 4.4.2), services and operation (Chapter 4.3.1), people mobility (Chapter 4.2.2), and logistics (Chapter 4.3.2). This is depicted in the impact pathways below in Figure 39. The figure offers a general overview that can be adapted or extended to specific CCAM systems studied. Each project should tailor it by specifying relevant indicators and units.

Figure 39. Input needed from the other impact areas for economic activity and employment impact assessment and its outputs.

Table 58 provides examples of outputs of the economic activity and employment impact assessment that serve as inputs for other impact areas. Some of these outputs overlap with the recommended indicators listed above, while others must be additionally considered. Please note that the required input needs must be specified in detail, as they are unique to each project. The table below is not exhaustive.

Table 58. Outputs from economic activity and employment impact assessment required as input for other impact areas.

Impact area requiring input	Needed input
People mobility	Economy: Demand for travel
Logistics	Economy: Demand for goods transport
Land use	Number of jobs and businesses per area
Socio-economics	Employment, yield of investments

Overview of approaches and methods

Selecting the right method for evaluating economic activity and employment impacts ensures relevant and reliable results. The choice is influenced by the project's objectives and the resources available to the partners. Additionally, the available tools and data shape the feasibility and effectiveness of different approaches (see Chapter 3.3 for further details).

Table 59 provides an overview of various approaches used in economic activity and employment evaluations. It highlights the strengths, weaknesses, and requirements of each method, helping to identify those that best align with the project’s objectives, resources, and specific evaluation aspects. It is important to note that, even when the cons outnumber the pros, one pro can outweigh multiple cons.

Table 59. An overview of approaches and methods for evaluation of economic activity and employment.

Approach/method	Pros	Cons	Requirements
Focus groups for CCAM developers or operators	<p>Provides qualitative estimates on the expected impacts, including job creation and loss due to CCAM.</p> <p>Identifies specific job roles and industry demands due to CCAM.</p>	<p>May lack sufficient information to determine realistic scenarios or to make accurate estimates.</p> <p>Results depend on the diversity and expertise of participants.</p>	<p>Balance between fewer, in-depth groups with extended discussions, and more, shorter sessions to reach a larger number of participants.</p> <p>Structured facilitation and expert moderation.</p>
Modelling change in GDP or jobs, e.g. with system dynamics	<p>Cost- and time-efficient.</p> <p>Allows evaluation in controlled environment.</p>	<p>Accuracy depends on model accuracy, assumptions, and input data.</p>	<p>Selection of model appropriate for the research question.</p> <p>Availability of reliable input data for calibration.</p>
Ceteris Paribus analysis	<p>Cause-and-effect economic analysis to isolate the impact of specific CCAM-related variables.</p> <p>Allows testing of how changes in one economic variable (e.g. automation adoption) affect another (e.g. employment levels) while holding all other factors constant.</p>	<p>Ignores the complexity of human behaviour and broader economic interactions.</p> <p>Difficult to account for all possible independent variables affecting economic trends.</p>	<p>Expertise in economic modelling and statistical techniques.</p> <p>Clearly defined assumptions and variables.</p>
Input-output analysis	<p>Shows input required from specific sectors to produce one unit of CCAM services.</p> <p>Able to capture interdependencies and feedback loops.</p> <p>Simulates the effects of changes in demand, supply or pricing.</p> <p>Identifies key sectors driving economic vitality, employment and added value.</p> <p>Assesses whether new job creation offsets job displacement.</p>	<p>Requires large datasets and detailed assumptions, which may not be available or reliable.</p> <p>Assumes a fixed and linear relationship between inputs and outputs.</p> <p>Oversimplifies economic dynamics.</p> <p>Does not account for market mechanisms like competition or technological disruption.</p>	<p>Specification of sectoral outputs flows (i.e. how industries interact and contribute to CCAM-related services).</p> <p>Access to suitable economic datasets.</p>

Pitfalls and best practices

Evaluating impacts on economic activity and employment requires consideration of the methods and approaches used, as these can significantly influence the validity and reliability of the results. Overlooking potential pitfalls may lead to flawed conclusions, misinterpretation of findings or unintended biases. By proactively addressing the pitfalls, these can be avoided.

Table 60 provides some common pitfalls of economic activity and employment impact assessment and presents actionable best practices to address them.

Table 60. Pitfalls in economic activity and employment impact assessment and best practices to avoid them.

Topic	Pitfall	Related best practice
Focus groups	The focus groups do not adequately represent all key stakeholders, leading to incomplete assessment of impacts.	Recruiting representative focus groups: Clearly identify the key stakeholders whose employment and profitability may be affected. Ensure diverse representation across industries, skill level and roles.
Use of modelling tools	Different economic models produce conflicting results, leading to uncertainty in assessment.	Use simulation tools specifically developed for studying changes in GDP and job creation/loss. Validate models against real-world data and ensure assumptions are clearly defined.
Digitalisation	The impact of CCAM may be difficult to separate from the parallel impacts of digitalisation on mobility.	Be transparent and explicitly document which aspects of overall digitalisation are addressed in the CCAM evaluation and which are excluded.

4.4.4. Socio-economics

4.4.4.1. Introduction

Definition and scope

EU-CEM defines the socio-economic impact area as follows:

Socio-economic impact assessment addresses the economic and societal implications of CCAM, integrating and quantifying its diverse impacts as benefits and costs in order to assess its societal and economic value.

This area assesses the effects of CCAM on societal welfare²⁵ by quantifying monetary values for both costs and societal benefits across various impact areas, such as traffic safety (Chapter 4.3.4), traffic flow efficiency (Chapter 4.3.5), and environmental impacts (Chapter 4.3.6) [13]. These values provide a basis for evaluating CCAM's overall contribution to society and its stakeholders. While CCAM can generate benefits, some of these may also result in negative outcomes, referred to as disbenefits.²⁶

²⁵ In socio-economic impact assessment, the term 'welfare' refers to financial and societal needs of population, combining material and non-material aspects.

²⁶ In socio-economic impact assessment, also the disbenefits are addressed under the term "benefits".

The distribution of welfare impacts, in terms of assessing how benefits and costs may be distributed between population groups, regions or time periods, is covered in the equity impact area (Chapter 4.4.5).

Background

Socio-economic assessment focuses on how CCAM affects welfare. Welfare can be analysed from societal and stakeholder perspectives, but these analyses must be treated separately, as the magnitude of impacts and the unit costs estimating their economic value differ between the two.

Welfare (or utility) is derived from consumption of goods and services, leisure and well-being [10][13]. Mobility contributes to welfare, for example via accessibility, but it also incurs costs. These costs are categorised as:

- Direct costs, such as fuel expenses and road toll fees.
- Indirect costs, such as travel or delivery time.

Transport technologies, such as CCAM, can impact welfare by affecting travel costs, traffic flow efficiency, the environment, and other factors. The core task of socio-economic impact assessment is to estimate the societal value of all expected impacts of CCAM. Whenever possible, this societal value is expressed in monetary terms, while non-quantifiable impacts are assessed qualitatively.

The focus is on the net welfare impacts of CCAM for the society, comparing the benefits (including disbenefits) that result from CCAM with the costs it incurs (Figure 40). For example, a study of SAE level 3 automated passenger cars found that welfare impacts were mainly derived from expected reductions in traffic accidents and from a lower unit cost of travel time [13].

Figure 40. Main components of the socio-economic impact area.

Cost-benefit analysis (CBA) systematically estimates the expected costs and benefits of CCAM compared to a baseline scenario without CCAM. It assesses welfare impacts by multiplying the expected change in each impact type by standard unit costs, which reflect the welfare effect of a one-unit change for that impact type. CBA consolidates all these welfare impacts into an overall evaluation, summarised as either a net benefit (in EUR) or a benefit-cost ratio (BCR).

Based on welfare economics principles, CBA is commonly used to determine societal beneficialness. Socio-economic evaluations typically construct scenarios for a system’s entire lifespan. Alternatively, a snapshot approach [13] may be used, where the system is evaluated for a specific year or time period, when all its impacts have materialised at a chosen or predicted CCAM penetration or usage rate. This snapshot is then compared with a baseline societal scenario for the same period without the system, assuming a steady-state society and holding all other factors constant.

Although standard unit costs are essential for determining the monetary value of impacts, no authoritative source universally defines which unit costs to use. National-level recommendations exist, but the methods for estimating these costs vary significantly between countries. Therefore, the basis for selecting unit costs and applied values must be well documented. These costs differ based on impact type and whether the analysis considers the overall society or specific stakeholder groups. [13]

4.4.4.2. Guidelines

Indicator recommendations

Result indicators recommended to be evaluated by each project addressing the socio-economic impact are listed in Table 61 below. If it is not possible to evaluate some of the indicators below, the reason for this should be reported as part of the ‘comply or explain’ principle of the EU-CEM. The indicators listed below are not exhaustive; in addition to these, each project should define indicators of their own in accordance with Guideline 3.12.

Table 61. Indicators recommended to be evaluated by each project addressing the socio-economic impact.

Indicator short name	Definition	Unit
Monetised benefits	Total monetary value per type of impact (benefit), as used in CBA.	€
Societal cost	Total societal cost, as used in CBA.	€
Benefit-cost ratio (BCR)	Total monetised impact (benefit) to society divided by the total societal cost, as used in CBA.	-
Net benefit	Total monetised impact (benefit) subtracted by total societal costs.	€
Net present value (NPV)	Discounted total monetised impacts minus discounted costs over a specified period of time.	€

Impact pathways

Impact pathways illustrate how changes caused by CCAM, and assessed in other impact areas, affect the outcomes of this impact area. Mapping these cause-and-effect relationships helps scope the evaluation by grounding it in established theories or empirical findings. It clarifies how localised effects can escalate to larger scale impacts, shows whether one area influences another and reveals how these changes ripple through vehicles, individuals, the transport system and beyond. Using these pathways can help identify where additional

information is needed or where collaboration is required with other impact areas, or to ascertain whether certain aspects fall outside the scope of the assessment.

Socio-economic impact is influenced by the impact of CCAM on traffic safety (Chapter 4.3.4), traffic flow efficiency (Chapter 4.3.5), energy and environment (Chapter 4.3.6), as well as economic activity and employment (Chapter 4.4.3). This is depicted in the impact pathway below (Figure 41). The figure offers a general overview that can be adapted or extended to specific CCAM systems studied. Each project should tailor it by specifying relevant indicators and units.

Figure 41. Input needed from the other impact areas for socio-economic impact assessment and its outputs.

Overview of approaches and methods

Selecting the right method for evaluating socio-economic impacts ensures relevant and reliable results. The choice is influenced by the project’s objectives and resources available to the partners. Additionally, the available tools and data shape the feasibility and effectiveness of different approaches (see Chapter 3.3 for further details).

Table 62 provides an overview of various approaches used in socio-economic evaluations. It highlights the strengths, weaknesses, and requirements of each method, helping to identify those that best align with the project’s objectives, resources, and specific evaluation aspects. It is important to note that, even when the cons outnumber the pros, one pro can outweigh multiple cons. More information on cost-benefit analysis is provided after the overview table.

Table 62. An overview of approaches and methods for socio-economic impact assessment.

Approach/method	Pros	Cons	Requirements
Cost-benefit analysis (CBA)	<p>Provides a clear comparison on whether costs outweigh benefits.</p> <p>Easy to compare socio-economic feasibility of services or alternative scenarios.</p>	<p>Not all impacts can be monetised, introducing uncertainty in the results.</p> <p>Reliably estimating implementation costs for future technologies is challenging.</p> <p>Predicting widescale deployment timelines for CCAM systems is difficult.</p> <p>CCAM is not the only changing factor in transport, making it challenging to isolate its impacts.</p>	<p>Comprehensive identification and quantification of all relevant costs and benefits.</p> <p>Sensitivity analysis to account for uncertainty in estimates and assumptions.</p>
Unit cost estimation	<p>Shared values allow comparability between different evaluations.</p>	<p>No well-established EU-wide methods for developing unit costs for impacts.</p> <p>Challenging to develop unit cost for the general welfare impacts of CCAM.</p>	<p>Transparent documentation of standard unit costs used and the basis for their selection.</p>
Willingness-to-pay (WTP) evaluation	<p>Allows assessing economic implications without requiring unit cost.</p>	<p>Potentially weak correlation with real-world behaviour and actual willingness to pay.</p>	<p>Expertise in formulating the questions and interpreting the responses.</p>
CBA by stakeholder type	<p>Enables evaluation of welfare effects per stakeholder group.</p> <p>Supports equity impact assessment.</p>	<p>Increases the complexity of impact assessment for other areas.</p> <p>Requires stakeholder type-specific unit costs, which may be challenging to estimate.</p>	<p>Identification of how impacts are distributed across stakeholders.</p> <p>Stakeholder group-specific unit costs must reflect financial effects accurately.</p>
Multi-criteria analysis (MCA)	<p>Provides a structured approach to determining overall preferences among alternatives.</p> <p>Can incorporate qualitative results and impacts without unit costs.</p>	<p>Strongly depends on expert judgement, which can introduce subjectivity.</p> <p>Quantifying all measures and applying appropriate weighting can be challenging.</p> <p>May create an illusion of precision, as numerical scores and weightings may not fully capture real-world complexities.</p> <p>Results may be difficult to communicate to the general public in a clear and transparent way.</p>	<p>Clearly defined evaluation objectives.</p> <p>Expertise in MCA.</p> <p>Relevant experts in all related areas.</p>

The structure of conducting CBA:

1. **Select the approach and societal scenarios:** Determine whether to use a snapshot or a full-lifespan approach, and clearly define the baseline and treatment societal scenarios for the impact assessment.
2. **Collect scaled-up impact results:** Gather both quantitative and qualitative results from different impact areas, ensuring consistency in societal scenarios, penetration rate, region and baseline assumptions.
3. **Apply unit costs:** Estimate the monetary value of the impacts by applying well-documented unit cost values appropriate for the impact type and perspective (societal or stakeholder-specific).
4. **Determine CCAM system costs:** Account for production, maintenance, investments and operational expenses.
5. **Calculate the benefit-cost ratio:** Compute the net benefit relative to costs using the quantified results, supplemented by an analysis of the qualitative results from a socio-economic perspective.

Pitfalls and best practices

Evaluating the socio-economic impacts of CCAM requires consideration of the methods and approaches used, as these can significantly influence the validity and reliability of the results. Overlooking potential pitfalls may lead to flawed conclusions, misinterpretation of findings or unintended biases. By proactively addressing the pitfalls, these can be avoided.

Table 63 provides some common pitfalls of socio-economic impact assessment and presents actionable best practices to address them.

Table 63. Pitfalls in socio-economic impact assessment and best practices to avoid them.

Topic	Pitfall	Related best practice
Lack of reliable cost estimates for CCAM	Uncertainty in cost estimates for automated vehicles, their operation, and infrastructure may compromise the validity of the analysis.	Conduct interviews or Delphi studies with CCAM developers, infrastructure owners and industry experts to improve estimates.
Benefits are not scaled up	Benefits derived for a small scale are not scaled up to the larger region or time scale addressed by the socio-economic impact assessment.	Design the impact assessment across all impact areas to allow for scaling up. Impacts defined per quantifiable unit relevant to the target region and timeframe.
Mismatch between impact areas	Different impact areas develop scenarios independently, leading to inconsistencies with the societal scenario set for socio-economic impact assessment.	Define societal scenarios first, ensuring that all impact areas align with them. Each impact area should build scenarios that are compatible with the agreed societal scenario used for socio-economic impact assessment (see Chapter 3.3).
No standard unit cost available	Some major impacts of CCAM lack standard unit costs.	Use an appropriate socio-economic assessment method that allows the inclusion of all impacts, including those lacking predefined unit costs or assessed qualitatively. Clearly document the unit costs applied and the basis for their selection.

Different unit costs by country	Unit costs vary by country, leading to inconsistent benefit values based on location.	Use EU-level unit costs where possible to allow equal consideration of benefits across countries.
CBA focuses only on quantifiable costs and benefits	CBA primarily focuses on quantifiable costs and benefits, overlooking psychological factors that can significantly influence decision-making.	Use complementary methods to capture psychological and qualitative factors that cannot be quantified in CBA.

4.4.5. Equity

4.4.5.1. Introduction

Definition and scope

EU-CEM defines the equity impact area as follows:

The equity impact area addresses the fairness, impartiality, and inclusivity of the CCAM by examining how impacts are distributed across different population groups, regions, or generations.

The distribution of CCAM’s potential benefits and burdens can vary across demographic groups, geographical areas, and time periods. For example, the impacts experienced today may differ from those that will affect future generations. Identifying these disparities is important for determining whether CCAM’s impacts can be considered equitably distributed.

Equity refers to the consistent and systematic fair and just treatment [104] of all individuals, recognising that people have different needs and require different levels of support and resources to ensure their rights are realised [105]. This includes individuals from underserved communities historically excluded from such considerations.

Equity must not be confused with equality, as the two concepts address fairness in different ways:

- Equity acknowledges that individuals do not start from the same position and require adjustments to address these imbalances.
- Equality, by contrast, provides the same resources and opportunities to everyone, regardless of their circumstances [106] or starting position.
- Justice ensures long-term equity by dismantling systemic barriers and addressing the root causes of inequity, creating sustainable and just solutions for future generations.

Figure 42 illustrates the differences between equality, equity, and justice.

Figure 42. Equality, equity, and justice.

The focus of this impact area is on the distribution of impacts, extending beyond the average impact across an entire society or nation. The disparities used in this impact area are:

- **Population group disparities** happen when impacts are not evenly distributed. Some groups may experience greater benefits, while others face more burdens than others. Examples include different groups differentiated by age, income, gender, (dis)abilities, technology access, digital literacy and adoption of CCAM, etc.
- **Regional disparities** can arise from factors such as CCAM service areas, the location of labour markets, and the areas where materials are sourced for constructing these systems. Considerations include whether production and operations are conducted sustainably and whether the benefits are equitably shared across locations.
- **Temporal disparities** occur when decisions made today produce different outcomes over time. For example, variations in material usage, infrastructure changes, and emissions (e.g. climate change) may impact current populations differently than future generations.

This chapter focuses on the main components of equity in CCAM (see Figure 43):

- Distribution effects among population groups (e.g. based on income, age or (dis)abilities).
- Distribution effects among regions (e.g. urban, sub-urban, and rural areas or countries).
- Distribution effects across time periods (e.g. present-day vs. future generations, intergenerational justice).
- Identification of disparities between population groups by examining the factors that distinguish affected populations.

Figure 43. Main components of the equity impact area.

Background

The success of CCAM depends not only on technological capabilities but also on societal acceptance and inclusion of diverse travellers. Europe’s rich regional diversity and varied population demographics, each with distinct travel needs, present both opportunities and challenges. CCAM has the potential to enhance mobility for all, including vulnerable and less mobile travellers.

However, if CCAM is primarily designed and deployed in regions with already diverse mobility options or tailored mainly for majority populations, the benefits may not be distributed equitably [107]. The distribution of the benefits and costs, through direct or indirect effects, can differ between groups and regions. Ignoring equity aspects risks marginalising disadvantaged populations and reinforcing existing inequalities [108]. The challenge lies in equitably aligning CCAM travel demand, different needs, and the available travel options across different demographic segments.

An equitable future envisions a mobility offering that improves accessibility for those who most need it, rather than only benefitting those who already have high levels of accessibility. Focusing solely on *doing things right* from one perspective—optimising systems for speed, capacity, cost or profit—can risk overlooking marginalised groups or even displacing them from urban spaces. In contrast, *doing the right things*—designing CCAM systems that actively address disparities—can lead to a more just and equitable distribution of benefits [109].

There is a growing focus among society, policymakers, and academia on the relationship between transportation, equity, and well-being. The United Nations’ Sustainable Development Goals (SDG), a collection of seventeen interlinked objectives, serve as a “shared blueprint for peace and prosperity for people and the planet, now and into the future.” [110] These goals call upon all United Nations Member States to work together to reduce inequalities.

Inequitable accessibility can result in social exclusion. Transport poverty, where people cannot reach essential activities or locations [111], limits their societal participation [112]. Equitable access to mobility, allowing them to reach more (or relevant to the particular group) activities, would improve their well-being [113]. Distribution of benefits and costs can, therefore, directly influence the quality of life (see Chapter 4.2.3).

There are several perspectives on justice and distribution:

- Utilitarianism: Seeks to maximise overall utility or societal benefit.
- Egalitarianism: Seeks to minimise inequalities between groups.
- Sufficientarianism: Seeks to ensure every individual achieves a minimum level of accessibility.
- Limitarianism: Seeks to set limits on extreme levels of wealth or, in the context of mobility, restricts extreme levels of mobility and their associated effects.

It is important to identify the role of CCAM in promoting equity. Using accessibility as an example, should CCAM:

- Increase accessibility for society as a whole?
- Prioritise disadvantaged groups with the lowest levels of accessibility?
- Ensure a minimum level of accessibility for everyone?

Without a clear focus on equity, CCAM risks widening existing disparities instead of reducing them, benefiting those with already high accessibility while neglecting those with low accessibility.

4.4.5.2. Guidelines

The impacts of CCAM vary across population groups, regions, and time periods. Understanding these variations when assessing equity impacts of CCAM requires examining the factors that influence how these impacts are distributed.

Population group

Differences in socio-demographic factors (age, income, health), as well as psychological, activity-related, and accessibility factors, can cause CCAM to affect various population groups differently. Additionally, users and non-users of CCAM may experience distinct advantages and disadvantages, as some individuals may be unwilling or unable to adopt the technology due to cost, digital literacy or accessibility barriers.

Regional dimension

Regional characteristics—such as infrastructure quality, availability of public transport, urban design, traffic volumes, housing types, connectivity, and even climate—play an important role in shaping both the deployment of CCAM and its beneficiaries. Moreover, the composition of population groups is often closely linked to regional typologies, whether high-density urban, suburban or rural, which further influences mobility needs. Decisions made in one region, such as deploying CCAM vehicles, can have far-reaching consequences elsewhere; the extraction of raw materials for CCAM vehicles may disproportionately affect the regions where these materials are mined.

Temporal dimension

The effects of CCAM are not limited to the present; decisions made today can have lasting consequences for future generations. Intergenerational equity concerns may persist if policies continue to neglect the needs of underserved groups, potentially exacerbating long-term inequalities. For example, climate change and emission reduction actions influence both regional and temporal dimensions, as their impacts are unevenly distributed among different population groups and regions and across generations.

In summary, multiple dimensions shape how CCAM impacts society. Table 64 categorises these dimensions and their associated factors for consideration when assessing equity impacts of CCAM, depending on the project’s aim, scope, and research questions. All of these factors may vary across regions and change over time, meaning that impacts of CCAM may vary as well.

Table 64. Factors of different dimensions of equity [114]. All of the factors in the table may vary across regions and change over time.

Dimensions	Factors
Population groups — Socio-demographics	Income, age, gender, household type, (dis)abilities, health, education, ethnicity, employment status, type of work (occupation), socio-economic status, travel capabilities, technology access and digital literacy, lifestyle, family situation.
Population groups — Access to mobility and equipment	Availability and ownership of transport modes, availability of mobility-related equipment and facilities, accessibility for people with mobility impairments (e.g. wheelchair, guide dog), driving licence, mobility subscriptions, subsidised or discounted mobility options, travel expenses, travel time, quality of transport services.
Population groups — Activity factors	Type of activity, location of activity, distance to activity/locations, amount/frequency of activities, discretionary vs. non-discretionary travel purposes, travel mode, timing of travel, amount/frequency of trips, trip length.
Population groups — Psychological factors	Satisfaction with mode, satisfaction with journey, attitude toward modes, attitude toward journey, general attitude in life, perceived safety, social norms and values.
Population groups — Geographical factors	Type of area (urban, suburban, rural), distance to activities, population density and land use distribution, presence of facilities, spatial characteristics, quality of the environment.
Regional dimension — Regional factors	Infrastructure, type and quality of roads and infrastructure, availability and accessibility of public transport, network layout, facilities, spatial design, traffic volumes, shares of housing types, population density, dedicated lanes (e.g. cycling lanes, public transport), share of travel modes present, digital connectivity, climate.

Indicator recommendations

No predefined set of equity-specific indicators is recommended for all projects addressing this impact area. Instead, equity in CCAM is best assessed using indicators available from other impact areas, to ensure that impact disparities of CCAM are captured accurately across different population groups, regions, and time periods.

While there are some equity-specific indicators, their applicability depends on the project’s goals, data availability, and the specific equity concerns relevant to the selected impact areas. For example, for economic aspects, the project might use the Gini coefficient, a well-established statistical measure of income, wealth or consumption inequality within a population.

Rather than relying on a predefined set of equity-specific indicators, it is recommended to assess equity impacts by disaggregating indicators from other impact areas to detect the disparities in CCAM impacts. The extent to which equity impacts of CCAM can be assessed depends on data availability and the granularity of the group distinctions. For instance, values of indicators related to traffic safety, people mobility or quality of life may differ

across specific groups, regions, or time periods, and these differences may remain concealed if not assessed separately.

For example:

- The average accessibility may increase due to a new CCAM service at the population level, but a more detailed analysis could reveal large differences in accessibility gains between groups.
- Impacts may be different for users and non-users of CCAM within the same region and time period.
 - Example: Users of robotaxis (e.g. adults without a driver’s licence, older adults, mobility-impaired travellers) may experience higher levels of accessibility. However, non-users like cyclists and pedestrians might face increased traffic volumes, resulting in reduced traffic safety and more stressful trips.

Table 65 presents examples of how the equity perspective of different indicators can be assessed.

Table 65. Examples of equity impact assessment for different indicators.

Impact area	Indicator short name	Equity assessment examples
User	User experience	How does the CCAM user experience differ across population groups? Are there differences based on age, digital skills, physical impairments or other demographic factors?
	Acceptance	How does acceptance of CCAM vary across different population groups? Does the perceived safety of shared robotaxis (rides shared with strangers) differ based on gender, age, disability or income levels?
	Experiences of non-users	How do non-users perceive and experience CCAM’s direct and indirect effects? Consider other road users (e.g. conventional car users, cyclists, pedestrians) and non-road users (e.g. residents, business owners).
People mobility	Mode share	Is CCAM equally available to all population groups? Consider factors like driver’s licence or other mode use requirements, affordability and physical accessibility, as well as regional variations in availability of travel modes and public transport level of service.
Traffic safety	Road injuries or injury accidents	Do traffic safety impacts differ between groups, such as CCAM users vs. non-users (e.g. conventional car users, cyclists, pedestrians)? How do safety impacts differ by road type (urban, suburban, rural)?
Accessibility	Reachable activities	How does the accessibility provided by CCAM to key locations (e.g. jobs, education, healthcare) vary among population groups and different regions?
	Understandability of mobility options	Do all groups have equal access to CCAM, or does it require specific devices (e.g. smartphones) or digital proficiency to use them?
Energy and environment	CO ₂ emissions	How do the effects on climate change (affected by CCAM’s emission impact) affect different population groups and regions over time? How are future generations affected?

	Air quality or noise exposure	How are the effects of CCAM on air quality or noise pollution distributed between regions and population groups?
Land use	Housing and land prices	How does CCAM affect housing and land prices across regions? How do these changes affect living expenses, considering median incomes?
Economic activity and employment	Number of jobs	How are CCAM-related job gains and losses distributed across regions? Are certain occupations or demographics (e.g. low-skilled vs. high-skilled workers) disproportionately affected?
Socio-economics	Benefit-to-cost ratio	Do the benefits and costs of CCAM disproportionately affect certain population groups, regions or time periods? Are economic gains and burdens evenly distributed?

Impact pathways

Impact pathways illustrate how changes caused by CCAM, and assessed in other impact areas, affect the outcomes of this impact area. Mapping these cause-and-effect relationships helps scope the evaluation by grounding it in established theories or empirical findings. It clarifies how localised effects can escalate to larger scale impacts, shows whether one area influences another, and reveals how these changes ripple through vehicles, individuals, the transport system and beyond. Using these pathways can help identify where additional information is needed or where collaboration is required with other impact areas, or to ascertain whether certain aspects fall outside the scope of the assessment.

Equity is influenced by different impact areas at the human (Chapter 4.2), transport system (Chapter 4.3), and society (Chapter 4.4) levels. The figure offers a starting point that can be tailored to the specific CCAM systems under study by specifying relevant indicators and units.

Figure 44. Input needed for the equity impact assessment and its output.

Overview of approaches and methods

Selecting the right method ensures relevant and reliable results. The choice is influenced by the project’s objectives and the resources available to partners. Additionally, the available tools and data shape the feasibility and effectiveness of different approaches (see Chapter 3.3 for further details).

Disaggregation of input impacts is usually necessary to identify target groups. This allows for the assessment of equity impacts for specific groups or regions regarding the benefits and burdens of CCAM. The methods described in Table 66 can be used in this process. The table highlights the strengths, weaknesses, and requirements of each method, helping to identify those that best align with the project’s objectives, resources, and specific evaluation aspects. It is important to note that, even when the cons outnumber the pros, one pro can outweigh multiple cons.

Table 66. An overview of approaches and methods for equity impact assessment.

Approach/method	Pros	Cons	Requirements
Questionnaires to equity experts and population group representatives	<p>Allows for both qualitative and quantitative data collection.</p> <p>Can be integrated with real-world experiments for direct observation.</p> <p>Enables identification of specific population</p>	<p>Results depend on how well the respondents are selected.</p> <p>Time consuming to construct and pilot a questionnaire.</p>	<p>Expertise in designing questionnaires.</p> <p>Carefully designed questions and response options that represent real-life situations and prevent bias.</p> <p>Clear identification of all relevant stakeholders.</p>

	groups, regions and time periods that should be considered in equity impact assessment.		Data collection strategy should allow distinguishing between subgroups.
Interviews with equity experts or population group representatives (e.g. non-governmental organisations and associations)	<p>Can be customised to project needs.</p> <p>Allows for qualitative in-depth insights on affected populations.</p> <p>Allows for open-ended discussion capturing rich contextual details.</p>	<p>Availability of relevant experts or representatives.</p> <p>Representativeness can be a challenge, limiting generalisability.</p> <p>Responses may be influenced by interviewer bias.</p> <p>Different groups can have conflicting viewpoints.</p>	<p>Identification and selection strategy for participants.</p> <p>Willingness to participate among respondents.</p> <p>Trained interviewers to minimise bias and ensure consistency.</p>
Demographic analysis (using socio-economic and demographic statistics for a specific region)	<p>May reveal large-scale trends across population groups.</p> <p>Historical and comparative data.</p> <p>Allows for comparison with national or regional averages.</p>	<p>Demographic information may oversimplify population differences.</p> <p>Does not capture individual mobility needs.</p> <p>Data may be outdated or not detailed enough for equity-specific insights.</p>	<p>Availability of detailed and up-to-date demographic statistics covering multiple socio-economic factors.</p> <p>Access to data disaggregated by population groups, regions or mobility characteristics.</p>
Indicators as descriptors of distribution (e.g. identification of population groups, regions or time periods with value within the lowest and highest 10% for an impact indicator)	<p>Simple, cost-effective, and uses existing indicators.</p> <p>Highlights inequalities between groups, regions or time periods.</p> <p>Can expose extreme disparities not visible in overall averages.</p>	<p>Focusing only on extremes, potentially missing inequities among mid-range groups.</p> <p>Does not explain causes of inequalities, only shows where differences exist.</p> <p>Requires granular and disaggregated data.</p>	<p>Selection of relevant indicators.</p> <p>Availability of detailed disaggregated data by population group, region or time period.</p>
Gini coefficient/index [115] (a statistical benchmark for economic inequality across a population)	<p>Widely used benchmark for analysing economic inequalities.</p> <p>Useful for comparing inequality across regions or time periods.</p>	<p>May overstate actual income inequality or fail to differentiate between income distributions with identical Gini values.</p> <p>Does not account for differences in absolute income levels or</p>	<p>Reliable and up-to-date GDP and income distribution data, preferably disaggregated by population groups and regions.</p>

		structural mobility barriers.	
Palma ratio [116] (Ratio of the top 10% of households' income to the bottom 40%)	Useful for analysing economic inequality and wealth distribution. Places more emphasis on disparities affecting lower-income populations compared with the Gini coefficient.	Similarly to the Gini coefficient, it may not capture absolute income levels. Countries may have identical Palma ratios while having vastly different poverty levels. Requires high-quality income data across income deciles.	Reliable and up-to-date income data, preferably disaggregated by population groups and regions.

Pitfalls and best practices

Evaluating equity impacts requires consideration of the methods and approaches used, as these can significantly influence the validity and reliability of the results. Overlooking potential pitfalls may lead to flawed conclusions, misinterpretation of findings or unintended biases. By proactively addressing the pitfalls, these can be avoided.

Table 67 provides some common pitfalls of equity impact assessment and presents actionable best practices to address them.

Table 67. Pitfalls in equity impact assessment and best practices to avoid them.

Topic	Pitfall	Related best practice
Target group(s)	Target group(s) are not correctly identified or sufficiently represented, leading to biased assessment of CCAM impacts.	Reserve sufficient time and resources for target group identification and engaging underrepresented groups in research and pilot studies. Use diverse recruitment strategies to ensure broad participation.
Data	Unavailability of disaggregated data on target groups or regions, making it difficult to assess equity impacts accurately.	Check the availability of disaggregated data on target groups or regions early on in the project, collect which factors are important and what this means for data collection. Identify key factors early in the project and plan data collection accordingly. Reserve sufficient time and resources for acquiring required data. Ensure access to relevant demographic, socio-economic, and mobility data. If possible, use available data from similar regions or groups.
Distribution effects	Social and geographical distribution effects are misrepresented, leading to unrealistic assessment of CCAM's benefits and disadvantages.	Conduct a thorough analysis of direct and indirect impacts, considering differences across populations groups, regions, and time periods. Use spatial and demographic data to model realistic distribution patterns. Clearly document any uncertain or missing distribution effects.

4.4.6. Sustainability

4.4.6.1. Introduction

Definition and scope

EU-CEM defines the sustainability impact area as follows:

The sustainability impact area addresses the implications of CCAM, assessing specifically the impacts on environmental integrity, social well-being, and economic vitality. It examines the capacity of CCAM to meet current needs, while not compromising resource and opportunity availability for future generations.

In this chapter, sustainability refers to a global state where present needs are met without compromising the ability of future generations to meet theirs. It includes three dimensions—environmental, social, and economic—consistent with the United Nations Brundtland Commission’s 1987 definition of sustainable development [117].

The outputs from previous impact areas can be used when evaluating the sustainability impacts of CCAM. CCAM is likely to have positive effects in some areas and negative in others, and these impacts may vary between the societal scenarios under consideration. The sustainability impact area is thus an integrated evaluation of all impacts addressed within EU-CEM (see Figure 5). It provides the means to summarise indicator results from different impact areas and contextualise their implications for the sustainability of the transport system and society. Although sustainability impact assessment mainly concerns the societal scenarios level, impacts may also be analysed at the transport system level (see Chapter 4.3) using traffic scenarios to identify the conditions under which benefits are maximised and disbenefits minimised (see Chapter 3.3 for the description of the different scenario levels).

In the context of transport, the European Union [118] defines sustainable transport system as one that:

- Ensures that basic access and development needs of individuals, businesses, and societies are met safely and in a manner consistent with human and ecosystem health, while promoting equity across and between generations.
- Operates fairly and efficiently, offering an affordable choice of transport modes and supporting a well-balanced economy and regional development.
- Limits emissions and waste to within the planet’s ability to absorb them. Uses renewable resources at or below their generation rates, and uses non-renewable resources at or below the development rates of renewable substitutes, all while minimising impacts on land use and noise generation.

For CCAM to contribute to sustainability, it must be deployed in a way that promotes sustainability across as many impact areas as possible rather than deteriorate it. A comprehensive consideration of CCAM’s impacts across various impact areas provides insights into its overall sustainability.

The chapter provides guidance on summarising, visualising, and interpreting the results of CCAM impact assessments from a sustainability perspective. It is important to note that this chapter does not determine whether a CCAM system is absolutely sustainable; rather, it examines changes in sustainability relative to the baseline scenario chosen for the impact assessments (see Chapter 3.3 for details on societal scenarios and baselines). Thus, the analysis indicates whether CCAM is more or less sustainable than the existing transport system for the defined societal scenarios.

Background

The Brundtland Commission's 1987 definition of sustainability divides the concepts into three pillars: environment, society, and economy (or planet, people, and profit). Figure 45 shows three alternative representations of these pillars:

- **Venn diagram:** Sustainability is achieved where all three pillars overlap, indicating a balance between environmental, social, and economic needs.
- **Nested model:** Economic needs are nested within societal needs, which in turn are nested within the environment (i.e. within planetary boundaries, see below). This model emphasises the importance of long-term ecological integrity over short-term economic gains.
- **Pillars model:** The three pillars are depicted as literal supports for sustainability, emphasising that the needs of society, the environment, and the economy must be considered equally.

Figure 45. Three ways to illustrate three pillars of sustainability: Venn diagram, nested model and three pillars.

Two distinct approaches to sustainability are identified:

- **Weak sustainability:** focuses on preserving the overall stock of assets for future generations. Under this concept, one asset may be substituted for another, provided the aggregate amount is maintained. For example, if one food source is depleted, another can replace it.
- **Strong sustainability:** Emphasises the preservation of irreplaceable assets or critical natural capital, such as the global climate system, biodiversity, and clean water. It recognises that certain damages are irreversible (e.g. biodiversity loss) and, therefore, the corresponding natural assets must be protected without substitution.

The distinction between weak and strong sustainability lies in ambition and the irreversibility of certain changes. Under strong sustainability, the pillars do not hold equal weight. When environmental degradation threatens to approach a point of irreversibility, these environmental concerns should be prioritised over societal and economic considerations and be considered non-negotiable.

To define an environmentally sustainable operating space within Earth's limits, nine planetary boundaries have been identified [119][120]:

1. Climate change
2. Biosphere integrity (health, extent, and diversity loss of organisms and ecosystems)
3. Stratospheric ozone depletion
4. Ocean acidification
5. Biogeochemical flows (disruption of nitrogen and phosphorus cycles)
6. Freshwater change (disruption of water cycles)
7. Land system change (transformation of natural landscapes)
8. Atmospheric aerosol loading
9. Introduction of novel entities to the Earth system (e.g. chemical pollution).

Reduction targets have been set for several of these boundaries. CCAM can affect several planetary boundaries. For example, an increase in vehicle kilometres travelled could lead to higher greenhouse gas and pollutant emissions. Similarly, CCAM can require changes in road space allocation and activity locations, potentially changing land use. The production and disposal of extra electronic equipment required by CCAM could introduce novel entities into the environment, leading to chemical pollution. Not all planetary boundaries are relevant in every CCAM system, and projects should decide which they expect to be relevant for the system under evaluation.

Another consideration is the *paradox of poverty* and the *paradox of affluence* [121]. In countries where the poverty paradox applies, priorities focus on meeting essential needs and ensuring minimum consumption standards. Conversely, once a certain income-per-capita threshold is surpassed, the *paradox of affluence* takes effect, meaning that increased consumption may contribute to escalating global and long-term environmental impacts, such as climate change and biodiversity loss.

CCAM systems are likely to be deployed first in high-income countries where the paradox of affluence applies. Therefore, a primary concern is to preserve nature's life support systems (strong sustainability). This means that CCAM should be designed to facilitate the alignment of lifestyles, values, behaviours, consumption, energy use, and resource use with the planet's ecological boundaries. However, even in wealthy nations, there are population groups and regions with unmet basic mobility needs. Therefore, all three pillars must be addressed.

4.4.6.2. Guidelines

Indicator recommendations

The sustainability impact assessment does not provide new result indicators but rather interprets the impacts found in the other impact areas from a sustainability perspective. Projects should incorporate, where possible, indicators representing all three pillars of sustainability: environmental, societal, and economic. If resources are limited, the evaluation should prioritise indicators expected to show a substantial effect (either positive or negative) compared to the baseline scenario. Even if only one or a few impact areas are quantitatively assessed, their sustainability implications should still be considered.

Impact pathways

In principle, every impact area and its indicators can contribute to the sustainability evaluation, with a few exceptions—such as technical functioning (Chapter 4.1.1), driving behaviour (Chapter 4.1.2), and user evaluation (Chapter 4.2.1)—which affect sustainability indirectly via other impact areas.

Overview of approaches and methods

Selecting an appropriate method for evaluating sustainability impacts of CCAM ensures relevant and reliable results. The choice depends on the project's objectives, available resources, tools, and data (see Chapter 3.3 for further details). For completeness, the potential sustainability impacts of non-studied impact areas may also be qualitatively assessed.

A simple way to visualise sustainability impacts is to display outcomes from the considered impact areas side by side. A **sustainability table**, which lists indicators and their outcomes for each impact area, provides a practical approach. This table can show both absolute and relative results and provide context for the sustainability evaluation.

A template for a sustainability table is provided in Table 68. Projects should adapt it to include the impact areas they consider. It can also be modified, for example extended to display multiple impact columns for alternative societal scenarios (see Table 69). When it is unclear which direction of impact is positive or negative for sustainability (column *Context*), projects must define whether an increase or decrease is considered positive for sustainability. Where possible, known target and threshold values for specific indicators should be included. Impacts can be colour-coded to make interpretation easier (e.g. green for positive sustainability outcome, red for negative sustainability outcome).

Table 68. Template for reporting sustainability impacts in a sustainability table (a full template is available in the CCAM knowledge base). Colour coding is recommended for visualisation: green for positive impacts, red for negative, and grey for no impact.

Impact area	Indicator	Impact	Context
Impact area X	Indicator X.1	[Result]	Positive/negative for sustainability
	Indicator X.2	[Result]	Positive/negative for sustainability

Table 69. Template for reporting sustainability impacts in a sustainability table across different scenarios (or CCAM systems, etc.), shown side by side. Colour coding is recommended for visualisation: green for positive impacts, red for negative, and grey for no impact.

Impact area	Indicator	Impact			Context
		Scenario 1	Scenario 2	Scenario 3	
Impact area X	Indicator X.1	[Result]	[Result]	[Result]	Positive/negative for sustainability
	Indicator X.2	[Result]	[Result]	[Result]	Positive/negative for sustainability
Impact area Y	Indicator Y.1	[Result]	[Result]	[Result]	Positive/negative for sustainability
	Indicator Y.2	[Result]	[Result]	[Result]	Positive/negative for sustainability

Especially when several impact areas and societal scenarios are studied, the table can become large. It is likely that the sustainability table will show both positive and negative impacts. The interpretation of these mixed results, i.e. what they mean for the sustainability of CCAM, is left to the project team and stakeholders. Such interpretations and conclusions are likely to reflect political choices: decision-makers may assign different importance to different impact areas based on specific policy goals.

As an example, two methods are introduced for assessing the sustainability impacts of CCAM based on impact area-specific results, allowing general conclusions to be drawn on the overall impacts:

Multi-criteria analysis (MCA) [122] offers a systematic approach for evaluating multiple, potentially conflicting criteria in decision-making. Different criteria can be combined into a single aggregated value ('score') by assigning weights, which may be determined by consulting the project team, relevant stakeholders, and external experts. However, MCA has limitations: the weighting can be difficult to determine, and results depend heavily on the expertise and effort of the stakeholders involved. Participatory evaluation methods can help ensure that the weights reflect broader citizen opinions.

SWOT analysis [123] (Strengths, Weaknesses, Opportunities, and Threats) offers a qualitative framework for interpreting sustainability impacts. By examining each impact area's results, the strengths (green cells in the sustainability table) and weaknesses (red cells) of CCAM from a sustainability perspective can be clearly understood. Green cells provide a basis for assessing opportunities and red cells for potential threats when upscaling the service to new regions. Similar to MCA, the results of the SWOT analysis depend on the stakeholders and experts involved. It provides an overview of the approaches described above. It highlights the strengths, weaknesses, and requirements of each method, helping to identify those that best align with the project's objectives, resources, and specific evaluation aspects. It is important to note that, even when the cons outnumber the pros, one pro can outweigh multiple cons.

Table 70 provides an overview of the approaches described above. It highlights the strengths, weaknesses, and requirements of each method, helping to identify those that best align with the project's objectives, resources, and specific evaluation aspects. It is important to note that, even when the cons outnumber the pros, one pro can outweigh multiple cons.

Table 70. An overview of approaches and methods for sustainability impact assessment.

Approach / Method	Pros	Cons	Requirements
Sustainability table	<p>Allows simultaneous visualisation of all dimensions contributing to sustainability.</p> <p>Provides an overview of positive and negative sustainability impacts from different impact areas.</p>	<p>Sometimes it may be challenging to determine whether an indicator's effect represents a positive or negative sustainability impact.</p>	<p>Results from other impact areas.</p> <p>Consensus on whether an increase or decrease in each indicator is beneficial, with clearly stated rationale.</p>
Multi-criteria analysis (MCA) [122]	<p>Allows systematic evaluation of multiple criteria in decision-making.</p> <p>Combines multiple criteria into a single aggregated score.</p>	<p>Assigning weights can be difficult.</p> <p>Results depend on stakeholders' expertise and effort.</p>	<p>Involvement of stakeholders with relevant expertise to establish appropriate weights across indicators.</p>

		Conclusions depend on which impact areas were assessed in the project.	
SWOT analysis [123]	Provides a qualitative framework to identify strengths, weaknesses, opportunities, and threats related to sustainability impacts. Facilitates visualisation of sustainability impacts. Allows upscaling in a qualitative way.	Results depend on stakeholders' expertise and effort. Conclusions depend on which impact areas were assessed in the project.	Results from other impact areas. Involvement of stakeholders with relevant expertise to provide balanced and representative insights across indicators.

Pitfalls and best practices

Evaluating the sustainability impacts of CCAM requires consideration of the methods and approaches used, as these can significantly influence the validity and reliability of the results. Overlooking potential pitfalls may lead to flawed conclusions, misinterpretation of findings, or unintended biases. By proactively addressing the pitfalls, these can be avoided.

Table 71 provides some common pitfalls of sustainability impact assessment and presents actionable best practices to address them.

Table 71. Pitfalls in sustainability impact assessment and best practices to avoid them.

Topic	Pitfall	Related best practice
Multi-criteria Analysis	Weights chosen in a non-systematic way.	Carefully select stakeholders for the weighting process and ensure their sample is representative. Perform sensitivity analysis with varying weights to assess the robustness of results.
	Inclusion of qualitative indicators can lead to debates about normalisation and weighting.	Assess the best way to present non-quantitative indicators, for example comparing with similar projects.
Assessing beneficialness of impact area results for sustainability	Defining whether results from an impact area are positive or negative from the sustainability impact perspective may not always rely on existing EU, national, or local targets or thresholds.	Research and align indicator target values with established sustainability goals and thresholds at the relevant level (EU, national, or local).

5. Guidelines for reporting evaluation outcomes and EU-CEM feedback

This chapter covers the reporting of the evaluation and impact assessment in CCAM projects. Reporting should not be seen as a mere administrative requirement but as an opportunity to reflect on the entire evaluation cycle, document lessons learned, and share insights with the different stakeholders.

Requirements for reporting the evaluation methodology and its outcomes can vary depending on the study commissioner. Evaluation reports are usually published at the end of the project when the evaluation is completed. However, they can also be released during the project, such as through a separate evaluation plan.

Although this chapter uses the term ‘evaluation report’ in the singular, reporting can include several interrelated documents depending on the project’s size and complexity.

5.1. Evaluation reporting

5.1.1. Reports for different stakeholders

Effective reporting addresses the distinct information needs of different audiences:

- **The project team** must thoroughly understand the details of the evaluation results to reach a consensus on the overall project outcomes and to guide further work and deployment.
- **The research community** needs sufficient information to judge the scientific validity of the methodology and results. They may use the report as a reference to compare with ongoing projects and plan future ones. If all the details of the methods and results do not fit into the project report, consider publishing them in supplementary scientific papers.
- **Decision-makers** need distilled information in an accessible format on the potential impacts of large-scale deployment. These summaries should be clear and actionable, allowing informed decisions on the future use and large deployment of CCAM, and show both the confidence and uncertainties of the evaluation results.
- **Other audiences**, including cities, the European Commission, traffic authorities, industry representatives, and user groups representing the general public, may primarily be interested in broader insights regarding CCAM and its potential contribution to societal goals.

Given these diverse audiences, it is recommended to produce multiple report formats, ranging from highly detailed technical documents to executive summaries and presentations. Particular attention should be given to effectively communicating information to stakeholders without technical, scientific, or evaluation-related backgrounds.

CCAM evaluation can be complex and produce estimates that indicate both desired and undesired impacts. For example, while CCAM may improve accessibility, a resulting increase in car traffic could lead to undesired consequences for traffic flow efficiency. Therefore, the communication of findings should be carefully planned to provide a clear and accurate overview of the impacts across multiple areas.

5.1.2. Reporting the evaluation methods and outcomes

Reports should clearly document the assumptions, methodological steps, and limitations of the evaluation process. Comprehensive reporting clarifies how outcomes and conclusions were reached, how the approach can be enhanced, and what research gaps remain. This facilitates knowledge transfer for future studies.

Several components are required in all evaluation reports, such as:

- The evaluation methodology, in line with Guideline 3.28 for reporting the evaluation plan.
- The evaluation results per impact area, research question, and indicator.
- Conclusions at all levels of evaluation, including limitations and future research needs.

Important note: A description of the CCAM system to be evaluated is produced at the beginning of the project (see Chapter 3.1). However, system attributes may change, or new details may emerge during the project—for example due to improvements in technology, system updates, technical challenges, or limitations of the testing environment. The evaluation report should include a summary of the CCAM system’s characteristics to clarify the evaluation outcomes.

Similarly, if an evaluation plan was published early in the project, updates to the methodology likely occurred as the project progressed. The final evaluation report should accurately reflect the methodology used to obtain the results. It is good practice to ensure that the reports are self-contained without the need to reference other reports for essential information.

It is important for the project team to discuss how the results should be presented and whether any of the data used for evaluation can be openly shared. Even if raw data cannot be made public, related materials such as data formats and video coding categories could benefit future projects. Refer to the Data Sharing Framework [18] for guidelines on sharing data and other information.

The evaluation report should answer all research questions and consider any hypotheses. If some research questions remain unanswered, the report should explain the reason for this. Answers to research questions and related indicator values should be structured according to the research question in the evaluation plan (see Guideline 3.6). A summary table can provide an overview of the research questions and their answers. The sustainability table (see Table 69) also serves this purpose.

Besides presenting results, providing context and interpretation is essential, as results alone are often insufficient for fully understanding the underlying phenomena. For example, it is crucial to communicate whether observed impacts on traffic flow efficiency resulted from shorter headways or differences in speed. A thorough understanding of causality helps users of the results maximise the benefits and minimise the drawbacks of CCAM.

Chapter 4 lists indicators for evaluating impacts across each impact area that all projects should use. If any indicator cannot be evaluated, the reason must be reported in accordance with the ‘comply or explain’ principle of EU-CEM.

Impact estimates usually involve some level of uncertainty. Therefore, this uncertainty should be addressed together with the related impact estimates. Use impact tables and causal loop diagrams for a clear overview of effects.

Conclusions can be drawn at all evaluation levels and in an overarching manner, not forgetting insights on the impacts of CCAM on sustainability. Chapter 4.4.6 gives recommendations for this process. In addition, it is important to list topics considered important for future research on the most significant aspects that lack understanding or knowledge.

The process of formulating and reporting the main conclusions requires discussion and reflection. It is recommended to start this well in advance, for example several months before the deadline, to ensure that the conclusions are well supported and understood by the entire consortium. The potential business interests of partners should be respected, but this does not mean that the evaluation team should avoid reporting conclusions unfavourable to the CCAM system. Rather, it is essential to present transparently all intended and unintended results.

The evaluation team should be aware of potential pressure from stakeholders seeking desired results, especially if they have invested heavily in the CCAM system. However, research ethics [124] must always take precedence. The evaluation team should provide clear, factual explanations especially when results do not meet initial expectations. Conclusions drawn directly from the evaluation results should be separated from expert opinions and expectations.

5.2. Reporting lessons learned and applicability of EU-CEM guidelines

The EU-CEM Handbook is designed to be enhanced over time through insights, lessons learned, and feedback from the CCAM community. Therefore, feedback on EU-CEM is appreciated to benefit future projects. A form is available for that purpose in the [Knowledge Base on Connected and Automated Driving \(CAD\)](#). Additionally, the EU-CEM developer team can be contacted at info@connectedautomateddriving.eu.

For deriving this feedback, it is recommended that at the end of the evaluation, the evaluation team reflects on the evaluation process. Consider questions such as:

- What went well?
- What did not, and why?
- Was EU-CEM helpful in the process? How could it be improved?

The EU-CEM developer team is interested in hearing:

- Was EU-CEM followed, what were the deviations and the reasons for them?
- Which chapters of EU-CEM provided useful guidelines? In what way, and where, were they not applicable or useful?
- What new best practices did the project successfully implement, and which ones would you recommend to others?
- What new or updated guidelines and impact areas would be useful in future updates of the EU-CEM? Were all relevant use-case perspectives covered? Were there other gaps identified in the EU-CEM?

5.3. Further guidance

For further guidance on research into Connected, Cooperative, and Automated Mobility, please visit the [Knowledge Base on Connected and Automated Driving \(CAD\)](#).

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Appendix

Table A 1. Indicator recommendations in alphabetical order and their respective impact areas. Impact area names below are hyperlinks that provide quick access to the corresponding chapters.

Indicator short name	Impact area
Acceleration sum	Driving behaviour
Acceptance	User
Accident risk	Traffic safety
Accident severity	Traffic safety
Affordability	Accessibility
Air quality exposure	Energy and environment
Amount of travel	People mobility
Average speed per speed limit	Driving behaviour
Behaviour with the system	User
Benefit-cost ratio (BCR)	Socio-economics
CO ₂ emissions	Energy and environment
Community cohesion	Liveability
Current operational domain (COD) success rate	Technical functioning
Delay	Traffic flow efficiency
Density of housing	Land use
Disengagement rate	Technical functioning
Distribution of kilometres travelled over time	Transport activity and fleet composition
Duration	Logistics
Economic vitality	Liveability
Energy use	Energy and environment
Fleet composition	Transport activity and fleet composition
Frequency of and/or % of distance driven in driving scenarios	Driving behaviour

Frequency of harsh braking events	Driving behaviour
Frequency of Minimal Risk Manoeuvres (MRM)	Technical functioning
Frequency of system failures	Technical functioning
Gross Domestic Product (GDP)	Economic activity and employment
Housing and land prices	Land use
Labour market demand for skills	Economic activity and employment
Land use distribution	Land use
Length of trips	People mobility
Local transport accessibility	Liveability
Median headway in car-following	Driving behaviour
Mobility options	Accessibility
Modal split	Transport activity and fleet composition
Mode share	People mobility
Monetised benefits	Socio-economics
Net benefit	Socio-economics
Net present value (NPV)	Socio-economics
Noise exposure	Energy and environment
Non-user experience	User
Number of businesses	Economic activity and employment
Number of jobs	Economic activity and employment
Operational costs	Services and operation
Pollutant emissions	Energy and environment
Population density	Land use
Productivity	Economic activity and employment
Property damage only accidents	Traffic safety
Public health	Liveability

Punctuality	Logistics
Quality of environment	Liveability
Quality of service	Services and operation
Reachable activities	Accessibility
Reachable people, households, or businesses	Accessibility
Resilience	Traffic flow efficiency
Road injuries or injury accidents	Traffic safety
Scalability and replicability	Services and operation
Societal cost	Socio-economics
Throughput	Traffic flow efficiency
Timing of trips	People mobility
Total kilometres travelled	Transport activity and fleet composition
Transport efficiency	Logistics
Transshipment time	Logistics
Travel time	Traffic flow efficiency
Travel time reliability	Traffic flow efficiency
Understandability of mobility options	Accessibility
User experience	User
Value of travel time	People mobility
Vehicle utilisation	Services and operation
Viability of business model	Services and operation
Waiting time	Logistics